

Deliverable D3.4:

**Guidance Document – Cost-
Benefit-Analysis in freshwater
ecosystem restoration**

Imprint

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MERLIN Key messages

- 1. Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) is essential for evidence-based freshwater restoration planning. CBA can support both public and private investment.**
- 2. Freshwater ecosystem restoration delivers multiple co-benefits (or ecosystem services).**
- 3. Valuing ecosystem services in a freshwater context requires tailored approaches.**
- 4. This guidance complements existing CBA frameworks, focusing on how to assess the costs and benefits of freshwater ecosystem restoration.**
- 5. Seven ecosystem services are included: biomass provision; flood risk mitigation; carbon sequestration; nutrient retention; drought mitigation; recreation and habitat provision.**
- 6. A coupled biophysical – economic modelling tool developed by MERLIN enables users to assess the effects of restoration on flood risk mitigation and nutrient retention using EU-wide datasets**
- 7. Real-world case studies – including the use of CBA on 5 MERLIN Case Studies – are presented to show how the methods work in practice.**

Acronyms

Acronyms	
BEAM	Basic European Asset Map
CBA	Cost Benefit analysis
CS	Case Study
CO ₂ e	Carbon dioxide equivalent
DR	Discount rate
EA	Economic Appraisal
EAD	Expected Annual Damage
EEA	European Environment Agency
ES	Ecosystem Service
ETS	Emissions Trading System
EU	European Union
FWE	Fresh Water Ecosystem
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GWP	Global Warming Potential
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
LAWA	Länderarbeitsgemeinschaft Wasser (German Working Group on Water Issues)
N	Nitrogen
NPV	Net Present Value
P	Phosphorus
SCC	Social Cost of Carbon
SP	Stated Preference
SWAT	Soil and Water Assessment Tool
VCMS	Voluntary Carbon Market System
WTA	Willingness to accept
WTP	Willingness to pay

MERLIN Executive Summary

Applying Cost Benefit Analysis to support freshwater ecosystems restoration

This guidance document provides targeted support for applying Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) in the planning and assessment of freshwater ecosystems restoration. CBA is widely used across the European Union to justify public investments, particularly under legal frameworks such as the Floods and Water Framework Directive and Nature Restoration Regulation.

Applying CBA to freshwater restoration is challenging due to data gaps, uncertainty, and the complexity of valuing ecological and social co-benefits. This guidance offers practical methods for integrating ecosystem service (ES) values into CBA. It covers flood and drought risk mitigation, nutrient retention, carbon sequestration, recreation, habitat provision and is supported by five MERLIN case studies and the German AMBERS project. It details how to identify, quantify, and monetise key ES benefits using biophysical modelling (notably SWAT+) and economic valuation (sections 4-12). We provide starting points for the estimation of restoration costs (Section 3), and discuss how CBA can inform the development of private co-funding of restoration (Section 13).

The guidance is intended for practitioners conducting CBAs, as well as decision-makers and project developers commissioning or interpreting them. It helps users understand what CBA can offer, how to structure it effectively, and how to use it to support transparent, evidence-based planning and investment decisions. This is not a comprehensive manual for conducting CBAs but a practical resource for incorporating ecosystem services into CBA and should be used alongside generic CBA guidance documents.

Estimating restoration costs

Costs of restoration generally include investment/construction costs, land acquisition or opportunity costs, and recurring costs. Although literature-based estimates or unit costs can be used in strategic planning phase, these are often scarce or inconsistent for freshwater restoration measures: When available, site-specific estimates are preferable, especially considering the high sensitivity of costs to context-specific factors (such as land price and accessibility).

Quantifying and monetising ecosystem services

Restoration generates a wide range of ecological, social, and economic effects. In a freshwater restoration context, the ecosystem services (ES) framework is often used to identify and describe benefits from interventions in natural ecosystems. There are three main categories of ecosystem services: provisioning (e.g. water supply, food production), regulating (e.g. water purification, flood control) and cultural (e.g. recreation, aesthetics). Quantifying impacts of restoration on ecosystem services involves linking restoration actions to ecological responses and societal benefits, often using hydrological or biophysical models.

Ecosystem service valuation methods are broadly divided into preference-based and market-based approaches. Preference-based methods aim to capture the value individuals place on ecosystem services based on their preferences. They are particularly useful for valuing non-market services such as cultural or recreational benefits. Market-based methods use existing price data or cost proxies and are best suited to provisioning services.

Flood risk mitigation

Freshwater ecosystems help reduce flood risks by storing and gradually releasing rainwater, which lowers run-off and flattens peak river flows. Restoration measures that expand or enhance these ecosystems provide significant flood risk mitigation benefits. These benefits can be valued either by estimating the costs of engineered flood protection that would otherwise be needed – known as replacement costs, or by calculating the damages avoided thanks to restoration – known as avoided damage costs. The avoided damage approach is best suited to areas with frequent flooding and little existing infrastructure, while the replacement cost approach is more appropriate in highly regulated systems where restoration can reduce the need for costly flood protection upgrades.

Climate change mitigation

Freshwater ecosystems are important carbon sinks, storing carbon in lakes, reservoirs, and wetland vegetation. The carbon sequestration potential of restoration efforts can be quantified by comparing carbon sequestration in baseline and restored scenarios, converting these to CO₂ equivalents, and assigning a monetary value per ton of CO₂e. Valuation approaches include emission trading prices, the social cost of carbon, or efficient CO₂ prices, with the choice depending on the purpose

and national guidelines. Market prices should generally be avoided in CBAs, as they do not reflect the full societal cost of emissions. Most EU or member state CBA guidance recommends using social cost of carbon or efficient prices.

Nutrient retention

Freshwater ecosystems help reduce nutrient pollution by retaining and removing excess nutrients through plant uptake, sediment storage and denitrification. Accurately valuing these benefits requires robust modelling, as nutrient retention depends on complex interactions in both land and water. For economic valuation, the replacement cost method — estimating what it would cost to achieve the same nutrient removal with constructed wetlands — can be used, or environmental damage costs. When using a replacement cost method, one should ensure there is societal demand for the replacement and that replacement is the least-cost alternative. Where possible, it is preferable to use national data on damage costs for more context-specific and reliable results.

Drought mitigation

Peatland and wetland restoration enhances a landscape's ability to absorb and slowly release water, improving soil moisture, supporting higher river baseflows, and boosting groundwater and reservoir recharge. Increased water availability during drought benefits hydropower generation (by stabilising low and high flows and reducing reservoir sedimentation), irrigated agriculture, and drinking water supply. The economic value of these benefits can be estimated using production functions, market prices, or cost-based methods, depending on the sector. Supporting river baseflow also helps maintain navigable water levels for shipping and supports water-based recreation, both of which are sensitive to water levels. For accurate valuation, localised assessments are essential, as drought impacts and recreational benefits are highly site-specific. However, impacts on irrigated crops can often be valued using standard crop and revenue data.

Recreation

Wetlands, floodplains, and rivers provide diverse recreation opportunities, from fishing and wildlife watching to hiking, cycling, and water sports. Restoration can boost recreation by increasing species diversity, improving water quality, and expanding accessible natural areas. The economic value of these benefits is typically estimated using preference-based or benefit transfer methods, based on either increased recreation capacity or the balance of supply and local demand. As more

recreation opportunities do not necessarily lead to higher use — benefits are greatest where unmet demand exists — it is preferable to take demand into account. Large-scale restoration can also attract visitors from outside the local area, so preferably both local and regional recreation dynamics are included in CBA.

Habitat provision

Habitat provision reflects the availability and quality of habitats in rivers and floodplains, underpinning biodiversity and supporting a range of regulating ecosystem services. Restoration measures like rewetting peatlands and reconnecting floodplains can significantly enhance habitat quality and diversity. Quantifying habitat provision relies on indicators such as habitat area, connectivity, and species composition: as there is no internationally agreed best practice, indicators and modelling approaches are often tailored to the local context. Economic valuation typically uses non-market approaches, including preference-based methods or benefit transfer, to estimate the non-use value people place on biodiversity. Cost-based methods can also be used to estimate total restoration value but should not be combined with other ES valuations to avoid double counting.

Biomass provision

Freshwater ecosystem restoration can affect biomass provision by changing land use and/or biophysical conditions, influencing the production of food, fibre, fodder, or energy crops. Biomass provision is best quantified as harvested yield (e.g., tons per hectare), using national or EU agricultural statistics or field data. For social CBA, it is recommended to value biomass provision using total yields multiplied by market prices. Methods that separate ecosystem and human contributions — such as production functions, land rental prices, or resource rents — can be used for assessing impacts on the farming sector specifically.

Connecting CBA to private benefits

The main goal of a CBA is to assess whether restoration benefits society as a whole, not just specific sectors. However, by identifying and quantifying a broad range of societal benefits, a CBA can also inform private co-funding opportunities — such as those linked to markets for biomass, recreation, or carbon credits. To inform private actors' business cases, costs and benefits have to be attributed to specific stakeholders, and valuation methods that reflect actual revenues or cost savings should be used. Other key differences between CBA and business cases include the timing and time horizon of

benefits, and the level of detail included in the cost assessment.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Cost benefit analysis: what and why

Across Europe, (social) cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is a widely used tool to justify public investments and prioritise projects. In a CBA, the economic viability of a project or policy is evaluated by comparing investment costs to benefits, which are both determined in relation to a baseline scenario where no intervention occurs. The purpose of the analysis is to evaluate how a project or policy impacts the overall well-being of a society and to determine if undertaking a project is desirable from a socioeconomic perspective.

There can be many reasons for undertaking a CBA. Some European countries mandate a minimum benefit-cost ratio as a requirement for funding projects related to flood risk management (ICPDR, 2021). Although the instrument is especially well-established for larger projects and often conditional to receiving grants, there are various benefits of doing a CBA regardless of whether it is mandatory: CBA can help identify the preferred alternative from a range of options, increase transparency in decision-making, support optimisation of project design, support stakeholder dialogue and inform the development of cost-sharing and funding strategies by identifying costs and benefits incurred by stakeholders.

1.2 CBA to support freshwater investment planning in the EU

In each member state, national institutions (e.g. Ministries for Environment, Water or Nature) set the framework in which restoration takes place, based on national and EU laws such as the Floods Directive, Habitat Directive, Water Framework Directive and Nature Restoration Regulation. This framework dictates mandates, budgets and/or funding access, timelines, and overall planning procedures. Strategic planning and project development may be done by public or private (conservation) actors, depending on governance structures and land ownership at the relevant scale. Investments in restoring freshwater ecosystems may come about in various ways: either driven by compliance with EU and/or national or local policies (for example, costs and benefits of measures included in the Nature Restoration Plans have to be assessed) or through bottom-up private restoration or conservation initiatives. We note that regarding the latter, the instrument of social cost-benefit analysis is not to estimate costs and benefits for specific sectors. To make CBA outcomes more valuable for informing funding strategies, including e.g. compensation schemes or cost-sharing keys, some additional steps may be needed (see Section 13).

Use of CBA in EU member states

Many EU Member States have embedded use of CBAs or similar instruments (e.g. cost-effectiveness or multi-criteria-analysis) into infrastructure planning procedures (Cools & Interwies, 2024): especially for larger projects or strategy level (e.g. water basin management plans) CBA is often mandatory. EU (co-) financed or large-scale projects typically require a rapid or extended CBA as part of the project selection and approval process. On investments involving climate change adaptation, risk prevention and disaster resilience in the water sector, the EU Economic Appraisal Vademecum (Sartori & Marra, 2020) states that decisions should be based 'on a thorough assessment of the economic costs and benefits, to inform the technical development of the project in an iterative process and to ensure that the outcome can reach a balance between affordability and sustainability.'

Tailoring the analysis to the planning phase and scale

Restoration in key freshwater ecosystems - including lakes and ponds, rivers and streams, and wetlands (including peatlands) - takes place at various scales (Figure 1). Large-scale efforts include development of strategic plans or investment programs at the (large) river or basin scale (regional or landscape scale); smaller-scale efforts focus on projects within a smaller watershed, river sections (e.g. upper, middle and lower course) or individual floodplains (local scale). The scope and set-up of the CBA should be tailored to the scale of the restoration effort, as CBA can be quite resource-intensive (Cools & Interwies, 2024). To support project prioritisation in the strategic planning phase, a rapid assessment of costs and benefits should be done for each potential project, potentially combined with semi-quantitative policy-led multi-criteria analysis (Sartori & Marra, 2020). Such a 'rapid' or quick scan CBA aims to deliver a quick overview of expected cost and benefits, relying on simplified assumptions, models and readily available data, and focuses on major impacts only. Projects selected for implementation at the local or regional scale should be evaluated with an extended CBA. This is a more detailed and comprehensive analysis, using detailed modelling and valuation of impacts, local/context-sensitivity data collection and analysis, stakeholder consultation and expert input, and including distributional effects and uncertainty analysis. This guideline focuses on the regional to supra-regional scale and presents a range of methods, which are suited to different needs, for both types of CBA - from rapid costs

and benefits assessment (using default data available at the EU level) to detailed in depth extended CBA (using local data).

Figure 1 - Schematic overview of type of CBA depending on scale of investment planning. In the red line, the focus of this guidance report.

1.3 Key target audience

This guidance document is meant for:

- (Economic) consultants who want to develop a strategic –level / catchment scale CBA in a context of freshwater ecosystems restoration: the guidance serves as a starting point.
- Restoration project developers or decision makers planning to commission a CBA and/ or interpret and use its results. It will help to: a) better understand how CBA works and what it can(not) bring; b) identify required data and inputs; and c) facilitate interpretation of results.

1.4 What is in this guidance?

Although guidelines may exist in Member States on whether and how to execute CBAs in specific contexts, as well as guidelines for CBAs for Nature-Based solutions (van Zanten et al., 2023; EC, 2021), there is little guidance on how to value freshwater restoration specifically (Interwies & Cools, 2024). This guidance discusses how impacts of restoration efforts on freshwater ecosystem services can be quantified and monetised in a CBA at the catchment-landscape strategy level. Conducting a CBA in a freshwater restoration context can be challenging, due to a lack of assessment tools, limited cost data (Aerts 2018) and knowledge gaps in understanding relations between physical, ecological and socio-economic benefits. To address these challenges, this report provides guidance on 1) cost assessment, and 2) how biophysical data can be coupled with socio-economic metrics to monetise key ecosystem services. This report focuses on key restoration impacts identified in the MERLIN restoration cases and is therefore not exhaustive; additional reading is provided where relevant. It is not intended as a comprehensive guidance document covering all steps of a CBA and should therefore be used in conjunction with general CBA frameworks. Given the limited number of cases and examples included in our report, it is not possible (nor intended) to draw general conclusions about the magnitude or scope of freshwater restoration benefits from this report.

Lessons learnt and recommendations of this guidance document draw upon

- CBA carried out in 5 MERLIN case studies, where benefits of restoration on hydrological services (i.e. flood risk mitigation, nutrient retention) have been quantified and monetised using hydrological modelling (e.g. SWAT+, see MERLIN Deliverable 3.3) and monetary valuation methods;

- Examples of valuation approaches at the local project level scale from the German ‘AMBERS’ project (Roesch et al., 2025), which developed an assessment tool to quantify and monetise ecosystem services to compare different measure variants along waterways;
- Scientific literature on CBA of freshwater ecosystem restoration and the assessment of ES supplied by freshwater ecosystems.

Section 2 includes a generic introduction of the CBA methodology highlighting specific aspects of CBAs in the context of freshwater ecosystems restoration. Section 3 provides a short overview of how to approach a cost assessment. Section 4 provides a short overview of how to identify key benefits of a proposed project in general, quantify and monetise (or value) them. Section 5 briefly addresses methods to value bundles of ESs. Sections 6 through 12 discuss quantification and valuation approaches and lessons learned from MERLIN cases studies for specific ES: flood risk mitigation (Section 6), climate change mitigation (Section 7), nutrients retention (Section 8), drought risk mitigation (Section 9), recreation (Section 10), habitat provision (Section 11) and biomass provision (Section 12). Section 13 discusses how to adapt or complement a social CBA with valuation methods more suited to inform development of (private) business cases for freshwater ecosystem restoration.

2 Cost-benefit analysis in freshwater restoration

2.1 The CBA methodology in general

In general, any CBA starts with a description of the scope of the problem and/or objective of the envisioned project or policy. Then, the most likely development in absence of the project or policy is described - e.g. the expected development over time of the ecosystem condition under climate and anthropogenic pressures. Building on this, various project or policy alternatives are defined, generally distinct packages of a range of individual measures. After this, investments costs (both one-off and recurring) are determined, and benefits of the proposed measures. This starts with identification of main benefits of the intervention: the most significant expected benefits will then be quantified and possibly monetised. At the last stage, all costs and benefits incurred over the future are calculated to the same base year using a discount rate, to account for time preferences and inflation, and presented in an overview table. Analysis of main uncertainties - for example in prices of specific services or investments (e.g. sediments, carbon) or in the discount rates used and assumptions on the outcome - informs final interpretation and presentation of results. At this step, it is also valuable to attribute costs and benefits to specific stakeholders or - groups. This guidance document is focused on the determination of costs and benefits of freshwater ecosystem restoration projects (Figure 2). We refer the reader to references in the further reading section below for complete guidance documents on CBA.

Figure 2 - steps in a CBA (adapted from Romijn/Renes 2013); in the red line, the focus of this guidance report.

2.2 Challenges and solutions for CBA in freshwater ecosystems restoration

Economic appraisal of restoration in general, and specifically in freshwater ecosystems, is complicated due to several factors. It is good to be aware of these challenges and potential solutions to overcome such barriers when starting a CBA in the context of comparing project variants of freshwater ecosystems restoration.

Restoration and multi-functional solutions such as NbS require a wider scope in assessment

Common practice in CBA of infrastructure or water management is to focus on one or a few primary benefits for which the infrastructure project is designed. Nature-Based Solutions for traditional water management issues (which may contribute to restoration targets), as well as targeted freshwater restoration efforts often deliver multiple co-benefits beyond a single policy domain (e.g., flood risk or water quality). Thus, a wider or 'extended' scope in assessed benefits, ideally determined in coordination with a comprehensive set of multi-sectoral stakeholders, is essential for a sound economic evaluation (Cools & Interwies, 2024).

Use adaptive planning and sensitivity analysis to deal with uncertainty

In ecosystems restoration efforts and nature-based solutions, performance uncertainty stems from 1) unpredictability, e.g. due to natural variability and interconnected complex environmental processes, and 2) an incomplete knowledge of such complex processes, e.g. due to limited data availability or unreliable data (van der Lely et al., 2021.). In addition, uncertainty in results may arise from assumptions or choices made in monetary valuation. A solid sensitivity analysis of key assumptions (e.g. in dose-effect relations between hydrologic-biophysical and socio-economic impacts, discount rates, appraisal horizon and context-specific factors such as land price) and adopting an adaptive planning and management approach (e.g. using adaptation pathways (Haasnoot et al., 2013) or a Theory of Change approach (Pott et al., 2025)) can address these uncertainties. These aspects are beyond the scope of this guidance document, but useful resources on this topic are indicated in the further reading section below.

2.3 Final results – discounting and appraisal horizon

Converting future costs and benefits to the present

In cost-benefit analysis (CBA), discounting enables the comparison of values across time by converting future costs and benefits into present-day equivalents. The discount rate reflects how future values are perceived today, often based on time preference, inflation, and opportunity costs. The higher the discount rate, the lower the future benefits or costs are valued. If current and future benefits or costs are equally weighted, a discount rate of 0% is used (Bünge & Matthey, 2018). From a macroeconomic perspective, lower discount rates than market-based rates are used to give more weight to long-term societal impacts. This is particularly relevant in environmental valuation, where benefits and damages—such as those from ecosystem services or climate impacts—extend far into the future. For example, a 1% discount rate values a damage occurring in 30 years at 74% of its present value, but this percentage decreases rapidly with higher discount rates.

If monetary values are used that are not based on current price or cost data, these values must be adjusted to the year for which the analysis of project variants is carried out to reflect the economic situation of the respective year. In fact, all data must be adjusted to a reference year (Roesch et al., 2025).

Selecting the discount rate

Countries often have their own guidelines on which discount rates to use for project evaluations in different fields. For example, in the Netherlands social discount rates of 2.25% for benefits and 1.6% for costs are recommended, following Dutch guideline (Werkgroep & Discontovoet, 2020), reflecting lower financial risk for already incurred infrastructure investments (e.g. dikes). In some cases, a lower discount rate is recommended for environmental impacts and ecosystem services, because these benefits typically accrue over extensive time horizons and affect future generations. In Germany, a social discount rate of 1% is recommended for considering environmental impacts (Bünge & Matthey, 2018).

Alternatively, a relative price increase can be used for ecosystem services expected to become scarcer over time. Services with low substitutability and rising demand —such as biodiversity, landscape aesthetics, or recreation — may grow in value relative to general consumption. Applying a relative price increase adjusts for this expected scarcity and growth rate in value, which might surpass general consumption. Literature suggests price increases of 1-4% may be warranted (Heckenhahn & Drupp, 2024; Koetse & Rietveld, 2010).

Appraisal period

The appraisal period in cost-benefit analysis (CBA) should reflect the lifespan over which investments influence ecosystem service delivery, climate risks, and societal benefits. Conventional infrastructure projects typically use a 20–30 year horizon, while for nature-based solutions (NbS) or restoration projects, longer periods of 20–50 years are used to reflect slower ecological processes and extended benefit timelines (Contor, 2025). For intangible or long-term benefits—such as carbon sequestration, biodiversity recovery, and ecosystem resilience — even longer timeframes may be justified and recommended (van Zanten et al., 2023; O'Mahony, 2021). For example, the Dutch CBA guideline for integrated spatial development (ECORYS & WitteveenBos, 2009) advises using an appraisal period of at least 100 years for nature and water projects to reflect the enduring impacts of restoration on hydrological regimes, ecological functions, and climate adaptation.

Further reading: general CBA guidelines

- EC (2020) Economic Appraisal Vademecum 2021-2027. General Principles and Sector Applications. https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/publications/guides/2021/economic-appraisal-vademecum-2021-2027-general-principles-and-sector-applications
- EC (2014): Guide to Cost-Benefit Analysis of Investment Projects: Economic Appraisal tool for Cohesion Policy 2014-2020. https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/studies/cba_guide.pdf
- OECD (2006): Cost-Benefit Analysis and the Environment: Recent Development. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2006/01/cost-benefit-analysis-and-the-environment_g1gh604e.html
- HM Treasury (UK) (2022) The Green Book: Central Government Guidance on Appraisal and Evaluation. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-green-book-appraisal-and-evaluation-in-central-government>
- World Bank (2023). Assessing the Benefits and Costs of Nature-Based Solutions for Climate Resilience – a Guideline for Project Developers. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/entities/publication/9ed5cb4b-78dc-42a4-b914-23d71cef24a2>

3 Cost assessment

Costs of restoration generally include investment/construction costs and (land-) acquisition (one-off) costs, and (recurring) management costs. The costs of restoration depend on many variables, which may be very project or context-specific, e.g. relating to the design of restoration, regional variations in land prices, labour or energy costs. The REFORM project (Ayres et al., 2014) recommends a cost typology for river restoration (Table 1).

Table 1 – Restoration costs typology; adapted from (Ayres et al., 2014).

Type	Description
Planning and design costs	Costs incurred during project preparation, including project team set-up, data collection, set project objectives, planning and detailed design and implementation strategy.
Transaction costs	Costs other than investment or operation and maintenance costs incurred during planning and implementation phase, including for communication, legal fees, decision making processes, quality control.
Investment/Construction costs	Costs needed to physically implement the project, including e.g. labour, material and equipment, soil sanitation.
Land acquisition costs	Costs of land or property that needs to be acquired to implement the project – this may also take the form of compensation for current tenants.
Maintenance & monitoring costs	Annual costs needed for upkeep and repair of the restored area. This may also include monitoring costs to analyse changes in ecological and hydromorphic conditions.

The cost categories in bold are the most used in cost-benefit analysis. Instead of land acquisition costs, opportunity costs are often used, i.e. the foregone benefits that would have been received if land use was not changed (e.g. agricultural revenues).

Table 2 presents rough cost estimates from MERLIN Case Studies (CS) for some freshwater ecosystems (FWE) restoration measures. Box 3.1 and Box 3.2 provide examples of detailed analysis of restoration costs in two MERLIN CS. A detailed analysis of restoration costs incurred by all MERLIN CSs will be made available in Deliverable 2.5.

Table 2 - Implementation costs of restoration in a selection of MERLIN case studies.

Type of measures	Type of cost	€/stretch (km)	€/ha	Case Studies
Riparian buffer	Opportunity cost		2,526	MERLIN CS13. Sorraia floodplain
Peatland rewetting	Land works, ash fertilization, trees sowing, bog vegetation restoration, duckboards building		3,100	MERLIN CS14. Komppasuo peat extraction area
Peatland rewetting	Blocking of ditches, reprofiling of exposed peat		2,100	MERLIN CS17. Forth catchment
River channel restoration and floodplain reconnection	Ditches locking, scrapes creation, channels diversion, leaky dams, tree planting.		2,540	MERLIN CS17. Forth catchment
Floodplain reconnection	Dike setback (large river)	29 M (km)		MERLIN CS04. Room for the Rhine branches
Floodplain reconnection	Side channel (large river)	27 M (km)		MERLIN CS04. Room for the Rhine branches

Lessons learned & recommendations

- Cost data availability and granularity: Cost data for nature-based solutions and restoration measures is often scarce or inconsistent. At the catchment scale, literature-based unit-cost estimates can be used for strategic planning CBAs. However, at a more local planning and design scale it is advisable to obtain site-specific data: as illustrated by the case in the Netherlands (Box 3.2), net costs for floodplain reconnection varied significantly across river branches, influenced by factors such as urbanization, land prices, accessibility, and material availability. Site specific data can be obtained by commissioning cost assessments by engineering firms or consulting local contractors.
- Maintenance and monitoring are long-term commitments: Restoration is not a one-off investment. Long-term costs for upkeep and ecological monitoring should be included in cost estimates.
- Use of standardized cost typologies improves comparability: Applying frameworks like the REFORM cost typology helps structure cost data and facilitates comparison across projects and regions.

Further reading: restoration costs assessment

- [REFORM](#)
 - [D1.4: Inventory of restoration costs and benefits](#)
 - [D5.2: Cost effectiveness of river restoration](#)
- [Glenk et al., 2022: the cost of peatland restoration, data and analysis.](#)
- [Moxey and Moran \(2014\): UK peatland restoration: Some economic arithmetic](#)
- [Aerts \(2018\): a review of cost estimates for flood adaptation.](#)

Box 3.1: Estimating opportunity costs of riparian buffer zones in the Sorraia floodplain, Portugal (MERLIN CS 13)

Based on spatial analysis using buffer zones around streams (ARCGIS), the surface area of cropland to be converted to buffer zones was determined (860 ha). To break this down to specific crop types, two sources were used - generic crop data from the Portuguese COS2018 land use database (DG Território, 2018), and, where available, more detailed crop data provided by the local water authority (In absence of national or local data, the widely available CORINE database can be used). The resulting summarized areas per crop type were then connected to Standard Output Coefficients, the average monetary value of agricultural output at farm-gate price, in €/ha for specific crops (2023 price level; averaged for the Alentejo region in Portugal; derived from EU's Integrated Farm Statistics database <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/a9c5638c-8940-4e25-b6de-02ace3e161e7/library/23467ccb-9d33-4376-a877-95925673044b>). Annual opportunity costs were then discounted over a horizon of 100 years, at discount rate 3%.

As a result, the annual production loss related to installing riparian buffer strips in the Sorraia watershed is estimated at € 2.17 million (average €2526/ha), which accumulates to a present value of €70.8 million.

Box 3.2: Floodplain reconnection in the Netherlands: cost breakdown (MERLIN CS 04)

In the preparation phase of the Dutch 'Room for the River' Programme (2010-2020), a database of cost estimates for 1166 river widening measures was developed to support strategy design (Prins & Levelt 2015). This database can serve as input to derive average unit implementation costs (Table 3) and provide information on main cost elements (Figure 3).

Table 3 - Unit costs per measure type along the Rhine Branches in the Netherlands per river kilometre (stretch) in MEUR at price level 2023, including VAT (21%). Estimates include CAPEX and OPEX but exclude land acquisition costs. From Kok et al (submitted).

Mesure/river stretch	Upper Rhine, Waal and Merwede	Pannerdensch Kanaal and IJssel	Nederrijn/ Lek
Floodplain reconnection project (e.g. lowering)	30	12	12
Dike relocation	39	18	32
Construction of side channel or flood channel	22	38	21

Differences in unit costs per river branch can be due to factors such as the degree of urbanisation in the area. Overall, land acquisition (including right of superficies – right to own constructions on land owned by another person or entity) and compensation and physical works make up a large part of the costs. Costs for both land acquisition/compensation and physical works increase with urbanisation. Expected operation and maintenance costs were also derived from the cost database: 0.5% for floodplain reconnection projects and side channels, and 0.4% for dike relocation projects.

Figure 3 - Cost breakdown based on cost estimates of Room for the River database. From Kok et al (submitted)

4 Quantifying and monetising benefits

Restoration generates a wide range of ecological, social, and economic effects. Quantifying and monetising these effects or benefits, is the basis of a cost-benefit analyses. In a freshwater restoration context, the ecosystem services (ES) framework is often used to identify and describe benefits from interventions in natural ecosystems. This chapter outlines how freshwater restoration measures affect ecosystem services, and describes the process of identifying, quantifying, and valuing these benefits, referring to tools, existing databases, and relevant projects across Europe.

In most cases, the valuation of ecosystems restoration builds on the concept of ecosystem services (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2013), which link ecosystems to human well-being and the economy. Ecosystems provide a large range of services to people, categorised as provisioning services (e.g. water supply, biomass production), regulating services (e.g. climate regulation, flood risk mitigation) and cultural services (e.g. recreation, aesthetic value).

4.1 Identification & quantification

Freshwater ecosystem restoration measures can influence a wide array of ecosystem services, both positively and negatively. Identifying and selecting the most relevant benefits for evaluation is the first step. This requires understanding of how proposed interventions affect ecosystem services and which impacts are most critical for local stakeholders and policy objectives.

Different types of restoration measures influence ecosystem services in various ways. For instance, rewetting a floodplain may reduce provisioning services like crop production, while enhancing regulating services such as CO₂ sequestration, nutrient retention and flood mitigation. A good starting point to assess which ES are affected by the proposed interventions is to use matrices such as developed by Natural Water Retention Measures (NWRM) (<https://www.nwrn.eu/catalogue-nwrn/benefit-tables>) or the RESI project (Hornung et al., 2019) which visualise how interventions may positively or negatively impact the delivery of ES (Figure 4). Impacts in these matrices are based on existing experiences and literature (see e.g. Birk and al. 2025); of course, the relationship between restoration and a specific ES may vary from site to site, and such generic matrixes should be used with caution.

Interventions	Ecosystem Service										
	Provisioning			Regulatory and Supporting						Cultural	
	Water storage	Fish Stocks and Recruiting	Natural biomass production	Biodiversity preservation	Climate adaptation and mitigation	groundwater/ aquifer recharge	Flood risk reduction	Sediment Control	Water purification	Recreational opportunities	Aesthetic/ cultural value
Wetland restoration and management	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High
Floodplain restoration and management	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High
Remeandering	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High
Stream bed renaturalization	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High
Restoration and reconnection of seasonal streams	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High
Reconnection of oxbow lakes	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High
Riverbed material renaturalization	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High
Removal of dams and other longitudinal barriers	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High
Natural bank stabilisation	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High
Elimination of riverbank protection	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High
Lake restoration	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High
Restoration of natural infiltration to groundwater	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High
Renaturalisation of polder areas	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High	High

Figure 4 - Benefit table of freshwater ecosystems restoration measures and their likely effects on ES – adapted from nwrn.eu

It is important to consider not only the benefits of restoration, but also potential ecosystem disservices (EDS)—unintended negative impacts on human well-being, such as increased mosquitoes, ticks, or allergies from restored wetlands (Guo et al., 2022). Including these in assessments helps identify locally adapted, widely supported solutions. Expanding current evaluation methods and cost-benefit analyses to include both positive

and negative effects can ensure comprehensive, integrated planning processes and increase public support (Guo et al., 2022; Potgieter et al., 2019; Roy et al., 2012).

Before the impacts of proposed interventions can be monetised for the cost-benefit analysis, these impacts must be quantified. This involves tracing the links between restoration actions, ecological responses, and the benefits to society and nature. Quantification of the impact of freshwater ecosystems restoration interventions often requires hydrological and/ or biophysical modelling, using models and tools such as the hydrological SWAT+ and/or ES modelling tools such as InVEST ([Natural Capital Project Data Hub](#) | [Natural Capital Project](#)). In chapters 5-12 we discuss quantification approaches for specific ecosystem services in more detail.

4.2 Co-benefits; valuing ecosystem services monetary valuation

There are several types of methods to value ecosystem services in monetary terms, each with different levels of precision, data needs, and applicability. Broadly, valuation methods fall into two categories: preference-based methods and market-based methods. Preference-based methods aim to capture the value individuals place on ecosystem services based on their preferences. They are particularly useful for valuing non-market services such as cultural or recreational benefits. Market-based methods use existing market data or cost proxies to estimate the ecosystem service values – this approach is generally more straightforward but may not capture full welfare impacts. They are best suited to provisioning services. We shortly introduce main valuation methods for ecosystem services and main underlying assumptions.

Revealed Preference Methods estimate the value of an ecosystem service based on observed behaviour in actual markets or real-world decisions. Often used approaches include:

- The Travel Cost Method (TCM), in which the value of recreational sites is determined by analyzing how much people spend to visit them (both in time and money). This captures the consumer surplus from recreational activity, which reflects individual welfare gains. The underlying assumption is that the travel costs are an accurate reflection of the willingness to pay for the activity – this may be an over or underestimation (e.g. if people are also visiting other things; or would be willing to pay more).
- Hedonic Pricing, which involves evaluation of how environmental attributes (e.g. proximity to water bodies, good or bad water quality) influence property prices. This measures the marginal willingness to pay for environmental attributes. The underlying assumption is that markets are competitive, and buyers are fully informed – if this is not the case, the prices may be underestimated.

Stated Preference Methods estimate the value of an ecosystem service by directly asking individuals about their preferences in hypothetical scenarios. An advantage of this approach is that it can be used to capture non-use values such as the bequest/existence value of biodiversity. Often used approaches include:

- Contingent Valuation (CV), in which individuals are asked directly about their willingness to pay (WTP) for specific ecosystem services or restoration outcomes. Respondents are assumed to understand and truthfully respond to questions – as such, the approach is quite sensitive to survey design and biases, which may lead to under or overestimation of the WTP.
- Choice Experiments (CE) present respondents with different scenarios involving trade-offs, allowing estimation of marginal WTP for individual service attributes (e.g. 10% increase in water quality, biodiversity, recreational opportunities). The underlying assumption is that respondents understand and evaluate trade-offs well – this requires careful experimental design. Similar to contingent valuation, biases may still apply though the risk is lower with choice experiments.

Market-Based Methods use existing market data or cost proxies to estimate ES value. Often used approaches include:

- The Market Price approach uses actual prices of goods and services (e.g. fish, timber) to value provisioning services. The underlying assumption is that markets are efficient and stable, and that prices reflect true value – meaning that the price indeed reflects the willingness to pay for a service, and there are no significant externalities.
- Production Function approaches estimate how ES contributes to economic outputs (e.g. how pollinators affect crop yields). This requires a clear, well-understood causal relationship between the ES and production of the marketed good: a detailed production function as well as detailed models and data to estimate the impact are required and, in practice, are often unavailable.

Cost-Based Methods estimate the value of services based on the costs that would be incurred if those services were lost or had to be replaced by human-made alternatives. These methods do not measure people's preferences directly and but can be useful if preference-based data is unavailable or too complex to derive. Often used approaches include:

- The Replacement Cost approach, which estimates the cost of replacing an ES with man-made alternatives (e.g. a wetland can be replaced with a water treatment plant). The underlying assumption is that artificial substitutes can fully and efficiently replace ecosystem services, and that this would indeed be done if services were lost. Values may be underestimated (e.g. if a service is only partially substitutable) or overestimated (if replacement costs are inflated or over dimensioned).
- The Avoided Damage cost approach, which values services based on the costs they help prevent (e.g. flood regulation reducing property damage). The underlying assumption is that it is possible to accurately estimate avoided damage – and that this is a good reflection of individual WTP (disregarding the risk appetite of individuals).

If primary valuation studies are not feasible due to time, budget, or data constraints, **benefit transfer methods** offer a practical alternative, which requires limited resources. These methods estimate the value of ecosystem services by transferring results from existing studies conducted in similar contexts. There are two main types of benefit transfer:

- Unit Value Transfer, in which a single value (e.g., € per hectare) from a different study site is used in the evaluation.
- Benefit transfer functions, often based on a meta-regression model analyzing a wide range of values from different study sites, which allows for accounting for site-specific variables.

Both these approaches are sensitive to transfer errors – if sites, interventions or population differ, values can be over – or underestimated.

States preference and benefit transfer methods may be applied to value a bundle of ESs provided by freshwater ecosystem restoration, but this was not tested in MERLIN. Nevertheless, this approach may be relevant in given contexts and is therefore briefly discussed in Section 5. In Chapters 6-12 we present and discuss monetary valuation approaches for specific ecosystem services in more detail.

Note that there is an important difference in valuing ecosystem services in the context of CBA and in the context of ecosystem accounting (e.g., following the System of Environmental Economic Accounting or SEEA). In the first case, welfare values are used, that include changes in the value of both consumer and producer surpluses resulting from a project or policy. In the latter case, exchange values are used, that do not include consumer surplus and where values are consistent with the values found in national accounts. This report focusses on welfare based valuation, whereas the SEEA Ecosystem Accounting (United Nations, 2024) provides more insights in the valuation methods relevant for ecosystem accounting.

Further reading:

- **Identification and quantification of restoration benefits**
- Benefit tables – linking ecosystem services and measures:
 - [NWRM benefit tables](#)
 - Hornung et al. (2019) [Linking ecosystem services and measures in river and floodplain management](#)
- Vermaat et al. (2013) REFORM [D2.3 Valuing the ecosystem services provided by European river corridors – an analytical framework](#); includes a list of ecosystem services potentially provided by river corridors, alongside key abiotic and biotic conditions, relevant scale and societal beneficiaries.
- Grizetti et al. (2015) [EU cookbook for watershed-scale ecosystem service indicators for rivers](#)
- RESI River Project (Germany): Various studies on spatial tools and matrices for ES trade-offs ((Hornung et al., 2019; Podschun et al., 2018; Stammel et al., 2021).
- United Nations (2022). Guidelines on Biophysical Modelling for Ecosystem Accounting. United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Statistics Division, New York.
- MERLIN Deliverable 3.3: [The MERLIN modelling workflow to assess the biophysical and economic impact of freshwater ecosystem restoration at catchment scale](#)
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Monetary valuation of restoration benefits

- UN- [System of Environmental Economic Accounting](#) (UN et al., 2024)
- NCAVES and MAIA (2022). Monetary valuation of ecosystem services and ecosystem assets for ecosystem accounting: Interim Version 1st edition. United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Statistics Division, New York.
- Vermaat et al. (2016) Assessing the societal benefits of river restoration using the ecosystem services approach
- DEFRA (2020) [Enabling a Natural Capital Approach](#). Data sources, tools and studies for natural habitats and environmental impacts including economic valuation evidence for the UK, intended to facilitate natural capital assessment following the HM Treasury Green Book guidance.

5 Stated preference methods and value transfer to value ESs bundles

This section addresses stated preference and value transfer methods to estimate the value of a bundle of ESs provided by freshwater ecosystems restoration. In evaluating the societal benefits of freshwater ecosystem restoration, stated preference methods and value transfer approaches offer distinct advantages and limitations, especially when applied within spatially explicit cost-benefit analyses.

Stated preference methods, such as contingent valuation and choice experiments, are particularly valuable because they can capture both use and non-use values of ecosystem services—ranging from recreational benefits to cultural and existence values. These methods allow researchers to directly estimate people's willingness to pay (WTP) for specific restoration outcomes, which is essential for assessing the full societal value of non-market services. Examples of studies that integrate all ESs in one SP survey in the context of freshwater ecosystems can be found in Logar et al., (2019), De Blaeij et al., (2009), Kourtis & Tsihrintzis (2017) and Saarikoski et al., (2022). Moreover, when carefully designed, SP studies can be tailored to reflect stakeholder preferences and policy-relevant trade-offs. [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

However, stated preference studies are often resource-intensive and complex to implement. They typically require extensive survey design, piloting, and statistical analysis, which can be a barrier in large-scale or multi-site assessments. Another challenge lies in the interpretation of results: respondents often value bundles of ecosystem services rather than individual ones, making it difficult to isolate the value of specific services. Furthermore, these studies are rarely spatially explicit, which limits their usefulness in modelling geographically differentiated restoration scenarios. Unless the study is designed to link WTP to incremental biophysical changes, integrating results with ecological models can be problematic.

Value transfer, on the other hand, offers a more practical and cost-effective alternative, especially when primary data collection is not feasible. By using results from existing valuation studies, analysts can estimate benefits across multiple sites or scenarios with relatively low effort. This approach is particularly useful for initial screening-level CBAs or when broad coverage is needed. Recent advances in meta-analytic value transfer methods have improved the ability to adjust for contextual differences, making the approach more robust.

Several meta-analytic value transfer functions exist for ESs provided by floodplains (Perosa et al., 2021), wetlands (Brander et al., 2006; Ghermandi et al., 2010; Eric et al., 2022), lakes (Reynaud & Lanzanova, 2017) and rivers (Brouwer & Sheremet, 2017). However, to our knowledge, only one of these value transfer functions directly model the economic value of ecosystems restoration (Brouwer & Sheremet, 2017). Other functions model the ESs values provided by freshwater ecosystems. Nevertheless, these functions may be used to estimate restoration benefits in cases when they show a relationship between ESs values and site characteristics on which restoration has an impact, such as the extent of freshwater ecosystems (e.g. wetland area) and/or freshwater ecosystems condition (e.g. chemical and ecological status).

Yet, value transfer also comes with limitations. Transferred values may not accurately reflect local ecological, cultural, or economic conditions, especially in novel or highly site-specific restoration contexts. The lack of precision can be problematic when detailed, spatially explicit valuation is required. Moreover, without careful calibration, there is a risk of misrepresenting actual benefits, which can undermine the credibility of the analysis. For instance, when value transfer functions are developed from global meta-analysis, they may not provide accurate estimates at national or local scale (Natho & Hudson, 2024).

To address these challenges, it is increasingly recommended to integrate economic valuation approaches with biophysical models. Spatially explicit modelling enhances the robustness of ecological predictions, captures geographic and temporal variation in ecosystem service flows, and supports more nuanced scenario analysis. This integration is particularly important for freshwater restoration, where ecosystem service provision is closely tied to hydrological and land-use dynamics.

In summary, while stated preference methods offer depth and richness in capturing societal values, they require careful design and are less suited to spatially explicit modelling unless integrated with ecological data. Value transfer is more scalable and efficient but must be applied with caution to ensure contextual relevance. A hybrid approach—combining targeted primary valuation with broader value transfer—may offer the best balance between accuracy and practicality in freshwater restoration CBAs.

Further reading:

- Johnston et al. (2017) - Contemporary Guidance for Stated Preference Studies
- Johnston et al. (2021) – Guidance to enhance the validity and credibility of environmental benefit transfers.
- Johnston et al. (2015) – Benefit transfer of environmental and resource values: a guide for researchers and practitioners

6 Flood risk mitigation

6.1 ES logic chain

Ecosystems in freshwater catchments play a crucial role in reducing flood risks through their capacity to store and gradually release rainwater, reducing run-off and flattening peaks of high river flows. FWE restoration measures that increase the extent and/or capacity of ecosystems regulating water flows deliver flood risk mitigation benefits to property owners and residents living in flood prone areas of river catchments (Table 4).

Table 4 – Flood risk mitigation ES logic chain.

Ecosystem types	Factors determining supply		Factors determining use	Potential physical metric(s)	Benefits	Main users and beneficiaries
	Ecological	Societal				
Terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems (especially floodplains) within river catchments	Extent and condition of vegetation, ambient climate factors	Land use, ecosystem management	Existing flood protection infrastructures (e.g. dikes, levees)	Change in flood retention volume (m ³)/dike height (m) required for flood protection	Avoided flood protection costs	Property owners and residents – households, businesses, insurance sector, government
			Land use in flood-prone areas	Number/area of residential/business/farm properties at flood risk in case of a 100-year flood event	Avoided damages of flood events	

Flood risk mitigation benefits can be monetised through two valuation approaches:

- Replacement costs: the costs that would have been spent on flood protection infrastructure to reach the same level of flood mitigation had the restoration not taken place, or
- Avoided damage costs: or prevented (expected) damage costs caused by floods that would have occurred had the restoration not taken place.

Whether to use a replacement cost or an avoided damage costs approach depends on the biophysical and socio-economic context of the valuation. For instance, in the Dutch Rhine River basin (MERLIN CS 04), water flows are highly regulated, and flood barriers are regularly upgraded to prevent river flooding damages, at a safety standard (e.g. 1:10.000 year) set in law. Therefore, benefits of FWE restoration will materialise as a reduction of infrastructure works required to maintain flood protection standards: in this case, the replacement cost approach should be used to monetise benefits.

In the case of many large rivers with an (originally) flood-prone (e.g. low-lying and flat) hinterland, such protection infrastructure is present. Conversely, many small river catchments do not have an extensive flood protection system and are subject to regular flood events. In these catchments, the avoided damage cost approach is best suited to monetise benefits.

The rest of this section discusses possible quantification and valuation methods, with existing models and datasets, for the avoided damage costs approach (Section 6.2) and the replacement costs approach (Section 6.3), embedding lessons learnt from MERLIN CS CBAs, and end with recommendations.

6.2 Avoided damage costs approach

Estimating flood damage costs implies to quantify (1) flood hazard, i.e. the probability of flood occurrence, (2) flood exposure, i.e. the assets value exposed to flood hazard and (3) flood vulnerability, i.e. the proportion of assets value at loss in case of flooding.

Flood hazard

Flood hazard can be quantified with return period-based flood extent and depth maps (probability). For instance, a map with a return period of 1:100-year event shows the extent and depth of floods that occur every 100 years, corresponding to a probability of occurrence of 1%. A range of return periods are covered to quantify the effects of flood events with different magnitudes and frequencies. For instance, in Poland, the State Water Management Company published flood extent and depth maps with return periods of 10, 100 and 500 years.

Two types of models are required to produce flood extent and depth maps: 1) A hydrological model simulates hydrological processes in the catchment to predict river stream flow, which is used as input for 2) a hydraulic model to predict flood extent and depth. A coupled Hydrological – hydraulic model specific to the water catchment of interest is the preferred option, as these are generally developed and calibrated to fit the specific hydrological characteristics of the catchment. Include refs to catchment specific models.

Flood exposure and vulnerability

Flood exposure is the value of assets exposed to a flood hazard, which is the value of land and buildings located in an area exposed to floods. Flood exposure can be quantified by overlaying flood extent and depth maps with maps of land properties and infrastructures and their monetary values. Flood vulnerability refers to the susceptibility of these exposed assets to damage, often based on flood depth. Vulnerability is assessed using the method of depth-damage functions/curves, which relate flood depth (obtained from flood extent and depth maps) to damage intensity across asset types.

National datasets on assets and flood depth-damage functions exist in several countries. For instance, in Germany, the Basic European Asset Map (BEAM) provides asset types and values in €/m². These values can be combined with vulnerability curves that estimate damage percentages per asset class of the BEAM dataset per 5 cm flood depth increment (based on standard values for different measure types in Germany; [LAWA, 2023](#)).

There may be additional, more detailed studies for specific assets, and/ or separating direct and indirect damages (Martínez-Gomariz et al., 2020; van Ginkel et al., 2021). There is also a body of literature with addresses embedding distributional / equity considerations in flood risk assessment (Kind et al., 2020).

When no national depth-damage relations are available, the global database in Huizinga et al. (2017) can be used as default option. It provides Europe-specific flood depth – damage functions (damage % as a function of flood depth) for 6 land use classes (residential, commercial, industry, transport, infrastructure, agriculture). Moreover, this dataset provides country-specific maximum damage values for those 6 land use classes. Economic damages of floods as a function of flood depth can be calculated by multiplying the damage percentage and the maximum land use value.

Annualisation of flood damage costs

The above steps allow to estimate flood damage costs corresponding to a few, usually 3 to 5, return periods for which flood extent and depth maps have been generated. Those flood damage costs estimates are then used to approximate annualised flood damage costs (see Equation 1 in Annex 1).

MERLIN QGIS plugin

Catchment-specific hydrological – hydraulic models may not always be available or require too much expertise and resources. Likewise, national data on assets and flood depth – damage functions may not be available. Therefore, modelling of avoided flood damage costs is often not feasible, especially for an initial screening CBA. To address this issue, MERLIN developed a simplified method, available as an open-source QGIS plugin, that can be used as a default option in any EU country. The MERLIN method is still based on a hydrological model, SWAT+, but circumvents the need for hydraulic modelling. The hydrological model SWAT+ is used to simulate the benefits of FWE restoration measures on the return period of peak stream flows corresponding to flood events (see [D3.3](#)). Changes in flood return periods are then combined with existing EU data on flood extent and depth, land use and flood depth-damage relationships. A detailed methodological description is included in Annex 1 and Box 6.1 presents an application in a MERLIN CS.

6.3 Replacement costs approach

The replacement cost method estimates the monetary value and benefits of flood mitigation provided by ecosystem restoration by calculating the cost of achieving equivalent or similar flood mitigation using alternative, usually engineered infrastructure solutions (e.g. dikes, levees, flood polders, managed retention basins).

Box 6.1: Valuation of flood risk benefits with the MERLIN QGIS plugin in the MERLIN CS 05 Kampinos wetlands

Simulation of FWE restoration effects on peak stream flow return periods with SWAT+

Figure 5 shows the effects of Kampinos wetlands restoration on peak stream flows probabilities (averaged over all return periods), assessed with SWAT+: Channels with a green colour have a reduced peak flow probability thanks to restoration (while red colour channels have an increased peak flow probability). Blue areas show flooded areas. With the MERLIN tool, decrease in peak stream flow probabilities in “green” channels is translated into reduced flood probabilities in the nearby flooded areas (see Annex 2 for a detailed description). Then these reduced flood probabilities have to be combined with flood damage costs data.

Figure 5 – Effects of FWE on the probability peak stream flows and associated flood events

Estimation of flood damage costs

We compared results obtained with three different data sources: (1) using directly flood damage costs maps published by the Polish State Water Management Company, (2) using only the flood extent and depth maps published by Polish State Water Management Company, combined with other EU-wide data, (3) using only EU-wide data.

(1) using directly flood damage costs maps published by the Polish State Water Management Company

These maps provide the value of flood damages, for 3 return periods: every 10, 100 and 500 years (Figure 6). They span a range of frequent floods with low damages to rare events with high damages.

Figure 6 – Flood damage (in euros/m²) maps corresponding to flood events with return periods of 1/500 years (left), 1/100 years (centre) and 1/10 years (right)

(2) using only the flood extent and depth maps published by Polish State Water Management Company, combined with other EU-wide data

In some EU countries, flood damage costs maps may not be available. In those cases, flood damage costs need to be estimated based on flood extent and depth maps, land use data and flood damage depth functions. This was also done in the Kampinos wetlands case study, using flood extent and depth maps published by Polish State Water Management Company, with return periods every 10, 100 and 500 years, combined with EU-wide data.

Box 6.1: Valuation of flood risk benefits with the MERLIN QGIS plugin in the MERLIN CS 05 Kampinos wetlands

Information on land use was obtained from the Corine Land Cover dataset. Flood depth – damage functions and the economic value for each land use class were derived from the global database in Huizinga et al. (2017). Flood depth – damage functions relate a flood depth value (in m) to a flood damage fraction (0-1). By combining the flood extent and depth maps, land use map and land use specific damage fractions, we derived one flood damage costs map for each return period.

(3) using only EU-wide data

The methodology is the same than in (2) but instead of national flood extent and depth maps, EU-wide flood extent and depth maps are used ([River flood hazard maps for Europe and the Mediterranean Basin region](#)).

Table 5 shows differences in output between the three data sources. Damage values are much higher with the EU data than with the two other data inputs. This is due to an overestimation of the extent and depth of flooding in the EU-wide flood hazard maps (Figure 7). The total expected annual damage is 50% higher with the national + EU data than with national data only. Damage values mostly differ for the return period 1/10 year and are similar for the return period 1/500 year. Therefore, it is likely that the damage value at small flood depth (corresponding to frequent events) is overestimated in the EU data.

Table 5 : Damage costs of floods (in million 2024 Euros) based on national vs EU-wide data sources

	National flood damage maps	National flood maps + EU-wide data	EU-wide data
Total damage - return period 1/500yrs	368 M€	359 M€	1,203 M€
Total damage - return period 1/100yrs	152 M€	216 M€	1,000 M€
Total damage - return period 1/10 yrs	28 M€	69 M€	638 M€
Total Expected Annual Damage (in 2024 Euros)	10 M€	15 M€	77 M€

Figure 7 – Flood extent and depth (in meters) maps, return period 1/500 yrs. Left: national map. Right: EU map.

Calculation of the flood risk mitigation value of FWE restoration

In the MERLIN approach, flood damage costs are kept fixed between the baseline and restoration scenarios. FWE restoration influences the return periods, i.e. probabilities, of the flood damage costs occurrence. Changes in flood events probabilities are then converted in annual flood risk mitigation benefits (see Annex 1 for detailed calculation). In the Kampinos wetlands, the flood risk mitigation benefits were estimated at 23 K€ euros/year using the national flood damage maps. That corresponds to a reduction of about 0.23% of the total flood risks thanks to restoration.

To estimate the impact of an intervention on the ES flood mitigation, such as the lowering of the water table under a certain river discharge or reducing the probability of a specific high discharge hydraulic/ hydrologic models can be used (see also 6.2). To estimate the costs, a cost function is needed for the infrastructure design – in particular a detailed relationship of how a change in flood mitigation translates into the design and consequent implementation costs of the engineered alternative. Ideally, this is based on national (or even local) cost estimates for engineered solutions.

To illustrate, in the Netherlands, flood mitigation benefits of measures which lower the water table under high (design) river discharge along the large rivers are calculated via prevented reinforcement costs of dikes along the large rivers. The protection level for which the dikes are designed, was already set to an economically optimal level using the avoided damage cost approach (Kind, 2014). The replacement cost are calculated using the tool OKADER (de Grave, 2021). Input to this tool is the expected water table lowering per river section (km) compared to a baseline, under a specific (high) discharge at the upstream boundary, which is generally derived from hydraulic modelling using tool such as WAQUA, SOBEK or DELFT3D (Deltares, 2022, 2020). Underlying data in this tool includes for each dike section knowledge on prevailing failure mechanisms – including piping, macro stability and height (van der Meij et al., 2016).

Lessons learned & recommendations

- The avoided damage cost approach is preferable in areas with no or limited existing flood protection infrastructure and frequent flooding.
- The replacement cost approach is preferable in highly regulated systems with legally defined flood protection standards where restoration affects flood protection infrastructure lifecycle costs
- The MERLIN QGIS plugin offers a practical tool for estimating avoided damage costs in initial screening CBAs, especially where data or modelling capacity is limited. Annex 1 provides links to default EU-wide datasets (flood hazard maps, land cover maps, global depth-damage functions) that can be used in absence of national data. However, using high-resolution, local data is preferable for greater accuracy of results (see Box6.1).

Further reading:

- Vigerstol, K. L., & Aukema, J. E. (2011). [A comparison of tools for modeling freshwater ecosystem services. Journal of Environmental Management, 92\(10\), 2403–2409.](#)
- Maranzoni, A., D’Oria, M., & Rizzo, C. (2023). [Quantitative flood hazard assessment methods: A review. Journal of Flood Risk Management, 16\(1\), e12855.](#)
- Crossman N.D., Nedkov S., Brander L. (2019). [Discussion paper 7: Water flow regulation for mitigating river and coastal flooding. Paper submitted to the Expert Meeting on Advancing the Measurement of Ecosystem Services for Ecosystem Accounting, New York, 22-24 January 2019 and subsequently revised. Version of 1 April 2019.](#)

7 Climate change mitigation

7.1 ES logic chain

Freshwater ecosystems play an important role in climate change mitigation, acting as important carbon sinks: carbon is dissolved or buried in lakes and reservoirs (via phytoplankton and zooplankton), whereas vegetation in wetlands (e.g. floodplains) can capture carbon in below and above-ground biomass. Especially peatlands have a high carbon sequestration potential, by the accumulation of organic matter in soils. For both floodplains and peatlands, there are conditions (such as draining of peatlands) under which both ecosystems can become net sources of carbon (through CO₂ emissions). Restoring FWE generally increases their carbon sequestration potential.

The ecosystem benefits of restoration can be quantified via estimating the carbon capture potential of the baseline and restoration scenarios (e.g. in C per ha) and converting them to CO₂ equivalent. They can be monetised in price per (tonnes) CO₂. Here, there are various monetarisation options: 1) Emission trading prices, 2) the social cost (or ‘shadow price’) of carbon or 3) efficient CO₂ prices. Which option is used depends on the purpose of the valuation and potential country specific guidelines.

Table 6 – Climate change mitigation logic chain.

Ecosystem types	Factors determining supply		Factors determining use	Potential physical metric(s)	Benefits	Main users and beneficiaries
	Ecological	Societal				
Terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems within water catchments	Extent and condition of freshwater ecosystem (e.g. drained or undrained, vegetation type), soil type, sedimentation (in lake/banks), water table depth (in peatlands)	Land use, ecosystem management	Vulnerability to climate change (exposure, sensitivity and adaptive capacity)	Tons of CO ₂ eq emitted or sequestered	Reduced GHG concentration leading to avoided climate change-related damages.	Governments committed to meeting climate goals; those benefiting from selling carbon credits

The rest of this section discusses approaches for quantification (6.2), monetisation (6.3), and lessons learned, and recommendations from MERLIN cases.

7.2 Ecosystem service quantification

The amount of carbon sequestered or emitted in a specific location can be estimated based on the relations between land cover and carbon sequestered/emitted in terrestrial and marine ecosystems (in mg C/ha/year). The IPCC hosts a global database of Emission Factors (IPCC, 2022) tons of carbon sequestered/emitted per hectare for different ecosystems/land cover land use. The EEA (2022) provides a dataset with rates of carbon sequestration/emission in EU terrestrial and marine ecosystems. At the national level, more detailed emission factors (EF) for local (sub)ecosystems may be available (e.g. (Evans et al., 2017) [with EFs for the UK](#)).

In peatlands, the water table depth is the main driver of GHG emissions (Evans et al., 2021). Natural peatlands with a highwater table sequester CO₂, emit CH₄ due to anaerobic conditions, but are net GHG sinks. Drained peatlands are turned into net GHG sources, as low water tables increase CO₂ and N₂O emissions (though CH₄ emissions decrease). Apart from the water table depth, climate, elevation and the site vegetation are also driving GHG emissions. Though rewetting peatlands initially increase CH₄ emissions, it is expected to provide a long-term benefit for climate change, as CO₂ emissions drop and ultimately turn into CO₂ sequestration. When available, national EF database, providing EF specific to peatland condition, land use and vegetation should be used.

Box 7.1 and box 7.2 present examples of climate change mitigation benefits quantification in two MERLIN case studies.

Box 7.1: Quantification of climate change mitigation benefits from peatland restoration in the MERLIN CS 14 Komppasuo peat extraction area

The climate benefits of a complete restoration of 3500 ha of peat extraction sites by 2030 were estimated. To estimate GHG benefits, GHG emissions pre and post-restoration were calculated by multiplying the restored area with GHG emission factors. EFs were obtained from the scientific literature (Juutinen et al., 2019).

Table 7 -. GHG emission factors of peatlands with difference management and condition

Land use	CO ₂ emissions (g/m ² /year)	CH ₄ emissions	N ₂ O emissions (g/m ² /year)	Total CO ₂ e emissions (g/m ² /year)
Peat extraction areas (pre-restoration)	1,322	2.7	0.1	1,443.6
Open sedge peatlands (post-restoration)	-147	24	0	669

Peatlands rewetting has contrasting effects on emissions of different GHG: CO₂ and N₂O emissions are reduced but CH₄ emissions are increased. To take this into account, N₂O and CH₄ emissions are converted into CO₂ equivalent emissions based on their global warming potential¹ for 100 years (GWP100, 34 for CH₄ and 298 for N₂O, as Juutinen et al., (2019)), and all GHG emissions are summed in total CO₂e emissions for estimating climate mitigation benefits.

¹ The Global warming potential (GWP) is a measure of how much heat a GHG traps in the atmosphere over a specific time period, relative to CO₂.

Box 7.2: Carbon sequestration in restored floodplains in the MERLIN CS 04 – Room for the Rhine branches

Kok et al. (2025) assess the carbon sequestration potential of large-scale floodplain restoration in the Dutch Rhine, including floodplain reconnection and land use conversion from agriculture to wetlands. Initially, annual biomass growth is estimated by multiplying surface area per land cover type with annual growth rates (in m³/ha/year) for typical Dutch floodplain ecotopes (Koopman et al., 2018). Then, the amount of biomass retained in the system after harvesting is estimated (harvest fractions:100% for grassland, 70% for herbaceous vegetation and 10% for forested and swamp areas). The biomass remaining in the system was then converted to carbon using a conversion factor of 0.5 (Hendriks et al., 2020). In the baseline scenario, approximately 37,000 ha of floodplains sequester 11,800 tonnes of carbon annually. Increasing vegetation—particularly forested areas—boosts this potential by 49%. Ideally, carbon accounting should also include harvested biomass, which can act as either a carbon source or sink depending on its end use (Koopman et al., 2018; Pfau et al., 2019).

7.3 Ecosystem service valuation

7.3.1 Social cost of carbon

The social cost of carbon represents the economic damage to society associated with emitting one additional tonne of carbon dioxide (CO₂) into the atmosphere. These damages include, for example reduced agricultural productivity and damage to infrastructure and buildings due to climate change (e.g. associated to extreme events), health problems due to heatwaves, and ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss. Generally, the social cost of carbon is determined based on 1) analysis using climate model to determine how an additional tonne of CO₂ in the atmosphere affects global temperatures, sea level rise, and extreme weather patterns, which are then 2) translated into physical impacts and economic costs. A discount rate is then used to convert future damages to present-day values. Social discount rates can be calculated for different regions, across various climate and economic scenarios, and discount rates (see Box 7.3). To reflect the uncertainties in this process, the final cost of carbon is usually given as an average value, with a range.

Box 7.3: Use of Social cost of Carbon in German policy evaluation

The German Federal Environment Agency (UBA) applies the social cost of carbon (SCC) as a central metric in environmental policy evaluation (Matthey et al., 2024). For the reference year 2021, the UBA set the SCC at €282.50 per tonne of CO₂, based on a 1% pure time preference rate. This value was derived from interpolated data between 2020 and 2023 (Matthey et al., 2024). The UBA also applies equity weights, to account for global income disparities and intergenerational equity. Thus, when a 0%-time preference rate is applied, treating future generations equally, the SCC rises significantly to €880 per tonne of CO₂.

Table 8 Social cost of carbon. From Gesellschaftliche Kosten von Umweltbelastungen (Matthey et al., 2024)

Costs in Euro (2024) per ton CO ₂	2024	2030	2050
1% time preference rate	300	335	435
0% time preference rate	880	940	1080

7.3.2 Efficient CO₂ prices

Efficient prices reflect the costs needed to achieve emission reductions at the lowest possible expense. As the deadline of emission reduction targets approaches, marginal costs increase due to the exhaustion of low-cost options. Since the European Emission Trading System (ETS) does not cover all economic actors (yet) or the full volume of GHG emissions, additional policy measures are implemented outside the ETS in order to reach reduction targets. Efficient price paths embed both the ETS and additional policies. Usually, prices are calculated for various scenarios, including e.g. economic scenarios and scenarios for the ambition level of emission reduction targets (see Box 7.4).

Box 7.4: Carbon policy evaluation in the Netherlands: efficient CO₂ price paths

In the Netherlands, efficient prices are the official approach to price CO₂ in economic policy appraisals. These efficient prices are derived by Aalbers et al., (2017), using a discount rate of 3.5% (Table 9). In the 'high scenario', there is both high economic growth and a high emission reduction target. In the 'low' scenario there is low economic growth, and a low emission reduction target. The large bandwidths for the reported prices under the 2°C target stem from 1) the definition of the 2-degree goal, i.e. is temporary overshooting of the reduction target allowed or not, and 2) assumptions regarding large-scale applicability, capacity and costs of technologies such as carbon capture and storage and biogas production.

Table 9 Efficient prices and ETS prices of 1 ton CO₂ (in euros) used in the High and Low scenarios and in in the two degree scenario.

Scenario	Price type	2015	2030	2050
High	Efficient price	48	80	160
	ETS price	5	40	160
Low	Efficient price	12	20	40
	ETS price	5	15	40
2 degree	Efficient price	60-300	100-500	200-1000
	ETS price	5	100-500	200-1000

7.3.3 Compliance and voluntary market prices

Driven by targets set on emissions of greenhouse gases, the EU set up a cap-and-trade system, the Emissions Trading System (EU ETS). The ETS covers emissions from energy-intensive industries, power and heat generation, commercial aviation, and maritime transport. Starting in 2027, it will expand to include smaller industrial sectors, buildings, and road transportation. Carbon pricing is not unique to the EU: similar systems exist globally. Within the EU, prices are projected to rise from €80 per ton/CO₂ equivalent today to € 145 by 2030 and €177 by 2035 (Tiseo, 2025).

In parallel to compliance markets, voluntary carbon markets (VCM) have emerged. These markets allow individuals, companies and organisations to buy carbon credits to offset their emissions, often motivated by corporate sustainability goals or to compensate for specific activities such as air travel. Unlike the compliance markets, VCMs are not governed by legally binding emissions caps. In the voluntary markets, projects which capture and/ or sequester CO₂ - such as reforestation, renewable energy - can obtain credits verified by independent third parties, which can then be sold to buyers.

Despite rapid growth of the market in the past decade (e.g. supported by the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Regulation, EU 2024), prices in the voluntary carbon market are quite volatile. Between 2017 and 2021, prices ranged from (dollar) 2 to (dollar) 4 per ton CO₂. Key factors in this price are the type of carbon mitigation projects (forestry and land use have higher prices due to perceived high quality resulting in a non-homogenous market), the age of the credits (newer credits higher values), investor demand and geopolitical tensions (Liu, 2024).

Lessons learned & recommendations

- For rapid cost-benefit analyses (CBAs), lookup tables can be used to estimate carbon sequestration potential. However, for more accurate assessments — especially at the local scale — it is preferable to use national or regional data on greenhouse gas emissions by ecosystem type.
- For extended CBA, more detailed modelling of dynamic carbon cycling processes is recommended. Recent literature highlights that river-floodplain systems can act either as carbon sources or sinks, depending on the balance of various carbon cycling processes (Petch et al., 2023). The effects of restoration interventions on greenhouse gas emissions—particularly methane—remain uncertain. For instance, rewetting previously drained agricultural land may lead to a temporary increase in emissions.

- When evaluating the carbon sequestration potential of restoration efforts, vegetation management should be taken into consideration. If biomass is removed from the restored area, the assessment should account for whether the carbon is likely to be emitted or sequestered, depending on its end use (see Box 7.2; Pfau et al. 2019).
- When monetizing the impacts of carbon sequestration, market prices should be avoided as they do not reflect the full economic cost of emissions. Instead, the social cost of carbon or efficient pricing mechanisms should be used. Many EU countries have established official guidelines for carbon pricing in CBAs (see Box 7.3 & 7.4).
- An additional assessment using prices from the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) or voluntary carbon markets can offer valuable insights into the potential revenue streams of a project, particularly if it becomes eligible for carbon credits.

Further reading:

- Penman, J., Gytarski, M., Hiraishi, T., Krug, T., Kruger, D., Pipatti, R., Buendia, L., Miwa, K., et al. (2003). Good Practice Guidance for Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, National Greenhouse Gas Inventories Programme (IPCC-NGGIP)
- IPCC Task Force on National Greenhouse Gas Inventories. 2013 Supplement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories: Wetlands. (IPCC, 2014).
- Nordhaus, W.D. (2017). Revising the social cost of carbon. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 114(7), 1518-1523. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1609244114.
- World Bank (2025). State and Trends of Carbon Pricing 2025.
<https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/state-and-trends-of-carbon-pricing>

8 Nutrient retention

8.1 ES logic chain

Water purification services are the ecosystem contributions to the restoration and maintenance of the chemical condition of surface water and groundwater bodies through the breakdown or removal of nutrients and other pollutants (United Nations, 2024). This guidance is focused on nutrient retention. This choice was driven by the importance of nutrient pollution for humans and ecosystems, as well as the large body of existing works on nutrient retention modelling and monetary valuation, upon which this guideline could build, while recognising that other pollutants, for instance pesticides, also have large effects on humans and ecosystems.

Pollution by nutrients has harmful effects on human use of water, for instance by restricting access to water for recreation activities (Pretty et al., 2003) and human health, for instance in case of nitrates excess in drinking water (Van Grinsven et al., 2010). High concentrations of nutrients in water bodies also lead to eutrophication, with negative consequences on ecosystem health and biodiversity (Grizzetti et al., 2011). By retaining nutrients, ecosystems mitigate the harmful effects of nutrients on humans and ecosystems, thereby providing a broad range of benefits, such as reduced water treatment costs, improved health and reduced eutrophication. Potential beneficiaries of this ES are water supply companies, water-based recreation businesses, water-front property owners and households. Freshwater ecosystems have a high capacity to supply nutrient retention ES. N and P concentration can be reduced by algae and plant uptake, as well as storage in sediments and soils in water bodies and wetlands (Reddy et al., 1999). Moreover, anoxic conditions in wetlands, riparian areas and water bodies stimulate the release of N to the atmosphere through denitrification by bacteria (Seitzinger et al., 2006).

Table 10 - Nutrient retention logic chain.

Ecosystem types	Factors determining supply		Factors determining use	Potential physical metric(s)	Benefits	Main users and beneficiaries
	Ecological	Societal				
Peatlands, wetlands, rivers and lakes	Ecosystem condition: chemical state, biological composition	Location, type and volume of released water pollutants	Demand for clean water for human consumption, water-based recreation, or other uses	Tons of pollutants removed by type of pollutant	Reduced water treatment costs, improved health outcomes, reduced eutrophication	Water supply companies, water-based recreation businesses, water-front property owners, households

8.2 ES quantification

Nutrient retention depends on complex climatic, physical, chemical and biological processes which take place in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Different modelling tools with various levels of complexity exist. InVEST and ESTIMAP, two multi-ES modelling platforms, are relatively easy to use but have important limitations with regards to modelling the effects of FWE restoration. For instance, InVEST does not capture in-stream retention processes, while ESTIMAP runs at rough scales, providing yearly averages of, on average, 180 km² sub-basins. The SWAT+ model captures both land and in-stream retention and has been widely used to model N retention. It is however requiring specific expertise and is data intensive. To facilitate the use of SWAT+ to model the effects of FWE on N retention, the MERLIN project has developed a user-friendly modelling workflow based on EU-wide publicly available datasets (Garcia et al., 2025). The MERLIN workflow can be used to model the effects on N retention of 5 different restoration measures (peatland rewetting, wetland rewetting, riparian buffers, channel restoration and floodplain reconnection).

8.3 ES valuation

8.3.1 MERLIN workflow valuation method

In the modelling workflow developed by MERLIN (see Deliverable report [D3.3](#) and annex 2), a replacement cost approach has been implemented to allocate a monetary value to nutrient retention benefits of ecosystem restoration. This approach values the nutrient retention service provided by the restoration of ecosystems in a water catchment on the assumption that the service would be replaced by constructed wetlands if it did not exist. This approach was adapted from La Notte et al. 2017. Replacement constructed wetlands are

dimensioned to provide a nutrient retention service equivalent to the service provided by the restoration of ecosystems.

Depending on the context, i.e. the relative importance of N and P retention for enhancing water quality, users may decide to dimension the constructed wetlands based on the N, P or both N and P retention service.

The monetary value of the nutrient retention service equals the sum of annualised net present value of the capital investment costs and yearly operational costs of the constructed wetlands. Annex 2 provides a detailed methodological description of the valuation method implemented in the MERLIN tool.

The validity of this replacement cost approach hinges on three core assumptions.

First, it is assumed that the constructed wetland can provide exactly the same ES as the ecosystems. Constructed wetlands have similar functions than freshwater ecosystems and were dimensioned to provide the same level of nutrient retention.

Second, it is assumed that there is an actual societal demand for the building of constructed wetlands as an alternative to the nutrient retention service. This can be checked using the water bodies quality status of the Water Framework Directive. If the WFD water quality targets reflect the societal demand for water quality, we can hypothesise that society would be willing to pay for constructed wetlands only where WFD targets are not met in the water basin of interest (see Box 8.1).

Third, it is assumed that constructed wetlands are the least-cost alternative to the nutrient retention service. La Notte et al. (2017) state that constructed wetlands are much less expensive than wastewater treatment plants and that the chosen constructed wetland type, i.e. free water surface constructed wetlands, is the less expensive one. However, other (possibly less costly) alternatives to constructed wetlands could be considered, for instance the reduction of nutrients losses from agricultural land management. Ideally, a replacement cost approach should consider all possible alternatives to the ES and be based on the combination of alternatives that minimise replacement costs. Grossman et al. (2012) provide an example of such a cost-minimisation approach. This kind of approach requires context specific data and models, thus was not feasible to implement in the MERLIN modelling workflow.

8.3.2 Other valuation methods

Nutrient retention may also be valued through the environmental damage costs caused by excess of nutrients in water bodies. Nutrients and eutrophication damage costs include drinking water treatment costs to remove nutrients, health costs due to the presence of nitrates in drinking water, reduced value of waterside properties, reduced recreational and amenity value, and loss of biodiversity.

Price & Heberling (2018) reviewed empirical literature on the effects of source water quality on drinking water treatment costs. They found that nutrient loads in source water had significant but moderate effects on treatment costs: a 1% increase in nutrient concentration led to 0.06% and 0.02% increase of treatment costs for N and P respectively. The effect of sediment load was higher (0.23%). Note however that those results were based on a handful of studies, mainly from the US.

Van Grinsven et al. (2010) estimated that the incidence of colon cancer increased by 3% due to nitrate contamination of groundwater in the EU, corresponding to a cost of 0.7 euro per kg of nitrate N leaching, but their estimate was inferred from one epidemiological study in the US.

Social costs of Nitrogen have been estimated in Europe (Brink et al., 2011; Van Grinsven et al., 2013), but these estimates are based on a few studies and have a large uncertainty. In some European countries, national estimates may be available. For example, the German Federal Environment Agency (Matthey et al., 2024) determined the social costs of Nitrogen at €21.44/kg N and €158.22/kg P (price level 2021, per year).

Box 8.1: Nutrient retention benefits estimation with the MERLIN workflow – MERLIN CS17 Forth Catchment

In the Forth Catchment, the SWAT+ model estimates that peatland rewetting enhances nutrients retention and therefore decreases quantities of nutrients reaching lakes and rivers. The effects were quantified as 88 tons of Nitrogen and 11 tons of Phosphorus removed per year. Applying the MERLIN plugin replacement cost approach the value of the nutrients retention benefit was estimated at 640 K€/year for N retention and 595 K€/year for P retention, i.e. 7.4 €/kg Nitrogen and 55.7 €/kg Phosphorus (2024 prices).

Defra's Enabling a Natural Capital Approach (ENCA) provide other options to value water quality improvement benefits (DEFRA, 2025). Based on the Farmscoper tool, the annual value of reducing a kg of nitrate/phosphorus in water is estimated at about 1.17 and 39.76 £ (2021 prices). These values are based on estimation of economic damages of nitrate and phosphorus on a range of ecosystem services, including drinking water quality, fishing, bathing water quality and eutrophication.

Therefore, in the case of the Forth catchment, the replacement cost approach seems to overestimates the societal benefits of nitrogen removal but generates estimates in line with the Farmscoper tool for phosphorus retention.

Note that both the replacement costs based and damage costs based values assume that all units of N retention provide the same benefit, i.e. each kg of N reduction has the same value. In reality, N emission reductions in sub-catchments where water quality is high have a lower value than N emission reductions in sub-catchments where water quality is poor. For instance, in the Forth Catchment restoration scenario, the nutrients retention benefit provided by peat restoration areas located in the Eastern part of the catchment, where water quality is mostly “moderate” to “good”, is likely higher than the benefit provided by peat restoration areas located in the North-Eastern part of the catchment, where water quality already reaches a “good” to “high” status.

Figure 8 – Nutrients retention benefit in the Forth Catchment.

Finally, both replacement costs based and damage costs based values integrate the value of multiple ESs related to nutrients content in surface water. Therefore, there is a risk of double-counting benefits if water-related ES benefits are also taken into account when valuing nature recreation (Section 10) or habitat provision benefits (Section 11).

Lessons learned & recommendations

- Use robust models like SWAT+ for accurate nutrient retention modelling, especially when restoration impacts are complex; simpler tools (e.g. InVEST, ESTIMAP) lack details on key processes. The MERLIN workflow provides a good starting point.
- Use national data for damage costs when available (e.g. UK, NL, Germany) for more context-specific and robust valuation in CBA.
- Avoid double counting, especially when other methods are included in the cost-benefit analysis (SP; WTP).
- When using a replacement cost method, ensure there is societal demand for the replacement and that replacement is the least-cost alternative.

Further reading:

- Seitzinger, S., Harrison, J. A., Böhlke, J. K., Bouwman, A. F., Lowrance, R., Peterson, B., Tobias, C., & Drecht, G. V. (2006). Denitrification Across Landscapes and Waterscapes: A Synthesis. *Ecological Applications*, 16(6), 2064–2090. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761\(2006\)016\[2064:DALAWA\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761(2006)016[2064:DALAWA]2.0.CO;2)
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9 Drought mitigation

9.1 ES logic chain

Peatland and wetland restoration increases the sponge function of a landscape: the soil moisture content (and water available to plants) is higher, and excess water is absorbed during floods and slowly released to ground – and surface water during dry periods. This process supports higher baseflows in rivers and improves the recharge rates of both natural and artificial reservoirs, including aquifers. As a result, water availability during drought conditions is improved. This benefits 1) Hydropower generation and 2) Irrigated agriculture, cooling (e.g. byers et al) and drinking water supply, which depend on stable water availability and increased base flows.

In large rivers and smaller streams, interventions such as re-meandering and other measures which reduce flow velocity help reduce riverbed incision. Riverbed incision exacerbates the disconnection of rivers from their floodplains and lowers groundwater tables in the vicinity of the river under low flow conditions. By maintaining higher water tables during dry periods (alongside higher baseflow), these measures contribute to 3) Inland shipping, by preserving navigable water levels; and 4) Water-based recreation, by sustaining water quality and water levels.

Table 11 – Drought mitigation logic chain.

Ecosystem types	Factors determining supply		Factors determining use	Potential physical metric(s)	Benefits	Main users and beneficiaries
	Ecological	Societal				
Peatlands, wetlands, rivers and lakes	Groundwater recharge (infiltration) and water storage in landscape	Water infrastructure – built to drain or to retain	Demand & infrastructure for irrigation water,	Average water yield in dry months	Increased agricultural yield	Farmers
Peatlands, wetlands, rivers and lakes	Groundwater recharge (infiltration) and water storage in landscape	Water infrastructure – built to drain or to retain	Presence of infrastructure to retain & release water	Outflow of reservoirs and lakes	Energy production	Energy companies
Large rivers	Riverbed elevation/ water depth in dry season; bed sedimentation /erosion	Water level regulation infrastructure (weirs, locks, groynes)	Depth of ships, load capacity	Water depth during low-flow	Navigation cost (function of load capacity)	Navigation/ transport sector
Large rivers & streams	Riverbed elevation/ water depth, water quality, upstream landscape retention capacity	Water level regulation infrastructure (weirs, locks, groynes)	Infrastructure for water-based recreation (marina's, rental companies, beach)	Changes in water level	Water-based recreation	water-based recreation businesses

9.2 ES quantification

Drought mitigation refers to the capacity of freshwater ecosystems—such as wetlands, floodplains, and riparian zones—to store, retain, and slowly release water. Hydrological models can estimate how much water is stored in floodplains or wetlands and how this affects downstream availability during droughts and erosion/sedimentation processes. Exactly what is to be modelled depends on the goal, but could include modelling of water retention and release at the basin scale to estimate probability of flow rates (e.g. with SWAT+, Garcia et al. (2025), water levels under low discharge at the river stretch level, implications for the fill level of natural or man-made reservoirs (under conditions of reservoir operation) and/ or groundwater modelling.

9.3 ES valuation: Water availability for crop production

After modelling expected impacts of interventions on baseflow and/ or natural/artificial reservoirs, the implications of changes in water availability on crop production can be monetised. There are various approaches to calculate the economic value of irrigation water:

- Using a production function to either estimate the additional yield generated by an additional unit of water (marginal value product) or the residual value of water after accounting for other inputs (residual value) (Steduto et al., 2012; Hack-ten Broeke et al., 2019; Bashe et al., 2022).
- Market price: actual price of irrigation water (m³) in places where such a market exists, e.g. through an irrigation scheme, (Karabulut et al., 2016).
- Revealed/ stated preference: the value of irrigation water can be embedded in land rental prices, which can be derived via hedonic pricing (Bashe et al., 2022): The price of agricultural land is determined by predicted profitability. Availability (and reliability) of irrigation water is one of many factors that influence the rent price. Another approach is to derive the willingness to pay via contingent valuation (large surveys asking farmers how much they are willing to pay for irrigation water).
- Replacement costs: by calculating the alternative price for (constructed) water storage infrastructure (Esen et al., 2023)-.

Box 9.1: Impact of Groundwater Changes on Agricultural Revenue near the Rhine Branches

The river Rhine in the Netherlands faces a disrupted sediment balance, which in turn causes riverbed incision and reduced lateral connectivity. This affects groundwater levels within and beyond the floodplains, which increases drought damage to (non-irrigated) crops.

Kok et al. (2025) estimated impacts of floodplain reconnection and riverbed sediment dynamics on mean low groundwater tables (MLGT)—influenced by river stage–discharge relations, using the Dutch WaterWijzerLandbouw model (Hack-ten Broeke et al., 2019). This model is specifically designed to quantify impacts of hydrological conditions on yield, and provides spatially explicit estimates of potential gross revenue per plot (€) and expected yield loss (%) due to dry conditions.

Under the baseline, losses due to low groundwater tables amount to € 86 million per year, in the area in which groundwater tables are influenced by the water table in the river (in places up to 10 km beyond the riverbed). Ultimately, the impact of changes in river water tables on groundwater-related yield loss was quite limited in the case study area (<1%). It should be noted that this study only reviewed the impact of changes in water tables on dry conditions: further dynamic groundwater modelling is recommended to assess the role of high groundwater tables, which may offset the limited benefits of MLGT increases (Bartholomeus et al., 2011).

9.4 ES valuation: Hydropower – sediment control and base flow

Hydropower generation is increasingly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. Hydropower facilities are designed based on historical flow regimes, which in turn depend on long-term precipitation patterns and the regulating ecosystem services provided by upstream watersheds (Spolum, 2021). As these patterns shift, the reliability and efficiency of hydropower generation are at risk. Hydropower systems generally benefit from stable, predictable flows throughout the year, and limited reservoir sedimentation. Sedimentation reduces the storage capacity of the reservoir and is one of the driving factors in lifecycle cost. Reduced storage capacity makes the hydropower dam more reliant on seasonal flows, making it even more important that these are stable and predictable over the year. Peatland rewetting, upstream forest restoration and other restoration measures that improve upstream retention and slower discharge (e.g. remaindering of streams) help smooth flows over the year (Cities4Forests) and reduce sediment flows which drive costs for hydropower generation (Guo et al., 2023).

Monetising those benefits requires economic modelling to understand how 1) changes in availability of water over the year relate to local energy market demands (which affect the price) and 2) how sedimentation volumes affect the lifespan and/ or lifecycle costs of the hydropower installation. The monetary value of sediment control can also be derived using cost-based methods, for example by calculating costs related to removing sediment in reservoirs (Esen et al., 2023).

Though research on the impact of ecosystem restoration on hydropower generation is limited, existing literature shows promising results. For example, ecological restoration (including revegetation) in the Yellow River Basin in China - characterised by high sediment loads - enhances hydropower potential – reducing upstream sedimentation. There is a trade-off: restoring vegetation in the area reduced runoff rates throughout the year, but the benefits of reducing the lifespan of the installation by reducing sediment rates outweighed this effect (Wu et al., 2025). In California’s Sierra Nevada, forest restoration after wildfires has been shown to influence both the quantity and timing of water flows, benefiting downstream hydropower generation (Guo et al., 2023). When increased runoff is expected under climate change, as in Sweden’s Ume river, ensuring sustainable environmental flow can be achieved with minimal loss to hydropower production (Widén et al., 2024).

Box 9.2: : From reservoir fill level to (prevented) losses in irrigated agriculture (Sorraia, Rhine)

Upstream land use changes can affect the water balance in a reservoir, and in turn the fill level of reservoirs used for irrigation and other water uses. In the MERLIN case on the Portuguese Sorraia basin, upstream (re)forestation scenarios are studied, comparing (non-native) eucalypt plantations and native oak forest restoration: the fill level of the reservoir decreases when eucalypt plantations are installed (modelled using SWAT2012). The impact on the agricultural productivity in the irrigated system was estimated by calculating Agricultural yields in the area combining crop-specific standard output coefficients (€/ha) for Portugal (building on EU-wide dataset from ESTAT 2024), which are farm-gate value of output (or gross revenue). Assuming in an irrigated system, the availability of water directly affects crop production (1:1.3, accounting for distribution losses), a 5% reduction in water inflow translated in a loss of €1.2 mln (or €21 million present value, at discount rate 3%).

In the case of the Rhine, interventions to restore the sediment level in the riverbed altered the distribution of water across the river branches, benefiting the fill level of the IJsselmeer reservoir at the outlet of the IJssel branch. The economic impacts was calculated based on a price per m³, derived using a marginal product value approach: €0.55/m³ (including VAT, 2020), for the affected area (the national average lies at €0,67). In a situation where flow distribution is redirected towards the IJsselmeer, this gives an annual benefit of €7 mln (or €231 mln present value, at discount rate 2.25% up till 2120)

9.5 ES valuation: Inland shipping

Inland waterways benefit from sufficient channel depth (or draught) during low-flow periods – this directly affects load capacity, and in turn transport costs for shipping. Freshwater restoration measures that reduce flow velocity and thereby riverbed erosion, and measures that increase the base flow can support higher channel depth during low flow. To evaluate the impact of impact of freshwater restoration measures on navigation requires 1) modelling of hydro-morphological changes over time (e.g. Cron et al., 2015) and 2) modelling of the impacts on shipping. The latter is typically done using a production function, calculating the impact of reduced draught on the carrying capacity on ships, as illustrated in Box 9.3.

Box 9.3 : Low flows and inland shipping on the German Elbe and the Dutch Rhine branches (MERLIN CS 04)

Grossmann (2012b) analyses the impacts of climate and socio-economic changes on channel depth and corresponding inland shipping costs, along the German Elbe basin. Departing from a projection of transport demands and fleet structure over time, the impacts of changes in frequency and magnitude of low flows on the effective carrying capacity on ships are calculated via variable vessel operating costs relations. Estimated losses for transport shipping due to low-flow conditions under climate – and economic change are estimated around €28–39 mln per year by 2050 for the Elbe basin. This is in line with (Folkens et al., 2024) who present a hydro-economic model for the Middle Elbe, linking hydrological data (e.g. discharge, fairway depth) with economic variables (e.g. ship utilization, replacement costs) to simulate damage costs for freight and passenger navigation under low-flow conditions. Key findings include €15.7 million in freight shipping losses and €5.6 million in passenger shipping losses in the low-flow year 2018; damage is not only caused by extreme low flows but also by prolonged periods of slightly suboptimal water levels, as seen in 2018 and critical navigation sections consistently show higher costs.

Similarly, (Asselman et al., 2022) calculate the effects of changes in climate change and riverbed elevation on inland shipping costs in the Dutch Rhine branches. Ongoing riverbed erosion affects water depth as it sinks below fixed barriers (e.g. inlets of locks/ weirs, cables and pipes under the riverbed) and alters the discharge distribution across river branches (or navigation sections). Their findings indicate that most of the projected cost increase—€213 million—is driven by altered discharge probabilities under climate change, while riverbed erosion contributes an additional €102 million. Kok et al (2025) evaluate the effects of floodplain-river management scenarios for inland shipping in the same area. By modelling navigation demand and water depth under climate projects and resulting load capacities, the impact of reduced water depths on annual transport costs can be calculated – ranging from € 2 to 3 mln per year.

9.6 ES valuation: Water-based recreation on lakes and inland waterways

Water-based recreation—such as boating, beach activities, swimming, and angling—is highly sensitive to both water levels and water quality. Changes in water levels can affect physical access, alter the microclimate, and influence the aesthetic appeal of recreational sites (Loomis & Bair, 2023). Water quality is equally critical; for example, algal blooms—often exacerbated by higher concentrations of pollutants during low-flow conditions—can deter recreational use and pose health risks.

Several studies illustrate the economic and experiential impacts of these factors. Neher et al. (2013) found that a 12 million increase in water volume at Lakes Mead and Powell in the U.S. led to an estimated \$374,000 boost in visitor spending in tourism-related sectors. Similarly, Eiswerth et al. (2000) reported that a one-foot decline in water level resulted in a loss of \$12–18 per person annually in recreational value. Grossmann (2012b) examined the effects of low streamflow on recreational boating, particularly on minor waterways where locks operate less frequently under such conditions. This reduced frequency increases waiting times for boaters. Using contingent valuation, the study estimated that boaters were willing to pay approximately €1.20 per hour to avoid these delays.

Economic valuation of the impact of reduced water levels—and the associated decline in water quality—can be conducted using stated preference methods, such as contingent valuation or choice experiments.

Lessons learned & recommendations

- Use localized assessments for accurate valuation; the effects of low flow on drought impacts (e.g. Related to recreational use) are highly site-specific. This variability makes it challenging to develop reliable benefit transfer functions.
- For inland navigation, well-established modelling workflows to estimate impacts of low flows exist - however, these require elaborate modelling efforts, including navigation modelling to project changes in fleet composition and cargo loads and hydraulic modelling to assess impacts on navigability.
- Assessing the impacts of water availability on irrigated crops is relatively straightforward and can be done with widely available crop (and crop revenue) data. Assessing the impacts of groundwater-related damage to crops (too low/ too high) is more complex, and requires more high-resolution, sensitive groundwater models. It is good to estimate beforehand if changes are expected to have significant effects; as illustrated in the Rhine case, impacts of river water table on groundwater-related crop damage were limited. For peatland

restoration it might be more relevant to estimate wet/drought damage to crops when changing water tables (but this was not tested in MERLIN).

Further reading:

- Mens et al. (2022) [Integrated drought risk assessment to support adaptive policymaking in the Netherlands](#)
- Folkens et al. (2024) [The Hydro-Economic Modelling of Low-Flow Events on the Middle Elbe: Assessing Socio-Economic Impacts on River Navigation](#)

10 Recreation

10.1 ES logic chain

(Semi-)natural landscapes, including wetlands, floodplains and streams or rivers, offer a wide array of potential recreation opportunities: sport fishing, wildlife/ bird watching, hiking, cycling, beach recreation and water recreation such as motorboating/sailing, canoeing and swimming. Changes in this landscape or in the quality of the water affect the recreation capacity (Vermaat et al., 2013). If there is unfulfilled local recreation demand, this benefits the local population. If the area or activities offered are of sufficient size and interest, this may also attract visitors and tourists from afar. Restoration of freshwater systems may for example: increase the species abundance and diversity, attracting wildlife watchers; increase the interconnectedness and size of surface waters, of interest for water-based recreation; increase fish diversity and abundance and accessibility of open water for anglers; increase landscape diversity and quality, of interest to hikers and cyclists.

Table 12 – Recreation logic chain

Ecosystem types	Factors determining supply		Factors determining use	Potential physical metric(s)	Benefits	Main users and beneficiaries
	Ecological	Societal				
Terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems within water catchments	Extent and condition of freshwater ecosystem, availability of wildlife/ fish, landscape diversity and quality, openness of the landscape	Land use, accessibility, path density	Recreation capacity per land use type	Recreation capacity and opportunities, in turn benefiting physical and mental health	Local residents; recreation/ tourism entrepreneurs; permit issuing agencies	Terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems within water catchments

10.2 Ecosystem service quantification & valuation

Typically starting from either an analysis of increased recreation capacity based on landscape metrics (supply) or a more detailed confrontation of supply and (local) demand, the economic value of ES recreation can be estimated based on a range of methods:

- **Contingent valuation** (revealed or stated preference) to determine a willingness to pay, e.g. based on transport costs for reaching the area, entrance fees or questionnaires/ large surveys with choice experiment, expenditures to local recreation agencies (e.g. canoe or bike rental, birdwatching tours).
- **Benefit transfer.** Usually, a local study in the willingness to pay for (changes in) recreation opportunities is too much effort: it is common to use benefit transfer from primary research studies. In this case, it is good practice to find results from such studies which are as close as possible in geographic regard; similar socio-economic and demographic situation and type of (change in) landscape (quality). In this section, we discuss some examples – hiking and cycling in floodplains, angling and water-based recreation in river stretches. This is not exhaustive, other types of water-based recreation may also be affected by restoration measures – e.g. water-based recreation in lakes and reservoirs (sensitive to water quality and fluctuation in water levels).

10.2.1 Hiking and cycling in reconnected floodplains – confronting supply and demand

Changes in land cover types, the degree of openness of a landscape and path density influence the capacity of an area for hiking and cycling recreation. Whether this translates into economic value depends on proximity between recreation potential and – demand, which can be estimated using spatial models, e.g. The Natural Capital Model by De Knegt et al. (2022). This model estimates and compares local supply (linked to land cover and path density data) and demand within specified distances for walking and cycling, resulting in remaining demand per grid cell. This can be monetized using spatial data on population density, the number of desired activities per person/year and prices per activity. These prices vary between countries, but De Nocker et al.

(2016) report, based on meta-analysis of European contingent valuation studies, an average of €1.8 per walking activity and €3.7 per cycling trip (2023 price level).

Box 10.1 : Valuation of Walking and Cycling Recreation in MERLIN CS 04 Room for the Rhine branches

Using the Natural Capital Model (De Knecht et al., 2022), walking and cycling recreation supply was quantified for various river – and floodplain management strategies with distinct land use/ land cover – especially the 'Living Rivers' strategy involved a shift from agricultural to natural land uses. By comparing local supply and demand within 10 km (walking) and 20 km (cycling) of residences, unfulfilled demand was assessed – fulfilling this demand has an economic value, as local recreation in green space has low substitutability. The changes in unfulfilled demand were monetised using activity frequency (47.3 walking and 14.6 cycling activities/person/year) and willingness-to-pay data (€1.80 per walk, €3.70 per cycle derived from Nocker et al 2016; price level 2023).

Overall, the benefits were very modest (max. €0.3 million/year) due to very low unfulfilled demand – only in the Lek branch, situated about 8 kms from the city of Utrecht there is a slight benefit of increasing recreation capacity. In the Netherlands, (local) recreation capacity shortages are found mostly in the big urban areas in the West. It should be noted that the approach followed in this case does not include supra-local tourism – with the potential creation of a large, interconnected natural area, it seems likely recreation/ tourism benefits are underestimated in this case.

10.2.2 Angling in reconnected floodplains

Floodplain reconnection, creation of (permanently flowing) side channels and other interventions that affect the occurrence, quality and connectedness of floodplain waters increase the potential for angling. We highlight three studies that have quantified or monetized this service:

Villamagna (2014) quantify freshwater recreational fishing capacity and demand in North Carolina and Virginia with a GIS-based approach. The study maps the capacity of ecosystems to support freshwater recreational fishing using biophysical factors (surface water area, game-fish species richness, water quality and riparian area) and social factors (accessibility, public awareness/ advertisement and game-fish stocking) and assesses societal demand for this service using fishing license data. By comparing these maps, the approach can identify areas where demand may exceed ecological capacity, which can inform sustainable management of the area. A disadvantage of this approach is that although the capacity approach is suitable for scenario analysis, it is difficult to estimate demand elasticity based on existing data.

Funk (2021) analyses the potential of floodplain reconnection to increase the capacity for water-based recreation. The starting point is a GIS-layer for floodplain water body areas where angling is permitted. By mapping direct loss of area due to restoration measures as well as indirect effects due to a loss of accessibility, changes in the potential. Additionally, habitat availability was used as a generic quality parameter, as a proxy for the diversity of habitats experienced during a recreational activity. As such, both a change in surface area of water bodies and a 'qualitative' change in nature experience can increase the value or capacity of freshwater recreation.

Kok et al (2025 & submitted) analyze quantify and monetize the value of reconnecting floodplains for angling by estimating the number of increased recreational fishing spots (defined as a 500-m shoreline stretch) using GIS and detailed land cover maps. Accessibility was assessed based on proximity to minor roads, with suitability decreasing over the first 250 meters from access points (Eeuwes et al., 2019). The demand elasticity was estimated based on survey data from the Dutch association of sport fishers, reflecting how many fishers would increase their activity if quality or amount of fishing spots in the floodplains improved. Combined with data on the (desired) number of fishing trips per year and the average expenditure per trip (for the Netherlands estimated at €65.70, Kantar 2021), the economic benefits of floodplain reconnection are estimated.

10.2.3 Water-based recreation on re-connected river stretch

Measures such as dam removal that shorten or extend uninterrupted and navigable river stretches affect the potential for recreational boating. In the AMBERS project, benefit transfer methods were used to create an approach for quantifying and monetizing impacts on boating routes (e.g. individual motorboats or canoes; or commercial river cruise or tour boats). First, the number of users affected by the measures should be estimated, in terms of number of tourists and average distance travelled by boat (ideally using weir and dam statistics; otherwise via expert-based assessment or local data from rental companies and tourism

associations). Changes in the potential for recreational boating may have no effect on holiday duration, lead to a shorter holiday or full relocation to another area – particularly when uninterrupted boating routes fall below 13 kilometers. By multiplying the number of boats in the area with average time spent (based on weir statistics and boat-type-specific use rates) and the willingness to pay per year per boat (€932.02 / canoe / year and motorboats €2,618.65 / motorboat / year based on Roesch et al. (2025), price level 2021), this service can be monetized – although the method is not yet well established, and especially the number of boat users has proven hard to estimate.

Lessons learned & recommendations

- Take into account demand elasticity - increased recreational capacity does not automatically lead to increased use. Demand elasticity can be modelled or estimated using stated or observed preferences (e.g. fishing licenses, user surveys, data from recreation agencies).
- The value of recreation opportunities is higher in areas with unmet recreational demand, as illustrated in the Rhine case: restoration projects yield higher economic returns when implemented near urban centers or regions with limited access to nature.
- It is expected that large-scale floodplain restoration has the potential to attract supra-local recreation and tourism benefits – therefore, including both local and regional recreation dynamics in CBA would improve the relevance of valuation for long-term spatial planning.

11 Habitat provision

11.1 ES logic chain

The ecosystem service "**habitat provision**" captures the **availability** and **quality** (functional and structural) of habitats in rivers and floodplains. It reflects ecological functioning, biodiversity, and the capacity of ecosystems to support a wide range of species (Podschun et al., 2018). As such, habitat provision is generally viewed as an intermediate ESS, that contributes to delivery of other ecosystem services, such as healthy fish populations, nutrient cycling or recreational opportunities. Aside from contributing to these 'use values', habitat provision also contributes to non-use values, such as the bequest and existence value people place on biodiversity and the intrinsic worth of nature: in this chapter we focus on the non-use value.

Restoration measures, such as rewetting peatlands and reconnecting floodplains, are expected to significantly improve wetland and riparian habitat provision. These hydrological interventions increase habitat heterogeneity, restore natural processes, and support the recovery of characteristic species and communities. In turn, they enable a wider range of ecosystem functions and services.

Table 13 – Habitat provision logic chain.

Ecosystem types	Factors determining supply		Factors determining use	Potential physical metric(s)	Benefits	Main users and beneficiaries
	Ecological	Societal				
Peatland, wetlands, rivers and lakes	Hydrological regime (flow variability), landscape connectivity, water quality, morphology	Land use, disruption	(as a final service) - perceived importance, cultural attachment, socio-economic and demographic factors	Habitat area and condition; landscape connectivity, species diversity, population density (Marshall et al, 2020)	Willingness to pay for bequest/ existence of freshwater species, reduced costs for achieving policy goals	Society at large, public agencies

11.2 ES quantification

Quantifying habitat provision requires robust indicators that reflect ecosystem structure, function, and response to restoration. Ideally, indicators are sensitive to spatial scale, ecological context, and data availability. In practice, many studies rely on habitat attributes, area-based and connectivity metrics (Marshall et al., 2020). A key challenge lies in the complexity of modelling and combining indicators relevant for freshwater species: many published models are biased towards terrestrial ecosystems and focus on long-term climate change as main driver, rather than short-term drivers that can be addressed through restoration. As such, there is a need to develop integrated models that can assess impact of (changes in) drivers on biodiversity and ecosystems (IPBES, 2016). Hydrological process models can be used to link changes in land cover and management to changes in quantity or quality of freshwater habitats, which in turn may be linked to species distribution models, habitat suitability models or community-level methods to predict changes in species richness, diversity or functioning. In practice, a wide range of (simple) indicators is available that can be used, including the proportion of typical floodplain habitats, land use intensity and cover, presence of protected areas (e.g. Natura 2000), structural quality of rivers and floodplains and biological indicators (e.g. species composition or WFD status). As there is no internationally agreed best practice, and relevant indicators and modelling approaches also strongly depend on scale and local context, Box 11.1-11.3 provide a few examples.

Box 11.1 : Habitat indicators in river-floodplain policy evaluation in Germany

In Germany, several indicators have been applied in evaluating river management policy. In the RESI project, Podschun et al. (2018) assess and quantify a ESS habitat index for the habitats of floodplains and rivers separately, on a 0 to 5 point-rating scale. For floodplains, the rating is based on the existing biotope types and their quality and on an assessment at the river-floodplain section level. For the river itself, the rating is based on biologically relevant watercourse structures, using the Valmorph method (Roesch et al., 2025, based on Quick et al., 2020) to assess morphological quality and biological indicators from the WFD, including fish, benthic invertebrates and macrophytes. In the AMBERS project a similar approach is used, awarding a bonus or malus to the rating for changes in flooding regime and chemical status of the waterbody (Roesch et al., 2025). Figure 9 shows an application of the RESI index on the case of the Ammer (Bavaria). The index is based on biotope types, with value adjusted for land use intensity, floodplain connectivity, and conservation status (e.g., Natura 2000 habitats). Higher scores are assigned to areas with natural vegetation, low disturbance, and ecological uniqueness. The habitat quality increases in the riparian reforestation scenario because land use intensity is reduced and additional areas are allowed to undergo natural succession into riparian forest. These forests are rare and ecologically valuable in Germany, and therefore receive a higher score.

Figure 9 – Restoration scenarios in comparison with status quo and its impact on changing habitat provision in Germany (Becker et al., 2022)

Box 11.2 : Habitat provision – policy achievement indicator for the Rhine in the Netherlands (MERLIN CS 04)

As part of a wider ecosystem service assessment of river-floodplain management scenarios of the Rhine in the Netherlands, Kok et al. (2025) developed a habitat provision indicator based on policy achievement, in order to assess the effectiveness of river-floodplain management (RFM) strategies in meeting habitat targets set under the Programmatic Approach Large Waters (PAGW). Habitat targets under the PAGW were determined using the LARCH model (van der Sluis et al., 2020), which uses species-specific area requirements to derive minimum habitat sizes and connectivity thresholds needed to support sustainable populations of key target species. The policy achievement indicator used in Kok et al. (2025) is a similarity index ranging from 0 to >1, comparing the actual surface area of natural ecotopes under each RFM strategy to the desired ecotope distribution stipulated in the PAGW.

Box 11.3 : National habitat provision indicator for scenario analysis in Germany and the Netherlands (MERLIN CS 04)

The MAES framework supports biodiversity indicators that can be used in national biodiversity monitoring and planning (Maes et al., 2016); for example the Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII; an aggregated indicator of species abundance and reference conditions) and Mean Species Abundance (MSA). Additionally, several member states have developed their own indicators.

In Germany the ecosystem service indicator “habitat provision” can be assessed, calculated and monetised based on the value of a biotope’s condition “Biotopwertpunkte” or Biotope value system. This value type describes the change in condition of a biotope before and after a measure. The condition type is regulated by the “Federal Compensation Ordinance” or in some cases the state’s individual compensation ordinance regulations, which use biotope value points to determine ecological compensation measures for interventions in nature (Ekinici et al., 2022). For the ordinance, calculating the condition of an ecosystem per hectare, based on criteria including age of an ecosystem, occurrence of threatened species, and naturalness. Classification of ecosystem condition in ratios from 0 (paved ground) to 24 (intact peat bogs, old (semi-) natural forests). Attribution of value to a comprehensive and consistent system of nation-wide data on ecosystem extent and condition based on German land cover, forestry, an EU directive’s data. Data weighing and aggregating to a physical number (e.g. C02).

In the Netherlands, the biodiversity points approach (‘natuurpunten’) (Bos and Ruijs, 2019), a standardised, transparent method to quantify the ecological impact of project alternatives, is recommended for use in CBA. The approach is a threat-weighted Ecological Quality Area, and is calculated based on the size of the ecosystem affected, the ecological quality (a score of 0-1) based on species presence v.s. intact reference ecosystems and a threat weight – reflecting the rarity and conservation priority of the ecosystem. A noted limitation is that the approach is less developed for water-quality related biodiversity due to diffuse impact areas and context-dependent quality metrics.

11.3 ES valuation

Beyond quantitative metrics to assess the impact of FWE restoration on habitat provision, various methods can be used to value this service. Valuation approaches for habitat provision are typically non-market-based, involving proxy methods such as using stated preference to derive a willingness to pay (WTP), or restoration and compensation costs. Stated preferences approaches are less accepted in some countries, which instead suggest presenting a habitat indicator alongside the cost-benefit analysis (e.g. in Dutch CBA guidance, Renes & Romijn, 2013) or using a restoration/ compensation cost approach.

11.3.1 Stated preferences

Stated preference methods, such as contingent valuation and choice experiments, can be used to monetize the habitat provision service by capturing the non-use values people assign to biodiversity and ecosystem restoration. These values reflect the societal importance of preserving nature for future generations (bequest value) and the intrinsic worth of ecosystems regardless of direct use (existence value). These methods estimate the willingness to pay (WTP) for improvements in wildlife habitats, which, with careful design, can be used to distinguish the use value (e.g. recreation) from non-use values (reflecting bequest and existence values). This is important to prevent double counting with other ecosystem services such as recreation (see

also chapter 12). If a direct valuation study is out of scope – they are resource-intensive – a meta-regression analysis can be used to derive a benefit transfer function. For example, Brouwer & Sheremet (2017) explicitly study the WTP for the function 'wildlife habitat' as a result of river restoration. Box 11.4 on the Rhine case provides an example of the application of such a benefit transfer function in a cost-benefit analysis.

Box 11.4 : Benefit transfer for valuation of habitat provision in MERLIN CS04 Room for the Rhine branches

In the Rhine Branches study (Kok et al, submitted), a benefit transfer function was developed to estimate households' willingness to pay (WTP) for biodiversity improvements based on a meta-regression analysis of European wetland valuation studies (Grossmann, 2012a). The function incorporates key variables such as the size of the restored area, average household income, and the degree of ecological improvement (linked to the policy achievement indicator, see box 11.2). The resulting WTP estimates ranged from €5.50 to €28.70 per household per year, depending on the degree of restoration in the strategy. These estimates were aggregated across the population to using a uniform distance decay function - assuming that the value people assign to habitat improvements diminishes with increasing distance from the restoration site due to place attachment. The market area was defined as 35 km radius around study area, based on empirical results for water quality improvements in the Netherlands (Schaafsma et al., 2012).

11.3.2 Restoration and Compensation Cost Approaches

Ecological damage and/ or the value of ecological restoration can be monetized using a cost-based approach, under the assumption that restoration or exchange yields an equivalent amount of ecosystem services. This cost-based value reflects total economic value, including use and non-use components, and can therefore not be used alongside other ecosystem service valuations to prevent double-counting. There is no standardized or widely accepted approach for monetizing losses or gains in habitat provision: existing methods vary significantly across regions and institutions. The following examples from the EU, Germany, and the USA illustrate how the cost-based approach to value habitat provision can be applied in practice.

The EU Handbook on the external costs of transport (van Essen et al., 2019) includes a method for estimating the negative effects on nature and landscape – including effects of habitat loss and degradation. Based on restoration costs, cost factors for all EU countries have been calculated, ranging from €3000-11.000 €/km/year for 'damage to inland waterways'.

In Germany, a standardized biotope value point system is used to guide restoration investment and compensation requirements under the planning law (Schweppe-Kraft et al., 2020). Habitats are scored from 0 (sealed surfaces) to 24 (high-value habitats like intact peat bogs) using a standardized ecological matrix, with adjustments of ± 3 points allowed based on field condition (e.g. degradation or exceptional quality). Three methods can be used to determine the monetary value per biotope value points (Ekinci et al., 2022; Schweppe-Kraft et al., 2023): 1) restoration investment cost (based on cost for achieving EU habitats directive: 3,634€ per biotope value point), 2) compensation market value (preliminary findings from habitat banking transactions; 16,000€ per point) and 3) WTP per point (based on WTP for national nature conservation programmes: 7800€).

In the USA, a similar approach is used to determine required compensation or restoration investment in case of ecological damage, which can also be used to assess the value of pro-active restoration projects: the Habitat Equivalency Analysis (HEA) (NOAA, 2006). The HEA uses a service-to-service approach (assuming a one-to-one trade-off in ecological services), but can also incorporate stated preference methods, e.g. to estimate non-use values, or address equity and distributional concerns. In the service-to-service approach, restoration is scaled so that quantity and quality of ecosystem services provided over time by the restoration project match those lost by the damage. The approach includes 1) Estimating the loss of ecological services over time until natural recovery. 2) Identifying restoration alternatives: These include both primary restoration (returning the resource to baseline) and compensatory restoration (offsetting interim losses), and 3) Scaling restoration: Determining the size and scope of restoration needed so that the present discounted value of ecological gains equals the present discounted value of losses. The approach indirectly accounts for restoration time: the longer it takes for a system to recover, the greater the interim loss.

Figure 10 – Biotope overview map of Germany and assigned biotope value points per biotope type (Ekinci et al., 2022).

Lessons learned & recommendations

- Habitat provision is an intermediate ESS that supports other services by maintaining ecological structures and biodiversity; however, the bequest or existence value of this service can be monetized using stated preference methods or benefit transfer functions. There is no standardized method for this. Primary valuation studies can be resource-intensive, so benefit-transfer of WTP may be more realistic.
- Quantitative indicators like biotope value points can be used to reflect (changes in) habitat quality (or quantity), and can be either 1) presented alongside monetized benefits in a CBA, 2) monetized, as demonstrated by Schweppe-Kraft et al. (2023) or 3) embedded in a benefit transfer function, as illustrated in the Rhine case (Box 11.4). Monetary valuation of biotope value points (e.g. using a restoration costs approach) is a relatively new field and deriving them can be methodologically challenging.
- Cost-based methods can be used to represent the total economic value for ecosystem restoration – as these estimates cover all ecosystem services they can therefore not be used alongside other ecosystem services.

Further reading:

(Schweppe-Kraft et al., 2023) [Ecosystem services for conservation of biodiversity/species and habitats. In: Nature under pressure.](#)

(Brouwer and Sheremet, 2017) [The economic value of river restoration](#) – meta-analysis, including assessment of WTP for habitat provision.

12 Biomass provision

12.1 ES logic chain

The biomass provision ES is the contribution of ecosystems to the growth of biomass that is harvested by economic agents for various uses such as production of food, fibre, fodder and energy.

Table 14 – Biomass provision logic chain.

Ecosystem types	Factors determining supply		Factors determining use	Potential physical metric(s)	Benefits	Main users and beneficiaries
	Ecological	Societal				
Peatlands, wetlands, floodplains	Soil fertility, climate, water supply	Farm management	Demand for biomass	Tons dry matter per ha	Food, fibre, fodder, energy	Farmers, households, Energy, Manufacturing

Freshwater ecosystems restoration may have multiple effects on biomass provision. The effects of FWE restoration may involve changes in land use. Such changes may lead to foregone biomass provision, for instance when a floodplain farmland is converted to natural ecosystems. By convention, foregone biomass provision is accounted for as costs in a CBA (opportunity costs). Land use changes may also provide opportunities for new production, such as pluviculture on wetlands (de Jongh et al., 2021; Wichmann, 2017) or extensive livestock grazing in floodplains, accounted for as biomass provision benefits. FWE restoration may also bear indirect effects on biomass provision, through changes in hydrology (e.g. groundwater recharge) or habitat for functional biodiversity (pollinators, natural pest enemies). Such indirect effects may be estimated by quantifying changes in intermediate ES supporting biomass provision (e.g. water provision, pollination, natural pest control). This section is focused on estimating the direct effects of restoration on biomass provision. Effects of hydrology changes on agricultural production are addressed in Section 8 on drought risk mitigation.

12.2 ES quantification

Biomass provision is straightforwardly quantified as harvested biomass, e.g. tons of reed dry matter per ha of peatland, using existing national agricultural and forestry statistics or field survey data. In the absence of national data, EU-wide datasets on crop types areas and yields also exist (see Annex 1). As harvested yields can vary greatly from year to year due to weather fluctuations, it is advisable to use multiple year averages.

Note that in most cases, biomass provision is a joint production process that involves human interventions (management, harvest) in combination with ecosystems contributions (e.g. water and nutrients cycling, pollination and pest control). Methods are being developed to disentangle human and ecosystem contributions (Wijngaart et al., 2019). In the context of a CBA of freshwater ecosystems restoration, separating human from ecosystem contributions in biophysical terms is not relevant, and the service can be quantified by harvested yields.

12.3 ES valuation

Monetary valuation studies of biomass provision ES usually attempt to value specifically the contribution of ecosystems to biomass provision. Three methods can be applied: production functions, land rental prices and resource rents. The contribution of land to biomass provision can be derived from a production function in which the production output is a function of land (the ecosystem), labour, capital and other factors. Such production functions allow to assess the marginal productivity of the land (ecosystem) to output, and, multiplying this marginal land productivity by the output price, the biomass provision ES value. In practice, applying this method requires the availability of farm level data on farm inputs and outputs which is often not available. As workaround, land rental prices can be used to approximate the marginal land productivity. However, land rental prices may not always represent a valid approximation of marginal land productivity, for instance in case of market distortion or land speculation. In the resource rent method, the contribution of land to biomass provision is the residual value of the biomass output after subtracting all other inputs values (farm inputs, capital, labour), derived from national statistics on farm incomes and production costs. A drawback of the resource rent method is that provides very variable estimates, sometimes negative, due to sometimes large annual variations of output yields and prices. It is therefore advised to use averages over multiple years.

In a social CBA, separating the values of ecosystem and human contributions is not relevant. It is more appropriate to use the total value of biomass production, i.e. total yield multiplied by prices, which indicates the benefit for societal welfare of the restoration project. However, the resource rent method, which is an

estimation of farming net incomes (after deducting production costs from product sales), can be useful to determine the effects of restoration on the farming sector (see Section 13).

Lessons learned & recommendations

- For a social CBA, it is recommended to use biomass yields and market prices to value the biomass provision ES.
- Methods used in the ES science domain to separate ecosystem and human contributions to biomass provision are not adapted to social CBA but may be useful to assess the effects of restoration on the farming sector.

Further reading:

- Joosten et al. (2016) [Paludiculture: sustainable productive use of wet and rewetted peatlands \(Vol. 10\)](#).

13 Connecting a social CBA to private financing of freshwater ecosystems restoration

This report provides guidance and recommendations for carrying out a social Cost - Benefit Analysis of FWE restoration. A social CBA evaluates costs and benefits of restoration for the whole society, aggregating benefits and costs of all public and private stakeholders. The primary aim is to determine whether it is in the interest of society as a whole to invest in the restoration project, not to estimate costs and benefits of FWE restoration for specific economic sectors. However, through the identification and quantification of a large range of societal benefits, a social CBA may be a valuable starting point for developing private (co)funding sources, e.g. through conventional markets (e.g. valorisation of biomass, recreation services), payment for ecosystem services or environmental markets (e.g. carbon credits) (see MERLIN Deliverable 3.6).

This report presents several methods for the monetary valuation of ESs in a social CBA context. Not all these methods deliver useful outputs for informing private funding opportunities. To be useful in development of a business case, special attention should be paid to attributing costs and benefits to specific (private, local) stakeholders, and valuation methods should be related to revenues or costs incurred by specific sectors; there is a disconnect between the sometimes abstract values of ecosystem values and practical application in non-public settings (Siebers et al, 2025). Table 15 presents an overview of which monetary valuation methods are preferred from a welfare-economics perspective, and which methods are most suited for informing a (co)funding/ financing strategy. For instance, while valuing carbon sequestration with social costs of carbon or efficient prices is recommended in a welfare economics perspective, in a context of generating revenues only the actual carbon credit prices on voluntary carbon market are relevant.

Table 15 – Recommended monetary valuation approaches for social vs business case.

Ecosystem Service	Social CBA	Business case	Potential funding source
Flood risk mitigation	Avoided damage costs Replacement costs	Avoided damage costs	Businesses (farms, industries, commercial units) exposed to flood risks and flood insurance sector
Climate change mitigation	Social cost of carbon, efficient carbon prices	Carbon market prices (voluntary or compliance)	Businesses compensating their GHG emissions
Nutrients retention	Replacement costs Avoided damage costs/social costs of nutrients	Water treatment costs Loss of recreation value	Water supply companies Water-based recreation businesses
Drought mitigation	Market price/ production function Replacement cost Avoided damage costs, Stated preference	Avoided damage costs Market price/ production function	Navigation sector, hydropower sector, water-based recreation businesses, water users (drinking water, irrigation, cooling water)
Recreation	Contingent valuation/Choice Experiment	Nature recreation business activity (e.g. resource rent of recreation sector)	Water-based recreation businesses
Habitat provision	Contingent valuation/Choice Experiment Restoration costs	Habitat banking, biodiversity market prices	Businesses compensating their impacts on biodiversity
Biomass provision	Market prices, resource rent, land prices, production function	Resource rent, production function	Farmers, land managers

Other key difference between social CBA and business cases include the timing of benefits, the time horizon of the assessment and the degree of details in the cost assessment. For instance, in a social CBA, carbon

sequestration benefits are accounted for from the first year when restoration effects on carbon sequestration take place. In a business case, the benefits only start to accrue when carbon credits are sold (depending on the contract, this may be a one-time payment or periodic), which may be at least 3 to 5 years after the first year when restoration effects on carbon sequestration take place. This can have important impacts on the financial viability of a project, especially since the discount rate used in private business plans is higher than in a social CBA. Similarly, the time horizons of interest in private sector are much shorter (2-10 years) than the horizon used to assess the societal benefits in a social CBA (20-100 years, see section 2.3). To inform a (co-)funding or financing strategy, a detailed understanding of the project cost structure and timing across the project lifecycle is needed, whereas the assessment of costs in a social CBA relies on unit cost estimates (see also section 3).

Though a social CBA is not directly transferable to a private investment setting, it provides valuable inputs for developing private (co)funding strategies. Estimates of the biophysical effects of restoration - such as tons of C sequestered, reduction in flood risk or maintenance of base streamflow - can deliver key inputs to assess benefits and costs of restoration for economic sectors. When doing so, specific monetary valuation methods that provide usable monetary estimates for private stakeholders should be used - those that reflect market prices, cost savings or revenue generation potential.

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Annex 1: Useful data sets and models

Data sets

Flood risk mitigation

- [Global damage depth functions](#) (Huizinga et al, 2017)
- [Corine Land Cover dataset](#) (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service)
- [River flood hazard maps for Europe and the Mediterranean Basin region](#) (JRC)
- [EEA flood risk areas viewer](#) (EEA)
- [Climate change mitigation](#)
- EEA (2022): [rates of carbon storage and sequestration in EU terrestrial and marine ecosystems](#)
- [IPCC \(2022\) Emission Factors database](#)

Biomass provision

- Copernicus Land Monitoring Service: High Resolution Layer Croplands, <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/high-resolution-layer-croplands>
- Copernicus Land Monitoring Service: High Resolution Layer Grasslands, <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/high-resolution-layer-grasslands>
- Copernicus Land Monitoring Service: High Resolution Layer Tree Cover and Forests, <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/high-resolution-layer-grasslands>, <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/high-resolution-layer-forests-and-tree-cover>
- Farm Accountancy Data Network database: <https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/FarmEconomyFocus/FADNDatabase.html>

MERLIN modelling tools

MERLIN Deliverable 3.3: The MERLIN modelling workflow to assess the biophysical and economic impact of freshwater ecosystem restoration at catchment scale.

https://plugins.qgis.org/plugins/water_purification/

<https://plugins.qgis.org/plugins/floodriskswatplus/>

Hydrological and hydraulic modelling tools

SWAT+ : The Soil & Water Assessment Tool is a small watershed to river basin-scale model used to simulate the quality and quantity of surface and ground water and predict the environmental impact of land use, land management practices, and climate change <https://swat.tamu.edu/software/plus/>

FloodAdapt: [open-source decision support software tool](#)

Ecosystem Services Modelling tools

InVEST is a suite of free, open-source models used to map and value ecosystem services:

<https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest>

INCA Tool is a QGIS plugin to support the calculation of ecosystem services accounts: <https://ecosystem-accounts.jrc.ec.europa.eu/index.php/inca-tool>

Artificial Intelligence for Environment & Sustainability (ARIES) for SEEA is an open-source digital tool to support the compilation of natural capital accounts: <https://aries.integratedmodelling.org/project/aries-for-seea/>

Nature Braid is an environmental and spatial framework that illustrates the impacts of land use, management, climate, etc on the environment and associated ecosystem services: <https://naturebraid.org/>

Annex 2: Detailed description of MERLIN plugin to value flood risk mitigation benefits

Methodological approach

The MERLIN plugin is methodologically based on the calculation of the average annual value of flood risk mitigation benefits through the calculation of the expected annual damage (EAD) (Dierauer et al., 2012).

This method assumes that flood damage costs are a continuous function of the probability of flood events. The expected annual flood damage (EAD) equals the (blue shaded) area under the flood damage costs curve, which is the integral of this damage probability function. The EAD can be approximated with the following formula :

$$EAD = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{D_{i+1} + D_i}{2} \times \left(\frac{1}{R_i} - \frac{1}{R_{i+1}} \right), \text{ Eq. 1}$$

Where n is the number of return periods, D_i is the flood damage cost corresponding to the return period R_i .

Figure 11 – Estimation of floods EAD from the flood damage probability function

This formula requires estimating damage costs corresponding to several flood return periods. These estimates should cover a representative range of flood events, capturing highly frequent low damage to low probability high damage flood events.

The EAD is calculated for the baseline and FWE restoration scenarios, and the flood risk mitigation benefit is calculated by subtracting the restoration scenario EAD from the baseline scenario EAD.

In the MERLIN approach, D_i , the flood damage cost corresponding to each return period R_i , is calculated by using existing flood extent and depth maps, land use data and flood depth – damage functions.

$$D_i = \sum_{j=1}^c DF_{ijk} \times V_{jk}, \text{ Eq. 2}$$

Where: c is the number of flood extent and depth map units, DF_{ijk} is the flood damage fraction for return period i and land use k in map unit j, V_{jk} is the economic value of land use k in map unit j.

$$DF_{ijk} = f(\text{Depth}_{ij}), \text{ Eq. 3}$$

Where Depth_{ij} is the flood depth for return period i and map unit j.

To estimate flood risk mitigation benefits, the plugin models the change in EAD due to restoration of FWE.

$$\Delta EAD = EAD_{\text{baseline}} - EAD_{\text{restoration}}, \text{ Eq. 4}$$

The plugin only uses a hydrological model, SWAT+, which allows to model the effect of restoration on the return periods/probabilities of peak stream flows and associated flood events (see MERLIN Deliverable 3.3). SWAT+ generates average daily flow rate output values at river section level, that can be used to estimate restoration induced changes in peak flow probabilities at river section level. The probability of flood damage in a raster cell of the flood damage map is then derived from the change in peak flow probabilities of the closest (Euclidean distance) river section.

Therefore, in Equation 1, only R_i changes between the baseline and restoration scenarios. D_i is kept constant and has to be provided as input data by users of the plugin. The next section provides guidance on methods and data sources to generate these inputs.

Figure 12 – Estimation of restoration effects on floods EAD

Methods and data sources to produce flood damage costs maps

A flood damage costs map corresponding to each flood return period R_i is needed to calculate D_i (see Eq. 1). Flood damage costs maps provide an estimate of flood damage costs for each map unit j (D_{ij}), which are summed over the total number map units, c , to calculate D_i . Flood damage costs for each map unit j are the product of the land use value of this map unit (V_{jk}) and the damage fraction (DF_{ijk}) due to floods (Eq. 2). To obtain V_{jk} a land use map and economic values of each land use class of the land use map are needed. Damage fraction (DF_{ijk}) due to floods in map unit j are derived from flood depth – damage functions, that relate DF_{ijk} to flood depth in map unit j , $Depth_{ij}$. Flood depth in map unit j is obtained from a flood extent and depth map. Thus, four different data sources are needed: a land use map, land use classes economic values, flood depth – damage functions and flood extent and depth maps for each flood return period.

The Freshwater Information System for Europe – Flood Risk Areas Viewer of the EEA Europe (<https://discomap.eea.europa.eu/floodsvviewer/>) provides links to flood extent and depth maps produced by EU member states in response to the EU Floods Directive.

National data sources on land use maps, land use classes economic values and flood depth – damage functions are the preferred option and may be available in many EU countries. When it is not the case, default EU data may be used. We present hereunder an approach based on EU data that has been applied to MERLIN CS CBAs.

The global database in Huizinga et al. (2017) provides Europe-specific flood depth – damage functions (damage % as a function of flood depth) for 6 land use classes (residential, commercial, industry, transport, infrastructure, agriculture). Moreover, this dataset provides country specific maximum damage values for those 6 land use classes.

Land use data was obtained from the Corine Land Cover dataset (<https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/corine-land-cover>). CLC classes were cross-linked to the 6 land use classes in Huizinga et al. (2017) (Table 16).

Table 16– Cross link of CLC classes and Huizinga et al. (2017) land use classes

CLC class level 1/2/3	Huizinga et al. (2017) land use class
1.1 Urban fabric (including all level 3 sub-classes)	Residential
1.2.1 Industrial or commercial units	Commercial & Industry
1.2.2 Road and rail networks and associated land	Infrastructure
1.2.3 Port areas	Transport
1.2.4 Airports	Transport
1.3.3 Construction sites	Residential
1.4.1 Green urban areas	Residential
1.4.2 Sport and leisure facilities	Residential
2. Agricultural areas	Agriculture

Note: Level 3 classes mineral extraction sites (1.3.1) and dump sites (1.3.2), as well as level 1 classes (including all level 2 and 3 sub-classes) forest and semi-natural areas, wetlands and water bodies did not have any corresponding land use class in Huizinga et al. (2017). Therefore, no flood damage is calculated on these land use/land cover classes.

Flood depth – damage functions in Huizinga et al. (2017) consist of look-up tables with 9 discrete flood depth points (0, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 meter) and their corresponding damage fractions (range 0 – 1). Using these values, we fitted quadratic/cubic functions for each land use class (Table 17).

Table 17– Flood depth – damage functions

Land Use Class	Depth Damage Function (y = Damage Fraction (0-1), x = flood depth in meters)
Residential	$y = -0.0275x^2 + 0.3166x + 0.066$
Commercial	$y = -0.0284x^2 + 0.3398x - 0.0069$
Industrial	$y = -0.0225x^2 + 0.3055x - 0.004$
Transport	$y = -0.054x^2 + 0.4659x + 0.0803$
Infrastructure	$y = -0.034x^2 + 0.3579x + 0.0576$
Agriculture	$y = 0.0097x^3 - 0.1288x^2 + 0.5882x + 0.0273$
Commercial & industrial*	$y = -0.0255x^2 + 0.32265x - 0.00545$

* As the land use class Commercial and Industrial correspond to only one class in the CLC dataset, we estimated a joint depth – damage function for the Industrial or commercial units CLC class by averaging the coefficients of the commercial and industrial depth – damage functions.

These functions allow to determine a damage fraction for flood depth values (between 0 and 6 meter) that are provided by flood extent and depth maps. When flood and extent maps provide single depth values per map unit (continuous data), those flood depth values can be directly used in the depth damage functions. When

flood and extent depth maps provide ranges for depth values per map unit (categorical data), a unique flood depth value per depth category needs to be determined. For instance, the flood extent and depth maps used in the Forth CS had three flood depth classes: Less than 0.3m, 0.3m to 1m and Greater than 1m. To estimate damage fractions, we used the mid-range value for the two first classes (0.15 and 0.65 m.) and a value just above the lower bound for the third class (1.1 m.) to avoid over-estimation.

Finally, the economic value of land use classes needs to be converted from 2010 euros to current year euros to consider inflation.

$$V_{yr} = V_{2010} \times (1 + r)^{(yr-2010)}, \text{ Eq. 5}$$

Where V_{yr} is the land use value in current year euros, r is the average inflation rate between 2010 and current year, yr is the current year.

The average value of the commercial and industrial classes is assigned to the Industrial or commercial units CLC class.

Annex 3: Detailed description of MERLIN plugin to value nutrient retention benefits

The MERLIN plugin values the nutrient retention service provided by ecosystems in a water catchment on the assumption that the service would be replaced by constructed wetlands if it did not exist. This approach was adapted from La Notte et al. (2017). Replacement constructed wetlands are dimensioned to provide a nutrient retention service equivalent to the service provided by the restoration of ecosystems. The biophysical outputs of SWAT+ (see D3.3) - water flows, nutrients inputs and losses - are used to quantify the provided nutrient retention service. The service can be modelled for Nitrogen, Phosphorus or both Nitrogen and Phosphorus retention. In the equations below, N means Nutrients, either Nitrogen or Phosphorus.

The replacement CW surface area is calculated for each landscape unit and the outlet channel in the water catchment using Eq. 1.

$$A_s = \frac{12 \cdot Q}{k} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{c_i - c^*}{c_e - c^*}\right), \text{ Eq. 1}$$

Where A_s is the CW surface area (in m^2),

Q is the monthly streamflow (in m^3/month),

k is an areal constant (m/year); for nitrogen removal $k = k_{20} \cdot \theta^{(T-20)}$ where T is temperature of the water in degree Celsius, k_{20} is 30.6 and θ is 1.102 for FWS CW (Kadlec & Wallace, 2009; La Notte et al., 2017),

c_i is the outlet N concentration (in mg/L) in the baseline scenario,

c_e is the outlet N concentration (in mg/L) in the restoration scenario,

c^* is the background N concentration, assumed to be 0 mg/L.

The ratio c_i/c_e , i.e. the concentration of N outputs in the baseline scenario over the concentration of N outputs in the restoration scenario, quantifies the nutrient retention provided by restoration in each landscape unit and the outlet channel, which is also dependent on the volume of treated water, Q . c_i , c_e and Q are derived from the SWAT+ model outputs at a yearly resolution for landscape units and channels (see Equations 2,3,4,5,6 and 7 below).

Calculation of the replacement CW area for landscape units

$$c_i = \frac{N_{out} \cdot 100}{q}, \text{ Eq. 2}$$

Where c_i is the yearly average outlet N concentration (in mg/L) in the baseline scenario,

N_{out} is the yearly total N mass (in kg/ha) leaving the landscape unit,

q is the yearly landscape unit water yield (in $mm = L/m^2$), obtained from SWAT+ water balance output files (field name: *wateryld*),

N_{out} is the sum of all N outputs leaving the landscape unit, obtained from SWAT+ nutrients balance output files.

For Nitrogen, $N_{out} = sedorgn + surqno3 + lat3no3 + tileno3 + satexn$

Where,

sedorgn is the organic nitrogen transported in surface runoff (in kg N/ha),

surqno3 is the nitrate nitrogen transported in surface runoff (in kg N/ha),

lat3no3 is the nitrate nitrogen transported in lateral flow (in kg N/ha),

tileno3 is the nitrate nitrogen transported in tile flow (in kg N/ha),

satexn is the nitrate nitrogen in saturation excess surface runoff (in kg N/ha)

For Phosphorus, $N_{out} = sedorgp + surqsolp + sedminp + tilelabp$

Where,

$sedorgp$ is the organic phosphorus transported in surface runoff (in kg P/ha),

$surqsolp$ is the soluble phosphorus transported in surface runoff (in kg P/ha),

$sedminp$ is the mineral phosphorus leaving the landscape attached to sediment (in kg P/ha)

$tilelabp$ is the soluble (labile) phosphorus in tile flow (in kg P/ha)

$$c_e = \frac{N_{out} \cdot 100}{q}, \text{ Eq. 3}$$

Where c_e is the yearly average outlet N concentration (in mg/L) in the restoration scenario,

N_{out} is the yearlyly total N mass (in kg/ha) leaving the landscape unit,

q is the yearly landscape unit water yield (in mm = L/m²), obtained from SWAT+ water balance output files (field name: wateryld),

N_{out} is the sum of all N outputs leaving the landscape unit, obtained from SWAT+ losses output files.

For Nitrogen, $N_{out} = sedorgn + surqno3 + lat3no3 + tileno3 + satexn$

Where,

$sedorgn$ is the organic nitrogen transported in surface runoff (in kg N/ha),

$surqno3$ is the nitrate nitrogen transported in surface runoff (in kg N/ha),

$lat3no3$ is the nitrate nitrogen transported in lateral flow (in kg N/ha),

$tileno3$ is the nitrate nitrogen transported in tile flow (in kg N/ha),

$satexn$ is the nitrate nitrogen in saturation excess surface runoff (in kg N/ha)

For Phosphorus, $N_{out} = sedorgp + surqsolp + sedminp + tilelabp$

Where,

$sedorgp$ is the organic phosphorus transported in surface runoff (in kg P/ha),

$surqsolp$ is the soluble phosphorus transported in surface runoff (in kg P/ha),

$sedminp$ is the mineral phosphorus leaving the landscape attached to sediment (in kg P/ha)

$tilelabp$ is the soluble (labile) phosphorus in tile flow (in kg P/ha)

$$Q = q \cdot Area \cdot 10, \text{ Eq.4}$$

Where Q is the yearly streamflow (in m³/year),

q is the yearly landscape unit water yield (in mm = L/m²), obtained from SWAT+ water balance output files (field name: wateryld),

$Area$ is the landscape unit surface (in hectares), obtained from SWAT+ landscape units input files.

Calculation of the replacement CW area for channels

$$c_i = \frac{N_{out} \cdot 1000}{q_{out} \cdot 60 \cdot 60 \cdot 24 \cdot 365}, \text{ Eq. 5}$$

Where c_i is the yearly average outlet N concentration (in mg/L) in the baseline scenario,

N_{out} is the yearlyly total N mass (in kg) leaving the channel,

q_{out} is the yearly average streamflow (in m³ per second) leaving the channel, obtained from SWAT+ channel output files (field name “flo_out”),

N_{out} is the sum of all N outputs leaving the channel, obtained from SWAT+ channel output files.

For Nitrogen, $N_{out} = orgn_{out} + no3_{out} + nh3_{out} + no2_{out}$

Where,

$orgn_{out}$ is the organic nitrogen leaving the channel (in kg),

$no3_{out}$ is the nitrate nitrogen leaving the channel (in kg),

$nh3_{out}$ is the ammonia nitrogen leaving the channel (in kg),

$no2_{out}$ is the nitrite nitrogen leaving the channel (in kg)

For Phosphorus, $N_{out} = sedp_{out} + solp_{out}$

Where,

$sedp_{out}$ is the sediment phosphorus leaving the channel (in kg),

$solp_{out}$ is the soluble phosphorus leaving the channel (in kg)

$$c_e = \frac{N_{out} \cdot 1000}{q_{out} \cdot 60 \cdot 60 \cdot 24 \cdot 365}, \text{ Eq. 6}$$

Where c_e is the yearly average outlet N concentration (in mg/L) in the restoration scenario,

N_{out} is the yearly total N mass (in kg) leaving the channel,

q_{out} is the yearly average streamflow (in m³ per second) leaving the channel, obtained from SWAT+ channel output files (field name “flo_out”),

N_{out} is the sum of all N outputs leaving the channel, obtained from SWAT+ channel output files.

For Nitrogen, $N_{out} = orgn_{out} + no3_{out} + nh3_{out} + no2_{out}$

Where,

$orgn_{out}$ is the organic nitrogen leaving the channel (in kg),

$no3_{out}$ is the nitrate nitrogen leaving the channel (in kg),

$nh3_{out}$ is the ammonia nitrogen leaving the channel (in kg),

$no2_{out}$ is the nitrite nitrogen leaving the channel (in kg)

For Phosphorus, $N_{out} = sedp_{out} + solp_{out}$

Where,

$sedp_{out}$ is the sediment phosphorus leaving the channel (in kg),

$solp_{out}$ is the soluble phosphorus leaving the channel (in kg)

$$Q = \left(\frac{q_{in} + q_{out}}{2} \right) \cdot 60 \cdot 60 \cdot 24 \cdot 365, \text{ Eq. 7}$$

Where Q is the yearly streamflow (in m³/year),

q_{in} is the yearly average streamflow (in m³ per second) entering the channel, obtained from SWAT+ channel output files (field name “flo_in”),

q_{out} is the yearly average streamflow (in m³ per second) leaving the channel, obtained from SWAT+ channel output files (field name “flo_out”),

Calculation of the monetary value of replacement CW

The monetary value of the replacement CW is the sum of the annualised net present value of the capital costs and annual maintenance costs, according to Eq. 8

$$CW \text{ value} = C \cdot r \cdot \frac{(1+r)^{LE}}{(1+r)^{(LE-1)}} + O \cdot A_s, \text{ Eq. 8}$$

Where,

C is the capital cost of the CW,

r is the actualisation rate, fixed at 0.03,

LE is the life expectancy of the CW, fixed at 50 years for replacement CW in landscape units and 20 years for replacement CW in channels (JRC, 2021),

O is the annual maintenance cost of the CW, fixed at 2,306.62 €/ha/year (2024 prices)

A_s is the CW area (in m²)

The capital cost of the CW, C, is a function of its area, according to the “Economies of scale” model¹ given by Kadlec and Wallace (2009) (page 807)

$$C = 223.74 \cdot \left(\frac{A_s}{10,000} \right)^{0.69} \cdot 1,000, \text{ Eq. 9}$$

Where,

C is the CW capital cost in € (2024 prices),

A_s is the CW area (in m²), and 0.03 ha < A_s < 10,000 ha

Considering either Nitrogen retention, either Phosphorus retention, or both

Depending on the relative importance of Nitrogen and Phosphorus retention for enhancing water quality, users may decide to dimension the constructed wetlands based on either Nitrogen retention only, either Phosphorus retention only, or both Nitrogen and Phosphorus retention. In the latter case, the largest of the constructed wetland areas needed to replace either the Nitrogen or the Phosphorus retention service is adopted.

Calculation of the monetary value of nutrient retention benefit provided by restoration

The total nutrient retention monetary value provided by in land ecosystems restoration in the water catchment is calculated by summing up all replacement CW monetary values over the total number of landscape units in the water catchment.

The total nutrient retention monetary value provided by in stream ecosystems restoration in the water catchment correspond to the replacement CW monetary value calculated for the final channel outlet of the water catchment.

¹ La Notte et al. (2012, 2017) also uses a price differential model to finally calculate the capital costs of the CWs by analysing the country-wise variation of the capital costs as fixed costs, labour costs, and filling material costs. The MERLIN plug in does not consider country-wise price differentiation.

Annex 4: CBA of MERLIN CS 05 – Kampinos wetlands

Case Study

The area of the Kampinos National Park is 38,544.33 hectares and is located in central Poland, north-west of the Polish capital Warsaw, in the Mazovia region (Figure 1). The Kampinos wetlands Regional Scalability Plan aims to restore and protect wetlands in the Mazovia region, leveraging the expertise of Kampinos National Park to scale up nature-based solutions. Key objectives are to rewet peatlands to reduce CO₂ emissions, restore species habitats, improve drought and flood resilience (Table 18). More information about the case study can be found [in the MERLIN CS portal](#).

Table 18 Restoration measures demonstrated in Kampinos

Restoration Measure	Objective (main targeted ecosystem service)
Wetland restoration: change in land use, dam removal, rewetting	Climate change mitigation, Water Purification, Flood Mitigation, Drought mitigation
Vegetation management: mowing of meadows, removal of invasive species, habitat creation	Biodiversity habitat

Figure 13 Map of Kampinos study area included in the CBA

Scenarios

Baseline scenario

In this scenario it was assumed that the present land use continues without any changes. No restoration measures were simulated in this scenario.

Restoration up-scaling scenario

The restoration scenario in this CBA focuses on rewetting of 18,673 ha of wetlands in floodplains of the Bzura basin in the Mazovia region (Figure 2). To model restoration, ICRA simulated rewetting of the area under non-urban land use in the floodplains and converted these areas into wetlands.

Figure 14 Location of Wetland Restoration sites

Restoration costs

Data and method

Investment costs in the restoration scenario were obtained by multiplying the investment cost per unit area of wetland restoration by the area of restored wetland sites. The investment cost per unit area of wetland restoration were derived from pilot restoration demonstrated in the MERLIN case study (Table 2).

To estimate recurring costs, we assumed that total maintenance and monitoring costs per hectare represented 10% of investment costs per hectare, spread over the time needed to complete restoration to a fully functional wetland (Frimpong et al., 2006; Ghimire et al., 2022). This time was assumed to be 25 years following Creed et al. (2022) and Valach et al. (2021) (Table 2).

To estimate opportunity costs of crop fields and pastures to be converted into wetlands, we used the value of crop and pastures annual production per hectare. We used the total crops output values from the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) database for the Mazowsze i Podlasie agroclimatic region of Poland (code 795 in FADN), in which the CBA area is located (Floriańczyk et al., 2024) (Table 2).

Table 19 Data sources used for the estimation of wetlands restoration costs

Land use	Investment unit costs		Recurring unit costs		Opportunity cost	
	Value	Source	Value	Source	Value	Source
Agricultural land	€ 607.74 / ha (2024 prices)	(Gerner et al., 2023; MERLIN, n.d.-b)	€ 2.43 / ha / year (2024 prices)	(Frimpong et al., 2006; Ghimire et al., 2022)	€ 1052.98 / ha * (2024 prices)	(European Commission, n.d.)
Pastural land	(total € 220,000 for 362 ha in 2024 prices)				€ 317.78 / ha ** (2024 prices)	

* Total crops output of farms with Field crops in Mazowsze i Podlasie Region (795) of Poland

** Average of total crops output of farms with milk and farms with other grazing livestock in Mazowsze i Podlasie Region (795) of Poland

Results

Investment costs were estimated at € 11.35 million (2024 prices) (Table 3), recurring costs at € 45,392.64/year (2024 prices) (Table 4) and opportunity costs at € 6.83 million / year (2024 prices) (Table 5).

Table 20 Total investment costs for wetlands restoration

Land use	Area restored	Investment unit costs	Total investment costs
Agricultural land	4050.71 ha	€ 607.74 / ha (2024 prices)	€ 11.35 million (2024 prices)
Pastural land	8072.66 ha		
Other non-urban land	6549.51 ha		
All	18672.88 ha		

Table 21 Total recurring costs for wetlands restoration

Land use	Area restored	Recurring unit costs	Total recurring costs
Agricultural land	4050.71 ha	€ 2.43 / ha / year (2024 prices)	€ 45,392.64 (2024 prices)
Pastural land	8072.66 ha		
Other non-urban land	6549.51 ha		
All	18672.88 ha		

Table 22 Total opportunity costs for wetlands restoration

Land use	Area restored	Opportunity unit costs	Total Opportunity costs
Agricultural land	4050.71 ha	€ 1052.98 / ha in 2024 prices	€ 4.265 million / year (2024 prices)
Pastural land	8072.66 ha	€ 317.78 / ha in 2024 prices	€ 2.565 million / year (2024 prices)
Other non-urban land	6549.51 ha	0	0
All	18672.88 ha		€ 6.83 million / year (2024 prices)

Flood risks mitigation benefits

Data and method

Flood risk mitigation benefits were estimated with the MERLIN modelling workflow and QGIS plugin (see Garcia et al., 2025; and Annex I of this report).

Flood damage maps for flood events of return periods 500 years, 100 years and 10 years were obtained from Państwowe Gospodarstwo Wodne Wody Polskie (PGWWP, 2022). The flood damage maps were used as inputs for the “Damage Units” function under the “FloodRiskS+” QGIS Plugin (Garcia et al., 2025) (Table 6). The output of this function is a damage unit map. A damage unit map is a vector shapefile containing the flood damages of flood events of multiple return periods. It simplifies the estimation of annual avoided flood damages (see below).

Table 23 Input parameters used in the “Damage Units” function under the “FloodRiskS+” QGIS Plugin

Parameter	Input	Source/Reasoning
Channel distance selection (m)	250	Suggested in D3.3
Damage unit cell size (m)	50	Suggested by MERLIN D3.3 to choose a size larger than pixel size
Pixel size (m)	10	Raster cell size of flood damage map
Rivs1_SWATP	Vector layer of channels of Bzura River	ICRA – SWAT+ model
Flood risk raster layer A	Flood damage map for flood of return period – 500 years	(PGWWP, 2022)
Flood risk raster layer B	Flood damage map for flood of return period – 100 years	(PGWWP, 2022)
Flood risk raster layer C	Flood damage map for flood of return period – 10 years	(PGWWP, 2022)

Estimation of Annual Avoided Flood Damages

The annual avoided flood damages were estimated using the “Flood Risk Mitigation” function under the “FloodRiskS+” QGIS Plugin. The damage units map was used as an input, along with the vector layers of subbasins and channels of the Bzura catchment, and the SQLite files of the two scenarios (Table 7).

Table 24 Input parameters used in the “Flood risk mitigation” function of the “FloodRiskS+” QGIS Plugin

Parameter	Input	Source/Reasoning
Adm_id	Subbasin	Column in the administrative units layer based on which results are aggregated
Administrative units	Vector layer of Subbasins of Forth catchment	ICRA
Return Period A	500	Corresponds to input in previous step
Return Period B	100	Corresponds to input in previous step
Return Period C	10	Corresponds to input in previous step
Rivs1_SWATP	Vector layer of channels of Bzura River	ICRA
SQLite Output BC	SQLite file of baseline scenario	ICRA
SQLite Output SC	SQLite file of restoration scenario	ICRA

The plugin produced two outputs:

- A map of channels indicating for each channel the average change in flooding probability across the three return periods (Figure 3).
- A map of estimated annual avoided flood damages in each subbasin (in € per year in 2024 prices) (Figure 4).

Using these maps we calculated:

- the effect of restoration in terms of flood risk reduction (in %), corresponding to the length-weighted average of changes in flooding probability of channels.
- the effect of restoration in terms of total avoided annual flood damage costs, by summing the annual avoided flood damage costs over all subbasins.

Results

Due to restoration, there was a 2.6% decrease in the probability of flooding across the CBA area resulting in monetary benefits of € 23 K per year (2024 prices).

Figure 15 Map of flooding probability change per channel after wetlands restoration

Figure 16 Map of annual avoided flood damage costs per subbasin due to wetlands restoration

Nutrients retention benefits

Data and method

Nutrient retention benefits were estimated following the approach detailed in Annex II of this report.

In biophysical terms, the service was quantified in terms of change in total nutrients exports (in tons) from the terrestrial ecosystems in the catchment, as well as change in nutrients concentration (in mg/L) in water flows (run-off, tile flow, etc.) leaving terrestrial ecosystems in the catchment. Nitrogen and Phosphorous exports and concentrations were calculated using SWAT+ outputs for the baseline and restoration scenarios.

The monetary valuation was based on the replacement cost approach, using constructed wetlands (CW) as a replacement alternative to restoration. Replacement CW area was calculated as a function of the water flow leaving the terrestrial ecosystems in the catchment, and the ratio of baseline scenario nutrients concentration over restoration scenario nutrients concentration. The effect of restoration was valued as the net present value of the investment requested to build the replacement CW.

Results

The relative effect of restoration on nutrients retention is small, a bit more than 1% of reduction in nutrients exports or concentration. In total, 14 tons of Nitrogen and 5 tons of phosphorous were retained thanks to restoration (Table 8). The monetary benefits were estimated at 150 K€ per year (2024 prices) considering nitrogen and 240 K€ per year (2024 prices) considering phosphorous, corresponding to 10.7 € per kg of nitrogen retained and 48.10 € per kg of phosphorous retained (Table 9).

Table 25 Effects of restoration on nutrients retention in biophysical terms

	Baseline scenario	Restoration scenario	Restoration effect	
			Mass/Concentration	% change
Total N exports (in tons)	1085	1071	-14	-1.29%
Total P exports (in tons)	373	368	-5	-1.34%
Average N concentration (in mg/L)	3.48	3.44	-0.04	-1.14%
Average P concentration (in mg/L)	1.19	1.18	-0.01	-1.15%

Table 26 Effects of restoration on nutrients retention in monetary terms

Nutrients retention benefits provided by landscape units	Nitrogen Purification Benefits (€ / year in 2024 prices)	Phosphorus Purification Benefits (€ / year in 2024 prices)
Total	150,168	240,499
Per kg of nutrient retained	10.73	48.10

Figure 17 Map of reduction of nitrogen concentration (in mg/l) out of terrestrial ecosystems

Figure 18 Map of reduction of phosphorus concentration (in mg/l) out of terrestrial ecosystems

Climate change mitigation benefits

Data and method

CO₂ emissions in the baseline and restoration scenarios were estimated by multiplying the area of land use classes in each scenario by their respective emission factors (Table 10). It was assumed that emission factors for each land use class remain stable over the entire time horizon of the CBA (100 years).

Tons of CO₂ were valued using social cost of carbon values recommended by the European Investment Bank to conduct economic appraisal of investment projects. The value of a ton of CO₂ after 2050 was assumed to remain constant at the 2050 level (Table 11).

Table 27 : Emission factors per land use class

Land use class	Emission Factor* (tCO ₂ e/ha/year)	Source of Emission Factor
Agricultural land (generic)	-0.445	(Ciais et al., 2010)
Forest (mixed)	4.03	(Verkerk et al., 2016)
Forest (evergreen)	4.03	(Verkerk et al., 2016)
Agricultural land (row)	-0.445	(Ciais et al., 2010)
Pasture	0.29	(Chang et al., 2015)
Range bush	-0.02	(Beier et al., 2009)

Forest (deciduous)	4.03	(Verkerk et al., 2016)
Wetlands (mixed)	1.06	(Fortuniak et al., 2024)

* Negative value indicates GHG source and positive value indicates GHG sink

Table 28 Social cost of carbon adjusted to 2024 prices based on inflation in Poland (Table 4-1 European Investment Bank (2023))

Social cost of carbon (€ / ton CO ₂ e in 2024 prices)	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
	122.26	252.17	382.07	596.04	802.36	1008.68	1222.64

Results

The restoration of wetlands resulted in additional 539.91 tons of CO₂e sequestration per year (Table 12), corresponding to a total net present value of € 6.93 million over the whole CBA time span.

Table 29 Net GHG balance of the baseline and restoration scenarios

Peatland Condition Class (condition code in brackets)	Emission Factor* (tCO ₂ e/ha/year)	Baseline scenario		Restoration scenario	
		Area (ha)	Net GHG balance (tCO ₂ e/yr)	Area (ha)	Net GHG balance (tCO ₂ e/yr)
Agricultural land (generic)	-0.445	3591.92	-1598.40	0	0
Forest (mixed)	4.03	360.92	1454.51	0	0
Forest (evergreen)	4.03	1158.03	4666.86	0	0
Agricultural land (row)	-0.445	458.79	-204.16	0	0
Pasture	0.29	8072.66	2341.07	0	0
Range bush	-0.02	1896.22	-37.92	0	0
Forest (deciduous)	4.03	3134.34	12631.39	0	0
Wetlands (mixed)	1.06	203.79	216.02	18,876.67	20,009.27
Total		18,876.67	19,469.36	18,876.67	20,009.27

* Negative value indicates GHG source and positive value indicates GHG sink

Cost Benefit Analysis outcomes

Data and method

For the restoration scenario, it was assumed that restoration measures would start in 2025 and be completed by 2035. Studies have found that full biophysical effects of wetlands restoration are realised about 25 years after rewetting (Creed et al., 2022; Valach et al., 2021). Following these estimates, it was assumed that the benefits of restoration would grow linearly from zero % in restoration year to 100 % 25 years after restoration. To simplify calculations, we took the mid-year of restoration works (2031) as the first year when benefits start flowing. Full benefits were then realized from 2055 onwards.

To account for the long-term benefits realised from restoration, a timeline of 100 years was used. The European commission's guide to cost-benefit analysis recommends a social discount rate of 5% for cohesion countries (which includes Poland) (European Commission, 2015). However, Baumgärtner et al. (2015) recommend using a discount rate that is 0.9% ± 0.3% below the social discount rate for manufactured goods, creating a reduction range of 0.6% to 1.2% (Baumgärtner et al., 2015).

We applied a declining discount rate because of the uncertainty around economic conditions over such a long timeline, which prompts precautionary planning (Freeman et al., 2018; Gollier, 2012). Following this approach, we started with a discount rate of 4.4% (5% - 0.6%) till year 33, declining to 3.8% (5% - 1.2%) for years 67 to 100 (Table 13). This declining rate reflects both the ecosystem service-specific adjustments recommended by Baumgärtner et al. (2015) and the growing uncertainty over longer timelines.

Table 30 Table of declining discount rates used in the cost-benefit analysis

Year (Year 1 is 2024)	1-33	34-66	67-100
Discount rate	4.4%	4.1%	3.8%

Results

The net present value of restoration is negative: - € 150 million in 2024 prices. The benefit-cost ratio is 0.09 (Table 14).

Table 31 Table of results of the cost-benefit analysis

Incremental Costs	Present Value (rounded to nearest million € in 2024 prices)
Total restoration costs	166
Incremental Benefits	Present Value (rounded to nearest million € in 2024 prices)
Flood Risk Mitigation	0.26
Nutrients Retention	3
Climate Change Mitigation	7
CBA Results	
Net Present Value (million € in 2024 prices)	-156
Benefit-Cost Ratio	0.06
Internal Rate of Return	N/A

Discussion and conclusion

This CBA shows a negative net present value, indicating that the analysed restoration scenario does not provide enough societal benefit to match the restoration costs. It is worth noting that our CBA is a first rapid cost and benefit assessment of the rewetting of floodplains in the Bzura River basin, based on a limited scope of benefits. This should be considered a starting point to be further developed with complementary analyses. Yet, our analysis indicates key issues to consider in the future strategic planning of restoration.

First, the CBA outcome is in part largely driven by high restoration costs, mainly due to the opportunity costs of the current land uses in the floodplains to be converted to wetlands.

Second, the restoration benefits in terms of flood risk mitigation, nutrients retention and climate change mitigation appear limited. Flood risk benefits represent a reduction of about 0.23% of the total expected annual damage from flooding in the CBA area. The relative effect of restoration on nutrients retention is small, a bit more than 1% of reduction in nutrients exports or concentration. Reduction in nutrient concentration in the water flows leaving restored landscape units were important, up to 31 mg N/l (Fig. 5) and 10.5 mg P/l (Fig. 6), but these local effects were diluted at the scale of the all Bzura catchment. The climate change mitigation benefits of the restoration were limited because the conversion of current land uses in the flood plains to wetlands had contrasted effects on carbon sequestration. The conversion of agricultural land and pastures to wetlands increased sequestration, but this effect was counterbalanced by the conversion of forests to wetlands.

To optimise CBA outcomes, we recommend to refine the restoration scenario in order to decrease costs and enhance potential benefits, and to extend the scope of benefits included in the analysis. The climate mitigation benefit of the restoration may be optimised by conserving forests in the floodplains. Opportunities for new agricultural products and extensive grazing systems in the restored wetlands should be assessed, in order to attenuate the loss of agricultural outputs. Future CBA works should include important potential benefits of wetlands restoration in the Buzra floodplains that we did not include in our analysis, in particular recreation opportunities and species habitat provision.

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Annex 5: CBA of MERLIN CS 14 – Komppasuo peat extraction area

Case Study

The Komppasuo case study is located within the Kuivajoki catchment in Finland (Figure 1), spanning approximately 3500 hectares. The study area is owned by a peat extraction company, Neova oy. Former peat extraction areas are now being afforested. The region also hosts agricultural lands and reindeer herding lands. Mining, establishment of solar panel fields, and windmill sites are arising as attractive land use options for abandoned peat extraction areas. Climate change also threatens peatland areas in the region, with the potential to alter the hydrological patterns and natural habitats. In MERLIN, this case study demonstrated rewetting and restoration of peatland extraction areas (Table 1). More information about the case study can be found [the MERLIN CS portal](#).

Table 32 Restoration measures demonstrated in Komppasuo

Restoration Measure	Objective (main targeted ecosystem service)
Peatland restoration: Rewet and restore former peat extraction areas	Climate change mitigation, Water Purification, Biodiversity habitat

Figure 19 Map of Komppasuo study area included in the CBA

Scenarios

Baseline scenario

In this scenario it was assumed that the present land use continues without any changes. No restoration measures were modelled in this scenario.

Restoration up-scaling scenario

The restoration scenario in this CBA focuses on rewetting and restoration of 3509 hectares of peatland extraction areas (Figure 2). To model restoration in SWAT+, we changed land cover, land use and hydrological properties of hydrological response units overlapping peatland restoration areas from barren or sparsely vegetated to fully functional peatlands (see Garcia et al., 2025).

Figure 20 Location of Peatland Restoration sites

Restoration costs

Data and method

Investment costs in the restoration scenario were obtained by multiplying the area of restored peatlands by unit investment costs of restoration per hectare. Unit investment costs (Table 2) were derived from the implementation plan of this case study (Gerner et al., 2023). The area of peatland extraction sites was estimated from the area of hydrological response units under barren or sparsely vegetated land use in the SWAT+ model (baseline scenario).

To estimate recurring costs, we assumed that total maintenance and monitoring costs per hectare represented 20% of investment costs per hectare, spread over the time needed to complete restoration to a fully functional peatland (Holden et al., 2008; Moran et al., 2013; Moxey & Moran, 2014). This time was assumed to be 16 years following Kalhori et al. (2024) and Nugent et al. (2018).

The opportunity costs were assumed to be null.

Table 33 Data sources used for the estimation of peatland restoration costs

Land use	Investment unit costs		Recurring unit costs	
	Value	Source	Value	Source
Former peat extraction sites (barren and sparsely vegetated)	€ 3165.46 / ha in 2024 prices (€ 374,000 for 120 ha in 2023 prices)	(Gerner et al., 2023; MERLIN, n.d.)	€ 39.57 / ha / year (2024 prices)	(Holden et al., 2008; Moran et al., 2013)

Results

Total investment costs were estimated at € 11.1 million (2024 prices) (Table 3).

Table 34 Total investment costs for peatlands restoration

Land use	Area restored	Investment unit costs	Total investment costs
Former peat extraction sites (barren and sparsely vegetated)	3508.49 ha	€ 3165.46 / ha (2024 prices)	€ 11.1 million (2024 prices)

The recurring costs per unit area were 39.57 €/ha/year in 2024 prices which lies within the range estimated in literature (Moran et al., 2013) (Table 4).

Table 35 Total recurring costs for peatlands restoration

Land use	Area restored	Recurring unit costs	Total recurring costs
Former peat extraction sites (barren and sparsely vegetated)	3508.49 ha	€ 39.57 / ha / year (2024 prices)	€ 138,824 / year (2024 prices)

Flood risks mitigation benefits

The flood risk mitigation benefits were considered null because the Kuivajoki river basin is not classified as a flood risk area (MERLIN, n.d.-c). The CBA area lies outside the zones identified as being at risk of flooding, which were mapped by the Finnish Environment Institute, (SYKE, 2024) (Figure 3).

Figure 21 Map of study area and flood risk zone of a flood event of return period 1000 years (SYKE, 2024)

Nutrients retention benefits

Data and method

Nutrient retention benefits were estimated following the approach detailed in Annex II of this report.

In biophysical terms, the service was quantified in terms of change in total nutrients exports (in tons) from the terrestrial ecosystems in the catchment, as well as change in nutrients concentration (in mg/L) in water flows (run-off, tile flow, etc.) leaving terrestrial ecosystems in the catchment. Nitrogen and Phosphorous exports and concentrations were calculated using SWAT+ outputs for the baseline and restoration scenarios.

The monetary valuation was based on the replacement cost approach, using constructed wetlands (CW) as a replacement alternative to restoration. Replacement CW area was calculated as a function of the water flow leaving the terrestrial ecosystems in the catchment, and the ratio of baseline scenario nutrients concentration over restoration scenario nutrients concentration. The effect of restoration was valued as the net present value of the investment requested to build the replacement CW.

Results

Restoration caused a reduction in the mass of nutrients exports but also a reduction of water flows out of landscape units, resulting in an increase in the concentration of nutrients in the water flows out of landscape units (Table 5). Since the monetary benefits are dependent on the change in the concentration of nutrients between baseline and restoration scenarios (see Annex II), nutrients retention benefits were estimated negative, at -112 K € per year (2024 prices) considering nitrogen and -73 K€ per year (2024 prices) considering phosphorous (Table 6).

Table 36 Effects of restoration on nutrient retention in biophysical terms

	Baseline scenario	Restoration scenario	Restoration effect	
			Mass/Concentration	% change
Total N exports (in tons)	75	70	-5	-6.67%
Total P exports (in tons)	40	37	-3	-7.5%
Average N concentration (in mg/L)	5.48	5.98	+0.50	+9.19%
Average P concentration (in mg/L)	2.95	3.19	+0.24	+8.14%

Table 37 Effects of restoration on nutrients retention in monetary terms

Nutrients retention benefits provided by landscape units	Nitrogen Purification Benefits (€ / year in 2024 prices)	Phosphorus Purification Benefits (€ / year in 2024 prices)
Total	-112,388	-73,174
Per kg of nutrient retained	-22.48	-24.39

Figure 22 Map of reduction of Nitrogen concentration (in mg/L) out of terrestrial ecosystems

Figure 23 Map of reduction of Phosphorous concentration (in mg/L) out of terrestrial ecosystems

Climate change mitigation benefits

Data and method

Greenhouse gas emissions in the baseline scenario were estimated using the emission factor of soil in peat production sites according to Juutinen et al. (2019) (Table 7). It was assumed that the former peat production sites would be converted into restored peatlands. The emissions of restored peatlands were estimated using the average value of emission factors of meso-eutrophic open-composite peatlands, open sedge peatlands and ombro-oligotrophic open peatlands (Juutinen et al., 2019). The total GHG emissions were estimated by multiplying the total area to be restored (3508.49 ha) by the corresponding emission factors. It was assumed that emission factors for each peat condition class remain stable over the entire time horizon of the CBA (100 years).

Table 38 Data sources used to estimate climate change mitigation benefits

Data	Description/Value	Source/Publisher
Land use map: "hrus.shp"	A land use map of hydrological response units in Komppasuo with 10 land use categories.	ICRA – SWAT+
GHG Emission factors	Emission factor of former peatland extraction sites indicated by the emission factor of emissions from soil in peat production option. Emission factor of restored peatlands indicated by the average of the emission factors of meso-eutrophic open-composite peatlands, open sedge peatlands and ombro-oligotrophic open peatlands.	Table S21 of (Juutinen et al., 2019)
The Economic Appraisal of Investment Projects at the EIB	Guidance document to conduct economic appraisals recommends social costs of carbon.	Table 4-1 of (European Investment Bank., 2023)

GHG emissions were valued using the social cost of carbon values recommended by the Economic Appraisal of Investment Projects at the EIB (European Investment Bank., 2023) (Table 8). The values were adjusted according to the inflation rate in Finland between 2016 and 2024 (World Bank Group, n.d.). The value of GHG emissions after 2050 was assumed to remain constant at the 2050 level.

Table 39 Social Cost of Carbon adjusted to 2024 prices based on inflation in Finland (Table 4-1 European Investment Bank (2023))

Social cost of carbon (€ / ton CO ₂ e in 2024 prices)	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
	97.52	201.14	304.76	475.43	640	804.57	975.24

Results

The restoration of peatlands results in 40,816.72 tons of CO₂e emissions avoided per year, corresponding to a total net present value of € 1,132.23 million over the whole CBA time span (Table 9).

Table 40 GHG emissions of the baseline and restoration scenarios

Land use	Emission Factor (tCO ₂ e/ha/yr)	Baseline scenario		Restoration scenario	
		Area (ha)	Emissions (tCO ₂ e/yr)	Area (ha)	Emissions (tCO ₂ e/yr)
Former peat extraction sites (barren or sparsely vegetated)	14.097	3,508.49	49,459.18	0	0
Restored Peatland	2.4633	0	0	3,508.49	8,642.46
	Total	3,508.49	49,459.18	3,508.49	8,642.46

Cost Benefit Analysis outcomes

Data and method

For the restoration scenario, it was assumed that restoration measures would start in 2025 and be completed by 2035. Studies have found that full biophysical effects of peatland restoration are realised 14-16 years after rewetting (Kalhori et al., 2024; Nugent et al., 2018). Following these estimates, it was assumed that the benefits of restoration would grow linearly from zero % in restoration year to 100 % 15 years after restoration. To simplify calculations, we took the mid-year of restoration works (2031) as the first year when benefits start flowing. Full benefits were then realized from 2046 onwards.

To account for the long-term benefits realised from restoration, a timeline of 100 years was used. The European commission's guide to cost-benefit analysis recommends a social discount rate of 3% for non-cohesion countries (which includes Finland) (European Commission, 2015). However, Baumgärtner et al. (2015) recommend using a discount rate that is 0.9% ± 0.3% below the social discount rate for manufactured goods, creating a reduction range of 0.6% to 1.2% (Baumgärtner et al., 2015).

We applied a declining discount rate because of the uncertainty around economic conditions over such a long timeline, which prompts precautionary planning (Freeman et al., 2018; Gollier, 2012). Following this approach, we started with a discount rate of 2.4% (3% - 0.6%) till year 33, declining to 1.8% (3% - 1.2%) for years 67 to 100 (Table 10). This declining rate reflects both the ecosystem service-specific adjustments recommended by Baumgärtner et al. (2015) and the growing uncertainty over longer timelines.

Table 41 Table of declining discount rates used in the cost-benefit analysis

Year (Year 1 is 2024)	1-33	34-66	67-100
Discount rate	2.4%	2.1%	1.8%

Results

The net present value of restoration of the Komppasuo is € 1,132 million in 2024 prices. The benefit-cost ratio is 93.2 and the internal rate of return is 23.59% (Table 11).

Table 42 Table of results of the cost-benefit analysis

Incremental Costs	Present Value (rounded to nearest million € in 2024 prices)
Total restoration costs	12
Incremental Benefits	Present Value (rounded to nearest million € in 2024 prices)
Flood Risk Mitigation	N/A
Nutrients Retention	-2
Climate Change Mitigation	1132
CBA Results	
Net Present Value (million € in 2024 prices)	1117
Benefit-Cost Ratio	93.2
Internal Rate of Return	23.59%

Discussion and conclusion

The CBA outcome is highly positive, with a benefit cost ratio of 93.2 and internal rate of return of 23.6%. Yet, it is important to note that this outcome is completely dependent on the value of climate change mitigation benefits. The restoration does not have flood mitigation benefits because the analysed catchment is not in an area vulnerable to floods and nutrients retention benefits were estimated as negative. Nevertheless, our CBA was limited in scope and did not include potentially important societal benefits of the planned restoration, such as recreation opportunities and the provision of species habitat.

It is worth noting that this CBA used social costs of carbon to value tons of CO₂e. Current tons of CO₂e prices on the carbon markets are much lower than social costs of carbon. For instance, the average price on voluntary carbon markets in 2024 was € 5.9 per ton of CO₂e (Forest Trends' Ecosystem Marketplace, 2025), whereas we used a social cost of carbon of € 180.4 per ton of CO₂e for the year 2024 in this CBA. This difference is important when considering carbon markets as potential private funding sources for the restoration.

Finally, an important aspect not covered by our CBA is the competition of alternative land uses to restoration in old peat extraction sites. These alternative land uses include solar panel fields, windmill sites and mining. Economic output of these competing land uses should be integrated as opportunity costs of restoration in future extended CBA.

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Annex 6: CBA of MERLIN CS 17 – Forth Catchment

Case Study

The Forth catchment is located in Scotland and spans approximately 1205 square kilometres, from Braes of Balquhider in the north-west to Stirling in the south-east (Figure 1). It hosts a diverse variety of habitats, including upland peat bogs, lochs, rivers and fertile floodplains. Over time, the landscape has been modified and faces pressures. Peatlands were converted into agricultural land, human-made weirs were built in rivers, and coal and iron were mined. Due to a high population, there are sewage outfall issues, affecting the water quality of the streams. In MERLIN, this CS demonstrated the rewetting of peatlands, reconnection of floodplain of the River Forth tributary and restoration of channel and riparian habitats (Table 1). More information about the case study can be found [in the MERLIN CS portal](#).

Table 1: Restoration measures demonstrated in the Forth Catchment

Restoration Measure	Objective (main targeted ecosystem service)
Peatland restoration: Blocking of historic drainage ditches passing through peatland to raise water table and rewet degraded peatland	Climate change mitigation, Flood mitigation
Peatland restoration: Forest to bog conversion - Potential conifer trees, reseedling from surrounding forestry to be removed	Nutrients retention, Climate change mitigation
Reconnection of floodplains	Flood mitigation, Nutrients retention
Restoration of riparian habitats	Flood mitigation, Nutrients retention

Figure 1: Map of the Forth catchment sub-basins included in the CBA

Scenarios

Baseline scenario

In this scenario it was assumed that the present land use continues without any changes. No restoration measures were modelled in this scenario.

Restoration up-scaling scenarios

The restoration scenario considered in this CBA focuses on the rewetting of 1657 hectares of degraded peatlands (Figure 2). To model peatland restoration, land use under actively eroding peatlands and drained peatlands were converted to “undrained” peatlands (see Garcia et al., 2025).

Figure 2: Location of Peatland Restoration sites

Restoration costs

Data and method

Peatland Restoration

Investment costs in the restoration scenario were obtained by multiplying the area of restored peatlands by unit investment costs of restoration per hectare. Unit costs were specified per type and condition of peatlands to be restored, based on Glenk et al. (2022). The area of peatland to be restored in each type and condition class was calculated by overlaying the restoration sites with a map of peatland condition (James Hutton Institute, 2024) (Table 2).

To estimate recurring costs, we assumed that total maintenance and monitoring costs per hectare represented 20% of investment costs per hectare, spread over the time needed to complete restoration to a fully functional peatland (Holden et al., 2008; Moran et al., 2013; Moxey & Moran, 2014). This time was assumed to be 16 years following Kalhori et al. (2024) and Nugent et al. (2018). Obtained recurring costs ranged from 20.44 €/ha/year to

23.65 €/ha/year in 2024 prices (based on peatland type and condition), a range similar to other estimated in the literature (Moran et al., 2013) (Table 2).

Opportunity costs were assumed to be null, because the current land use on peatland areas to be restored is very extensive (extensive grazing or grouse hunting).

Table 2: Data sources used for the estimation of peatlands restoration costs

Peatland type and condition	Investment unit costs		Recurring unit costs	
	Value	Source	Value	Source
Bare/eroding modified drained bog (Condition class 9)	€ 1891.95 / ha in 2024 prices (£ 1452.27 / ha in 2022 prices)	Table 6 of (Glenk et al., 2022)	€ 23.65 / ha / year (2024 prices)	(Holden et al., 2008; Moran et al., 2013)
Molinia drained, heather dominated drained, grass dominated drained, and sedge/rush dominated (Condition classes 11, 13, 15, 17)	€ 1635.04 / ha in 2024 prices (£ 1255.07 / ha in 2022 prices)	Table 6 of (Glenk et al., 2022)	€ 20.44 / ha / year (2024 prices)	(Holden et al., 2008; Moran et al., 2013)

Results

Total costs were estimated at € 2.81 million (2024 prices) for investment costs (Table 3) and € 35,117.47 / year (2024 prices) for recurring costs (Table 4).

Table 3: Total investment costs for peatlands restoration

Peatland type and condition	Area restored	Investment unit costs	Total investment costs
Bare/eroding modified drained bog (Condition class 9)	388.55 ha	€ 1891.95 / ha (2024 prices)	€ 0.74 million (2024 prices)
Molinia drained, heather dominated drained, grass dominated drained, and sedge/rush dominated (Condition classes 11, 13, 15, 17)	1268.64 ha	€ 1635.04 / ha (2024 prices)	€ 2.07 million (2024 prices)
All	1657.19 ha		€ 2.81 million (2024 prices)

Table 4: Total recurring costs for peatlands restoration

Peatland type and condition	Area restored	Recurring unit costs	Total recurring costs
Bare/eroding modified drained bog (Condition class 9)	388.55 ha	€ 23.65 / ha / year (2024 prices)	€ 9188.95 / year (2024 prices)
Molinia drained, heather dominated drained, grass dominated drained, and sedge/rush dominated (Condition classes 11, 13, 15, 17)	1268.64 ha	€ 20.44 / ha / year (2024 prices)	€ 25,928.52 / year (2024 prices)
All	1657.19 ha		€ 35,117.47 / year (2024 prices)

Flood risks mitigation benefits

Data and method

Flood risk mitigation benefits were estimated with the MERLIN modelling workflow and QGIS plugin (see Garcia et al. (2025) and Annex I of this report). This method involved two steps – creation of flood damage costs maps and estimation of annual avoided flood damages.

Creation of Flood Damage Costs Maps

A flood damage cost map is a raster map of economic damage (€/m²) caused by a flood event with a certain return period. The map is obtained by combining a flood extent and depth map corresponding to a given return period (e.g. every 100 years), a land use map, and a flood depth-damage function per land use class (see Annex I). Flood extent and depth maps were obtained from the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency. Land use was derived from the Corine Land Cover dataset. Flood depth – damage functions were derived from Huizinga et al. (2017) (Table 5).

Table 5: Data inputs used for the creation of flood damage costs maps

Dataset	Description	Publisher and links
Flood extent and depth maps	Extent and depth of flood events caused by rivers. They are three maps of return periods 10, 200, and 1000 years.	(SEPA, 2025)
Corine Land cover (CLC)	Pan-European CORINE Land Cover inventory for the 2018 reference year.	(European Environment Agency, 2019)
Global depth damage file (GDD)	Damage fraction estimates for nine discrete flood depth values (in a range of 0-6 metres) and the maximum damage values of six land use classes.	(Huizinga et al., 2017)

The global database in Huizinga et al. (2017) provides Europe-specific flood depth – damage functions (damage % as a function of flood depth) for 6 land use classes (residential, commercial, industry, transport, infrastructure, agriculture). Moreover, this dataset provides country specific maximum damage values for those 6 land use classes. To assign to a maximum damage value to each cell of the CLC, the land cover classes of CLC were reclassified to match the land use classes in Huizinga et al. (2017) (Table 6).

The flood extent and depth maps have three flood depth classes: Class 1: Less than 0.3m, Class 2: 0.3m to 1m and Class 3: Greater than 1m. It was assumed that these categorical classes represent absolute depth values of 0.15m (average between 0 and 0.3m), 0.65 metres (average between 0.3 to 1m) and 1.1 metres (a value just above 1m).

Huizinga et al. (2017) provides damage fractions for 9 discrete flood depth values (in a range from 0 to 6m). These 9 damage fractions - flood depth points were used in a regression analysis to build quadratic functions relating flood damage fractions to flood depth per land use class. Using the functions, the damage fraction for each land use class was calculated for depths of 0.15m, 0.65m and 1.1m, to fit with flood depth classes in the SEPA maps (Table 7).

Flood-damage costs maps were produced for flood events corresponding to return periods of 10, 200, and 1,000 years.

The flood damage costs maps were used as inputs for the “Damage Units” function under the “FloodRiskS+” QGIS Plugin (Garcia et al., 2025) (Table 8). The output of this function is a damage unit map. A damage unit map is a vector shapefile containing the flood damages of flood events of multiple return periods. It simplifies the estimation of annual avoided flood damages (the next step).

Table 6: Cross link of CLC classes and Huizinga et al. (2017) land use classes

GRID_CODE	Code_18	Cat_CLU	Damage class of GDD	Code assigned
1	111	Continuous urban fabric	Residential	1
2	112	Discontinuous urban fabric	Residential	1
3	121	Industrial or commercial units	Commercial & Industrial (Average)	2
4	122	Road and rail networks and associated land	Infrastructure	4
5	123	Port areas	Transport	3
6	124	Airports	Transport	3
7	133	Construction sites	Residential	1
8	141	Green urban areas	Residential	1
9	142	Sport and leisure facilities	Residential	1
10	211	Non-irrigated arable land	Agriculture	5
11	212	Permanently irrigated land	Agriculture	5
12	213	Rice fields	Agriculture	5
13	221	Vineyards	Agriculture	5
14	222	Fruit trees and berry plantations	Agriculture	5
15	223	Olive groves	Agriculture	5
16	231	Pastures	Agriculture	5
17	241	Annual crops associated with permanent crops	Agriculture	5
18	242	Complex cultivation patterns	Agriculture	5
19	243	Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation	Agriculture	5
20	244	Agro-forestry areas	Agriculture	5

Note: Level 3 classes mineral extraction sites (1.3.1) and dump sites (1.3.2), as well as level 1 classes (including all level 2 and 3 sub-classes) forest and semi-natural areas, wetlands and water bodies did not have any corresponding land use class in Huizinga et al. (2017). Therefore, no flood damage is calculated on these land use/land cover classes.

Table 7: Damage fractions per flood depth class and maximum damage values per land use class

Land use class	Damage fraction for Depth = 0.15m	Damage fraction for Depth = 0.65m	Damage fraction for Depth = 1.1m	Maximum damage (€/m ² 2024 prices)
Residential	0.11	0.26	0.38	223.65
Commercial & Industrial	0.05	0.20	0.33	422.4
Agricultural	0.11	0.36	0.53	0.097

Table 8: input parameters used in the “Damage Units” function of the “FloodRiskS+” QGIS Plugin

Parameter	Input	Source/Reasoning
Channel distance selection (m)	250	Suggested in D3.3
Damage unit cell size (m)	50	Suggested by MERLIN D3.3 to choose a size larger than pixel size
Pixel size (m)	10	Raster cell size of flood damage map
Flood risk raster layer A	Flood damage map for flood of return period – 1000 years	Output from previous step
Flood risk raster layer B	Flood damage map for flood of return period – 200 years	Output from previous step
Flood risk raster layer C	Flood damage map for flood of return period – 10 years	Output from previous step

Estimation of Annual Avoided Flood Damages

The annual avoided flood damages were estimated using the “Flood Risk Mitigation” function under the “FloodRiskS+” QGIS Plugin (Garcia et al., 2025). The damage units map was used as an input, along with the vector layers of subbasins and channels of the Forth catchment, and the SQLite files of the respective scenarios (Table 9).

Table 9: input parameters used in the “Flood risk mitigation” function of the “FloodRiskS+” QGIS Plugin

Parameter	Input	Source/Reasoning
Adm_id	Subbasin	Column in the administrative units’ layer based on which results are aggregated
Administrative units	Vector layer of Subbasins of Forth catchment	ICRA – SWAT+ model
Return Period A	1000	Corresponds to input in previous step
Return Period B	200	Corresponds to input in previous step
Return Period C	10	Corresponds to input in previous step
Rivs1_SWATP	Vector layer of channels of Forth River	ICRA – SWAT+ model
SQLite Output BC	SQLite file of baseline scenario	ICRA – SWAT+ model
SQLite Output SC	SQLite file of restoration scenario	ICRA – SWAT+ model

The plugin produced two outputs:

- A map of channels indicating for each channel the average change in flooding probability across the three return periods (Figure 3).
- A map of estimated annual avoided flood damages in each subbasin (in € per year in 2024 prices) (Figure 4).

Using these maps we calculated:

- the effect of restoration in terms of flood risk reduction (in %), corresponding to the length-weighted average of changes in flooding probability of channels.
- the effect of restoration in terms of total avoided annual flood damage costs, by summing the annual avoided flood damage costs over all subbasins.

Results

Due to restoration, there was a 8.8% decrease in the probability of flooding across the Forth catchment resulting in monetary benefits of € 190 K per year (in 2024 prices). Effects are especially visible in channels located downstream of the main peatland restoration areas (in the Northeast of the catchment) and monetary benefits are concentrated in the downstream parts of the catchment.

Figure 3: Map of flooding probability change per channel after peatland restoration

Figure 4: map of annual avoided flood damage costs per subbasin due to peatland restoration

Nutrients retention benefits

Data and method

Nutrient retention benefits were estimated following the approach detailed in Annex II of this report.

In biophysical terms, the service was quantified in terms of change in total nutrients exports (in tons) from the terrestrial ecosystems in the catchment, as well as change in nutrients concentration (in mg/L) in water flows (run-off, tile flow, etc.) leaving terrestrial ecosystems in the catchment. Nitrogen and Phosphorous exports and concentrations were calculated using SWAT+ outputs for the baseline and restoration scenarios.

The monetary valuation was based on the replacement cost approach, using constructed wetlands (CW) as a replacement alternative to restoration. Replacement CW area was calculated as a function of the water flow leaving the terrestrial ecosystems in the catchment, and the ratio of baseline scenario nutrients concentration over restoration scenario nutrients concentration. The effect of restoration was valued as the net present value of the investment requested to build the replacement CW.

Results

The relative effect of restoration on nutrients retention is small, less than 1% of reduction in nutrients exports or concentration. Depending on the areas of restoration, the reduction in Nitrogen concentration in the water flows leaving landscape units ranged from 0 to 4 mg N/l (Figure 6), and the reduction in Phosphorous concentration in the water flows leaving landscape units ranged from 0 to 0.45 mg N/l (Figure 5). In total, 88 tons of Nitrogen and 11 tons of phosphorous were retained thanks to restoration (Table 10). The monetary benefits were estimated at 640 K€ per year (2024 prices) considering nitrogen and 595 K€ per year (2024 prices) considering phosphorous, corresponding to 7.4 € per kg of nitrogen retained and 55.7 € per kg of phosphorous retained (Table 11).

Table 10: Effects of restoration on nutrients retention in biophysical terms

	Baseline scenario	Restoration scenario	Restoration effect	
			Mass/Concentration	% change
Total N exports (in tons)	9,128	9,041	-88	-0.96%
Total P exports (in tons)	1,330	1,319	-11	-0.83%
Average N concentration (in mg/L)	10.04	9.95	-0.09	-0.89%
Average P concentration (in mg/L)	1.46	1.45	-0.01	-0.74%

Table 11: Effects of restoration on nutrients retention in monetary terms

Nutrients retention benefits provided by landscape units	Nitrogen Purification Benefits (€ / year in 2024 prices)	Phosphorus Purification Benefits (€ / year in 2024 prices)
Total	640,161	595,250
Per kg of nutrient retained	7.34	55.71

Figure 5: map of reduction of phosphorous concentration (in mg/l) out of terrestrial ecosystems

Figure 6: map of reduction of nitrogen concentration (in mg/l) out of terrestrial ecosystems

Climate change mitigation benefits

Data and method

CO₂ emissions in the baseline and restoration scenarios were estimated using James Hutton Institute’s emission factors per peatland condition class (Evans et al., 2017; IUCN, 2023; James Hutton Institute, 2024). It was assumed that the area under the drained peatland condition classes (condition codes 11, 13, 15, 17) would be restored to their respective “undrained” classes (condition codes 12, 14, 16, 18); and the bare/eroding modified drained bog (condition code 9) would be restored to grass dominated undrained (condition code 16). This undrained condition class is the most realistic expected condition of a peatland after carrying out the restoration measures in the UK (DEFRA, 2023). Total CO₂ emissions for each scenario were estimated by multiplying the area under each peatland condition class (derived from James Hutton Institute, 2024) with their corresponding emission factors. It was assumed that emission factors for each peat condition class remain stable over the entire time horizon of the CBA (100 years).

CO₂ emissions were valued using social cost of carbon values recommended by the UK Government for valuation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions for policy appraisal, taking the lower bound of the uncertainty range (BEIS & ESNZ, 2021) (Table 12). The value of GHG emissions after 2050 was assumed to remain constant at the 2050 level.

Table 12: Social cost of carbon: uncertainty range capturing sensitivity of models to socio-economic assumptions, such as future trends in demography and GDP. (BEIS & ESNZ, 2021)

	2020	2030	2040	2050
Social cost of carbon (in € per ton CO₂e, 2024 prices)	173 - 520	202 - 605	235 - 705	272 - 819

Results

The restoration of peatlands results in 7,380.40 tons of CO₂e emissions avoided per year (Table 13), corresponding to a total net present value of € 39.35 million over the whole CBA time span.

Table 13: GHG emissions of the baseline and restoration scenarios

Peatland Condition Class (condition code in brackets)	Emission Factor (tCO ₂ e/ha/yr)	Baseline scenario		Restoration scenario	
		Area (ha)	Emissions (tCO ₂ e/yr)	Area (ha)	Emissions (tCO ₂ e/yr)
Bare/eroding modified drained bog (9)	18.86	388.55	7328.053	0	0
Molinia drained (11)	3.32	413.85	1373.982	0	0
Molinia undrained (12)	2.51	3297.73	8277.3023	3711.58	9316.0658
Heather dominated drained (13)	3.32	819.79	2721.7028	0	0
Heather dominated undrained (14)	2.51	7278.65	18269.4115	8098.44	20327.0844
Grass dominated drained (15)	3.32	20.21	67.0972	0	0
Grass dominated undrained (16)	2.51	383.64	962.9364	792.4	1988.924
Sedge/rush dominated drained (17)	3.32	14.8	49.136	0	0
Sedge/rush dominated undrained (18)	2.51	303.22	761.0822	318.02	798.2302
Total		12920.44	39810.7034	12920.44	32430.3044

Cost Benefit Analysis outcomes

Data and method

For the restoration scenario, it was assumed that restoration measures would start in 2025 and be completed by 2035. Studies have found that full biophysical effects of peatland restoration are realised 14-16 years after rewetting (Kalhori et al., 2024; Nugent et al., 2018). Following these estimates, it was assumed that the benefits of restoration would grow linearly from zero % in restoration year to 100 % 15 years after restoration. To simplify calculations, we took the mid-year of restoration works (2031) as the first year when benefits start flowing. Full benefits were then realised from 2046 onwards.

To account for the long-term benefits realised from restoration, a timeline of 100 years was used. The cash flow was discounted according to the declining long term discount rates suggested by the UK government's green book (HM Treasury, 2022) (Table 14).

Table 14: Declining discount rate used as recommended by HM Treasury (2022)

Year (Year 1 is 2024)	1-30	31-75	76-100
Discount rate	3.5%	3%	2.5%

Results

The net present value of restoration of the Forth catchment was € 64 million in 2024 prices, corresponding to a benefit-cost ratio of 22.8 and an internal rate of return of 17.9% (Table 15).

Table 15: Table of results of the cost-benefit analysis

Incremental Costs	Present Value (rounded to nearest million € in 2024 prices)

Total restoration costs	3
Incremental Benefits	Present Value (rounded to nearest million € in 2024 prices)
Flood Risk Mitigation	3.9
Nutrients Retention	13
Climate Change Mitigation	39
CBA Results	
Net Present Value (million € in 2024 prices)	53
Benefit-Cost Ratio	19
Internal Rate of Return	16.5%

Discussion and conclusion

Overall, our CBA indicates that investing in peatlands restoration in the Forth Catchment seems profitable from a social perspective, even though the scope of benefits included in our CBA was limited and did not include potentially important benefits such as recreation and provision of species habitat.

We discuss below results for each cost and benefit component of the analysis.

Costs

Regarding restoration costs, the main uncertainty is our assumption that opportunity costs were negligible. That assumption hinges on the current extensive use (extensive grazing, grouse hunting) taking place on the peatland areas selected to be restored in our analysis. Our restoration scenario only covered the Forth catchment and 1,657 ha of peatland restoration on degraded peatlands with extensive land use. The Forth Regional Scalability Plan targets a much larger region, the entire Firth of Forth and a total area of peat land restoration of 250,000 ha. As peatland restoration is upscaled, opportunity costs of the current peat land use may become significant and would have to be taken into consideration in a CBA of the total restoration planned in the Regional Scalability Plan.

Flood risk mitigation

Estimated flood mitigation benefits were 190 K€ (2024 prices) per year. Total annual damages from river flooding in the CBA area were estimated by the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency at 4.17 million € (2024 prices) (SEPA, 2015). Thus, our estimated flood mitigation benefits represent about 4.6% of annual damages estimated by SEPA. This may be an underestimation given that we estimated a reduction of flood risk reduction of 8.8% on the basis of changes in peak flow probabilities in channels.

Nutrients retention

Nutrients retention benefits were estimated at 640 K€ per year (2024 prices) considering nitrogen and 595 K€ per year (2024 prices) considering phosphorous, corresponding to 7.4 € per kg of nitrogen retained and 55.7 € per kg of phosphorous retained.

Defra's Enabling a Natural Capital Approach (ENCA) provide other options to value water quality improvement benefits (DEFRA, 2023). Based on the Farmscoper tool, the annual value of reducing a kg of nitrate/phosphorus in water is estimated at about 1.17 and 39.76 £ (2021 prices). These values are based on estimation of economic damages of nitrate and phosphorus on a range of ecosystem services, including drinking water quality, fishing, bathing water quality and eutrophication.

Therefore, in the case of the Forth catchment, the replacement cost approach seems to overestimates the societal benefits of nitrogen removal but generates estimates in line with the Farmscoper tool for phosphorus retention.

Note that both the replacement costs based and damage costs based values assume that all units of N retention provide the same benefit, i.e. each kg of N reduction has the same value. In reality, N emission reductions in sub-catchments where water quality is high have a lower value than N emission reductions in sub-catchments where water quality is poor. For instance, in the Forth Catchment restoration scenario, the nutrients retention benefit provided by peat restoration areas located in the Eastern part of the catchment, where water quality is mostly "moderate" to "good", is likely higher than the benefit provided by peat restoration areas located in the North-Eastern part of the catchment, where water quality already reaches a "good" to "high" status (Fig. 8).

Finally, both replacement costs based and damage costs based values integrate the value of multiple ESs related to nutrients content in surface water. Therefore, water-related ES benefits such as nature recreation or habitat provision were partly and indirectly valued through the nutrients retention service in our CBA.

Figure 24 – Nutrients retention benefit in the Forth Catchment.

Climate change mitigation

Regarding climate change mitigation benefits, we assumed that baseline emissions from degraded peatlands would remain stable over the entire CBA time span, 100 years. In reality, depending on the thickness of the remaining peat layer, baseline emissions may decrease over this time frame and the climate mitigation benefits of restoration may be lower than we estimated.

It is also worth noting that we used social costs of carbon to value tons of CO₂e. Current tons of CO₂e prices on the carbon markets are much lower than social costs of carbon. For instance, the average price of carbon credits purchased from Peatland Code projects in the UK in 2022 was € 28.1 per ton of CO₂e (UK Carbon Price Index | IUCN UK Peatland Programme, n.d.), whereas we used a social cost of carbon of € 179 per ton of CO₂e for the year 2022 in this CBA. This difference is important when considering carbon markets as potential private funding sources for the restoration.

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Annex 7: CBA of MERLIN CS 13 – Sorraia floodplain

Case Study

The Sorraia basin stretches from Couço in the northeast to Murteira in the southwest part of Portugal (Figure 1). The catchment area is approximately 7611 km² (Ferreira et al., 2024). It has a Mediterranean river landscape, dominated by agricultural land, pastures and oak forests (Van Der Laan et al., 2023). Hydro-morphological changes, discharges, flow regulation and pollution are the major pressures in the basin (Almeida et al., 2018). As a result of these pressures, the rivers length, profile and sinuosity have changed, and there is an uncontrolled growth of invasive exotic species (Ferreira et al., 2024). With climate change the precipitation and water quantity are expected to decrease, while nutrient concentrations are expected to increase (Almeida et al., 2018). In MERLIN, this CS demonstrated the establishment of riparian buffer strips and riparian habitat rehabilitation (Table 1). More information about the case study can be found [the MERLIN CS portal](#).

Table 43 Restoration measures demonstrated in the Sorraia catchment

Restoration Measure	Objective (main targeted ecosystem service)
Establishment of vegetated riparian forest buffer strips	Climate change mitigation, Flood mitigation, Nutrients retention
Rehabilitation of native habitats and removal of invasive species	Nutrients retention, Climate change mitigation
Improvement of river crossings to allow natural flow of river	Flood mitigation

Figure 25 Map of the Sorraia catchment sub-basins included in the cost-benefit analysis

Scenarios

Baseline scenario

In this scenario it was assumed that the present land use continues without any changes. No restoration measures were simulated in this scenario.

Restoration up-scaling scenario

This scenario focuses on establishing 509 hectares of riparian forest buffer strips along selected channels of the Sorraia river (Figure 2). To estimate the area of restoration, we used ARCGISPRO Model builder to create a layer of riparian buffer strips to be established on agricultural land adjacent to waterways in the Sorraia catchment. These buffer strips are approximately 20 meter wide, following Van Der Laan et al., (2023). To model the effects of those riparian buffer strips, land cover and land use of hydrological response units overlapping planned riparian buffer strips are changed from irrigated croplands and pastures into forested riparian buffer strips (see Garcia et al., 2025).

Figure 26 Location of Riparian Buffer Development

Restoration costs

Data and method

Investment costs in the restoration scenario were obtained by multiplying the area of restored riparian buffer strips by unit investment costs of restoration per hectare. Unit investment costs were derived from the implementation plan of this case study (Gerner et al., 2023) (Table 2).

To estimate recurring costs, we assumed that total maintenance and monitoring costs per hectare represented 10% of investment costs per hectare, spread over the time needed to complete restoration to a fully functional riparian forest (Frimpong et al., 2006; Ghimire et al., 2022). This time was assumed to be 19 years following Angiolini et al. (2023). The recurring costs per unit area were 23.48 €/ha/year in 2024 prices (Table 2).

Table 44 Data sources used for the estimation of investment and recurring costs for riparian buffer development

Land use	Investment unit costs		Recurring unit costs	
	Value	Source	Value	Source
Irrigated cropland and pastures	€ 4461.34 / ha in 2024 prices (€ 204,000 for 48.85 ha in 2022 prices)	(Gerner et al., 2023; MERLIN, n.d.-a)	€ 23.48 / ha / year (2024 prices)	(Frimpong et al., 2006; Ghimire et al., 2022)

To derive the opportunity cost (€ 1.21 million / year in 2024 prices), we calculated the monetary value of agricultural output at farm-gate price, in €/ha in 2024 prices, from the foregone agricultural production (Table 3). We determined pre-restoration land use of areas converted to buffer strips using detailed crop data for the year 2021, provided by Scholten (2022) with permission from local water users association Associação De Regantes E Beneficiários Do Vale De Sorraia (ARBVS). In locations where this detailed crop data was unavailable, we relied on generic crop classes from the COS2018 land use database (DG Território, 2018). The resulting summarized areas per crop type were then multiplied by Standard Output Coefficients for each crop type (average for Portugal), defined as ‘the average monetary value of agricultural output at farm-gate price, in €/ha in 2024 prices (ESTAT, 2024). The opportunity cost for other land uses was assumed to be zero.

Table 45 Data sources for the estimation of opportunity costs of riparian buffer development

Land use	Opportunity unit costs	
	Value (€ / ha in 2024 prices)	Source
Agriculture with natural and semi-natural spaces	2518.37*	(ESTAT, 2024)
Rice fields	2098.62	(ESTAT, 2024)
Temporary dryland and irrigated crops	5036.73**	(ESTAT, 2024)
Temporary crops and/or improved pastures associated with olive groves	5036.73**	(ESTAT, 2024)
Eucalyptus forests	251.94	(Lopes, 2013)
Maritime pine forests	157.46	(Lopes, 2013)
Stone pine forests	157.46	(Lopes, 2013)
Cork oak forests	95.25	(Corona et al., 2018)
Olive groves	633.85	(ESTAT, 2024)
Improved pastures	357.94	(ESTAT, 2024)
Stone pine agroforestry systems	157.46	(Lopes, 2013)
Cork oak agroforestry systems	95.25	(Corona et al., 2018)
Vineyards	2522	(ESTAT, 2024)

* Assumed 50% less production due to natural and semi-natural spaces

**Weighted average of value (assumed) irrigated crops from area covered with detailed crop data

Results

Total investment costs were estimated at € 2.27 million (Table 4), recurring costs at € 11,941.47 / year (Table 5), and opportunity costs at € 1.21 million / year (Table 6).

Table 46 Total investment costs for riparian buffer development

Land use	Area restored	Investment unit costs	Total investment costs
Irrigated cropland and pastures	508.57 ha	€ 4461.34 / ha (2024 prices)	€ 2.27 million (2024 prices)

Table 47 Total recurring costs for riparian buffer development

Land use	Area restored	Recurring unit costs	Total recurring costs
Irrigated cropland and pastures	508.57 ha	€ 23.48 / ha / year (2024 prices)	€ 11,941.47 / year (2024 prices)

Table 48 Total opportunity costs for riparian buffer development

Land use	Area restored	Opportunity unit costs (€ / ha / year in 2024 prices)	Total Opportunity costs (€ / year in 2024 prices)
Agriculture with natural and semi-natural spaces	0.84	2518.37*	2122.23
Rice fields	0.78	2098.62	1644.08
Temporary dryland and irrigated crops	231.93	5036.73**	1,168,194.35
Temporary crops and/or improved pastures associated with olive groves	0.35	5036.73**	1782.38
Eucalyptus forests	1.66	251.94	419.00
Maritime pine forests	1.27	157.46	200.07
Stone pine forests	4.79	157.46	753.81
Cork oak forests	7.82	95.25	744.49
Olive groves	1.65	633.85	1045.36
Improved pastures	74.38	357.94	26,625.31
Stone pine agroforestry systems	0.05	157.46	7.66
Cork oak agroforestry systems	12.12	95.25	1154.34
Vineyards	3.35	2522	8444.55
Other land use	167.56	0	0
All	508.56		1.21 million / year (2024 prices)

Flood risks mitigation benefits

Riparian buffer strips do not have an effect on the attenuation of peak flows in channels but may act as physical barriers protecting riparian areas from channel overflows. However, this potential effect of riparian buffer strips on flood mitigation could not be modelled with the modelling workflow developed by MERLIN, which is focused on the attenuation of peak flows in channels.

Nutrients retention benefits

Data and method

Nutrient retention benefits were estimated following the approach detailed in Annex II of this report.

In biophysical terms, the service was quantified in terms of change in total nutrients exports (in tons) and change in nutrients concentration (in mg/L) from the Sorraia river basin. Nitrogen and Phosphorous exports and concentrations were calculated using SWAT+ outputs for the baseline and restoration scenarios.

The monetary valuation was based on the replacement cost approach, using constructed wetlands (CW) as a replacement alternative to restoration. Replacement CW area was calculated as a function of the water flow leaving the outlet channel of the catchment, and the ratio of baseline scenario nutrients concentration over restoration scenario nutrients concentration in the outlet channel of the catchment. The effect of restoration was valued as the net present value of the investment requested to build the replacement CW.

Results

The relative effect of restoration on nutrients retention is small, around 2% of reduction in phosphorus exports or concentration and less than 0.5% reduction in nitrogen exports/concentration (Table 7). The monetary benefits are estimated at 6760 € per year (2024 prices) considering nitrogen and 82 K€ per year (2024 prices) considering phosphorous, corresponding to 24.14 € per kg of nitrogen retained and 2055.95 € per kg of phosphorous retained (Table 8).

Table 49 Effects of restoration on nutrient retention in biophysical terms

	Baseline scenario	Restoration scenario	Restoration effect	
			Mass/Concentration	% change
Total N exports (in tons)	336.84	336.56	-0.28	-0.08%
Total P exports (in tons)	2.15	2.11	-0.04	-1.86%
Average N concentration (in mg/L)	2.279	2.277	-0.002	-0.09%
Average P concentration (in mg/L)	0.0146	0.0143	-0.0003	-2.06%

Table 50 Effects of restoration on nutrients retention in monetary terms

Nutrients retention benefits provided by landscape units	Nitrogen Purification Benefits (€ / year in 2024 prices)	Phosphorus Purification Benefits (€ / year in 2024 prices)
Total	6760	82238
Per kg of nutrient retained	24.14	2055.95

Climate change mitigation benefits

Data and method

Carbon dioxide emissions in the baseline were estimated using the average value of emission factors of croplands and pastures following Chang et al. (2015) and Ciais et al. (2010) (Table 9). The emissions of riparian forests were estimated using the emission factor from Abdul Malak et al., (2021) and Villa & Bernal (2018) (Table 9). The total GHG emissions were estimated by multiplying the total area to be restored (508.57 ha) by the corresponding emission factors. It was assumed that emission factors for each land use class remain stable over the entire time horizon of the CBA (100 years).

Table 51 Data sources used to estimate climate change mitigation benefits

Data	Description/Value	Source/Publisher
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Land use map: "hrus.shp"	A land use map of Sorraia basin with 18 land use categories	ICRA – SWAT+
Carbon emission factor in Restoration scenario	Carbon sequestration rate of riparian forests: -1.76 tonnes CO ₂ e/ha/year	(Abdul Malak et al., 2021; Villa & Bernal, 2018)
Carbon emission factor in Baseline scenario	Average of carbon sequestration rates of croplands and of pastures: 0.18 tonnes CO ₂ e/ha/year	(Chang et al., 2015; Ciais et al., 2010)
The Economic Appraisal of Investment Projects at the EIB	Guidance document to conduct economic appraisals recommends social costs of carbon.	Table 4-1 of (European Investment Bank., 2023)

GHG emissions were valued using the social cost of carbon values recommended by the Economic Appraisal of Investment Projects at the EIB (European Investment Bank., 2023). The values were adjusted according to the inflation rate in Portugal between 2016 and 2024 (World Bank Group, n.d.) (Table 10). The value of GHG emissions after 2050 was assumed to remain constant at the 2050 level.

Table 52 Social Cost of Carbon adjusted to 2024 prices based on inflation in Portugal (Table 4-1 European Investment Bank (2023))

Social cost of carbon (€ / ton CO ₂ e in 2024 prices)	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
	95.85	197.70	299.55	467.29	629.04	790.80	958.54

Results

The development of riparian buffers in the Sorraia catchment results in 986.62 tons of CO₂e emissions avoided per year, corresponding to a total net present value of € 10.81 million over the whole CBA time span (Table 11).

Table 53 GHG sequestration of the baseline and restoration scenarios

Land use	Emission factor (tCO ₂ e/ha/yr)	Baseline scenario		Restoration scenario	
		Area (ha)	Emissions (tCO ₂ e/yr)	Area (ha)	Emissions (tCO ₂ e/yr)
Irrigated cropland and pastures	0.18	508.57	91.54	0	0
Riparian forest buffer strip	-1.76	0	0	508.57	-895.07
Total		508.57	91.54	508.57	-895.07

Cost Benefit Analysis outcomes

Data and method

For the restoration scenario, it was assumed that restoration measures would start in 2025 and be completed by 2035. Studies have found that full biophysical effects of riparian forest restoration are realised when left undisturbed for 19 years (Angiolini et al., 2023). Following these estimates, it was assumed that the benefits of restoration would grow linearly from zero % in restoration year to 100 % 19 years after restoration. To simplify calculations, we took the mid-year of restoration works (2031) as the first year when benefits start flowing. Full benefits were then realized from 2049 onwards.

To account for the long-term benefits realised from restoration, a timeline of 100 years was used. The European commission's guide to cost-benefit analysis recommends a social discount rate of 5% for cohesion countries (which includes Portugal) (European Commission, 2015). However, Baumgärtner et al. (2015) recommends using a discount rate that is 0.9% ± 0.3% below the social discount rate for manufactured goods, creating a reduction range of 0.6% to 1.2% (Baumgärtner et al., 2015).

We applied a declining discount rate because of the uncertainty around economic conditions over such a long timeline, which prompts precautionary planning (Freeman et al., 2018; Gollier, 2012). Following this approach, we started with a discount rate of 4.4% (5% - 0.6%) till year 33, declining linearly to 3.8% (5% - 1.2%) for years

67 to 100 (Table 12). This declining rate reflects both the ecosystem service-specific adjustments recommended by Baumgärtner et al. (2015) and the growing uncertainty over longer timelines.

Table 54 Table of declining discount rates used in the cost-benefit analysis

Year (Year 1 is 2024)	1-33	34-66	67-100
Discount rate	4.4%	4.1%	3.8%

Results

The net present value of restoration of the Sorraia catchment is negative € 17.82 million in 2024 prices. The benefit-cost ratio is 0.40 and the internal rate of return is -4.74% (Table 13).

Table 13 Table of results of the cost-benefit analysis

Incremental Costs	Present Value (million € in 2024 prices)
Total restoration costs	29.67
Incremental Benefits	Present Value (million € in 2024 prices)
Flood Risk Mitigation	Not estimated
Nutrients Retention	1.04
Climate Change Mitigation	10.81
CBA Results	
Net Present Value (million € in 2024 prices)	-17.82
Benefit-Cost Ratio	0.40
Internal Rate of Return	-4.74%

Discussion and conclusion

This CBA shows a negative net present value, indicating that the analysed restoration scenario does not provide enough societal benefit to match the restoration costs. However, it is worth noting that our CBA is a first rapid cost and benefit assessment, based on a limited scope of ecosystem services, which did not include several potential benefits of riparian buffer strips:

- **Local climate regulation:** Vegetation can locally reduce air temperature and increase humidity (Castellano 2022). Although this effect is local, riparian buffer strips can act as biodiversity shelter, especially relevant in semi-arid zones. Shade provided to the river channel by riparian zones moderate fluctuations in water temperatures, buffering eutrophication and improving water quality.
- **Erosion reduction:** By increasing stability of riverbanks and capturing sediments in overland flow, riparian buffers strips reduce erosion. In the downstream part of the valley, this in turn reduces inflow of sediments to the river. Due to lack of flushing from the reservoirs, these sediments tend to accumulate, in turn slowing flow, which contributes to growth of invasive species.
- **Biodiversity: habitat provision:** Riparian buffer strips nestled in agricultural landscapes represent a small portion of crop-intensive area, but can contribute significantly to the biodiversity, in turn supporting several crucial ecological processes.
- **Landscape aesthetics:** The introduction of riparian buffer strips adds to the diversity and greening of the landscape: in general, such linear landscape elements enhance the visual appeal of the landscape.
- **Natural pest control:** Riparian buffer strips provide a habitat for insects, e.g. arthropods (Perennes et al., 2023) that provide natural pest control to cropland, potentially increasing the yield.
- **Crop pollination:** Riparian buffer strips also provide a habitat for pollinating insects. Though most crops grown in the Sorraia catchment do not require insect pollination, there are some exceptions, notably pumpkins and almonds.

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Annex 8: CBA of MERLIN CS 04 – Room for the Rhine branches

The CBA of the MERLIN CS04 – Room for the Rhine branches – has been published in two scientific papers:

Kok, S., Le Clec'h, S., Penning, W. E., Buijse, A. D., & Hein, L. (2025). Trade-offs in ecosystem services under various river management strategies of the Rhine Branches. *Ecosystem Services*, 72, 10169–2. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2024.101692>

Kok, S., Hein, L., le Clec'h, S., Penning, W. E., & Buijse, A. D. (submitted). Room for the River: An extended cost benefit analysis of integrated river-floodplain management for the Rhine in the Netherlands. *Ecosystem Services*.